

Curiosity's Mars Hand Lens Imager (MAHLI) Mars Science Laboratory (MSL) Principal Investigator's Notebook: Sols 3903–3999

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Mars Science Laboratory (MSL) Mars Hand Lens Imager (MAHLI) Technical Report 0036

Cover photo

MAHLI view of a target with pinstripe laminations and a dark vein called Kolpos Megaron, acquired on Sol 3909 in full shadow. This is MAHLI image 3909MH0001900011401806C00.

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7.1 Definitions and conventions

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Acknowledgements

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Note that pages are not numbered in this document because all of the *Range and Scale Information Sheets*, *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets*, and *MAHLI Image Comment Sheets* were inserted separately after creation using a word processing tool that differs from the one used for the text.

Abstract

Covering the time between Curiosity’s 3903rd and 3999th Martian days (sols) of operations in northern Gale crater, Mars, this document is a compilation of the Mars Science Laboratory (MSL) Mars Hand Lens Imager (MAHLI) Team’s notes and information about MAHLI images and activities conducted during that period. The report includes brief sol-by-sol notes—written as the mission unfolded—regarding how the MAHLI instrument was used and significant events that occurred which impacted the MAHLI instrument or investigation. The document, further, contains information regarding range and scale (camera working distance and scale of in-focus elements of an image); the parent images, range, and scale information associated with each MAHLI focus merge product created onboard the instrument; and a description of the purpose and intent behind acquisition of each MAHLI image and creation of each onboard focus merge product. The MSL science team and rover engineers routinely used the information contained in this report during the course of the mission for tactical planning, strategic planning, and scientific analysis.

1 Introduction

1.1 Introduction and purpose

This document is a compilation of the Mars Hand Lens Imager (MAHLI) Team’s notes and information about MAHLI images and activities that occurred during the Mars Science Laboratory (MSL) mission between Sols 3903 and 3999.

MAHLI is a 2-megapixel color camera with a focusable macro lens mounted on the turret at the end of a robotic arm aboard NASA’s MSL rover, Curiosity (Edgett *et al.* 2012). The rover landed and began operation in northern Gale crater, Mars, on 6 August 2012 (Vasavada *et al.* 2014).

Each *Curiosity’s Mars Hand Lens Imager (MAHLI) Mars Science Laboratory (MSL) Principal Investigator’s Notebook* covers a specific period corresponding to a release of MAHLI data to the NASA Planetary Data System (PDS) Imaging Node (<http://pds-imaging.jpl.nasa.gov/>). As some MAHLI data can arrive from Mars months or years after a given release period, the publication of these reports typically lags behind the PDS release schedule by a period that varies from one occasion to the next, depending largely on when data acquired during that period arrive on Earth and when we have time to complete the *Principal Investigator’s Notebook* report.

This report, *Curiosity’s Mars Hand Lens Imager (MAHLI) Mars Science Laboratory (MSL) Principal Investigator’s Notebook: Sols 3903–3999*, corresponds to MAHLI data Release 35 in the NASA PDS archives. These are data acquired 29 July 2023 through 06 November 2023.

1.2 Versions and change log

The enclosed materials were compiled as the MSL mission unfolded. That being the case, we might sometimes have made errors. The reader should be aware that this report might be corrected via release of a new version in the future.

A new version would also be created if new data from this report’s period (Martian sols) are received from the instrument after an earlier version has been made available. This can occur because MAHLI can store data onboard the instrument for an indefinite period of time after acquisition. As a result, images are archived with the NASA PDS on the basis of when they are received on Earth, not when they are acquired on Mars.

Covering the Sol 3903 through 3999 period, this document is Version 1.

If this were a later version, this section would document the changes made relative to the previous.

2 Instrument activities for this period

This section captures day-by-day or sol-by-sol notes written by the MAHLI Team, as the mission unfolded, regarding how the MAHLI instrument was used or significant events that occurred which impacted the MAHLI instrument or investigation.

MAHLI Activities During Sols 3903 – 3999						
milestone or field site	date (UTC)	Sol	camera positions	Parent images	Onboard focus merges	Notes
Heading towards the base of the upper Gediz Vallis ridge	31 Jul 23	3904	0	0	3	Focus stack images from Sol 3902 were merged.
Heading towards the base of the upper Gediz Vallis ridge	01 Aug 23	3905	3	22	2	MAHLI imaged the target Novo_Paraiso and the focus stack images were merged.
	02 Aug 23	3906	4	32	3	MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed target Kefalonia and the focus stack images were merged.
	03 Aug 23	3907	8	64	0	MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed target Samaria and the target Kythira.
	04 Aug 23	3908	0	0	6	Focus stack images from Sol 3907 were merged.
	05 Aug 23	3909	7	54	0	MAHLI imaged the target Kolpos Megaron and the DRT-brushed target Sopoto.
	06 Aug 23	3910	0	0	5	Focus stack images from Sol 3909 were merged.
	08 Aug 23	3912	4	32	3	MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed target Ouranoupoli and the focus stack images were merged.
	10 Aug 23	3914	4	32	3	MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed target Skepato and the focus stack images were merged.
	12 Aug 23	3916	11	54	0	MAHLI imaged the DRT brushed target Ntourtourvana.
	13 Aug 23	3917	0	0	4	Focus stack images from Sol 3916 were merged.
At the base of the upper Gediz Vallis ridge	17 Aug 23	3921	7	62	6	MAHLI imaged the targets Kamenianoi and Eleftheroupoli. The focus stack images were also merged.
	23 Aug 23	3926	12	104	10	MAHLI imaged the target DRT-brushed target Mytikas, acquired a 1x4 vertical mosaic on Mytikas, and imaged the target Helmos. The focus stack images were also merged.
	25 Aug 23	3928	7	54	5	MAHLI imaged the targets Epidaurus and Limni Stymfalia. The focus stack images were also merged.
	27 Aug 23	3930	11	86	0	MAHLI imaged the targets Meteora, Styx and Knossos.
Heading towards the Sequoia/ Sequoia2 drill site	28 Aug 23	3931	0	0	8	Focus stack images from Sol 3930 were merged.
	31 Aug 23	3934	3	22	2	MAHLI imaged the target Paion and the focus stack images were merged.
Heading towards the Sequoia/ Sequoia2 drill site	03 Sep 23	3937	13	74	0	MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed targets Areopoli and Artemisio.
	04 Sep 23	3938	0	0	6	Focus stack images from Sol 3937 were merged.
	09 Sep 23	3943	7	54	5	MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed target Hydra and the target Dodoni. The focus stack images were also merged.

MAHLI Activities During Sols 3903 – 3999						
milestone or field site	date (UTC)	Sol	camera positions	Parent images	Onboard focus merges	Notes
Heading towards the Sequoia/ Sequoia2 drill site	12 Sep 23	3946	4	32	3	MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed target Antikythera and the focus stack images were merged.
	14 Sep 23	3948	4	32	3	MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed target Mosquito Flat and the focus stack images were merged.
	19 Sep 23	3953	0	0	3	The focus stack images from Sol 3948 were merged again; this happened because a fault occurred onboard the rover that prevented acquisition and merge of new MAHLI data planned for the DRT-brushed target Sugarloaf.
	21 Sep 23	3955	6	52	5	MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed target Sugarloaf (brushed on Sol 3953) and acquired a 2x1 mosaic of the target Toms Place.
	26 Sep 23/ 27 Sep 23	3960	4	24	2	MAHLI imaged the target Silver_Spur and the REMS UV Sensor. The focus stack images were also merged.
	29 Sep 23	3962	10	53	4	MAHLI imaged the targets Burnt Mountain and Blackcap Mountain as well as the MAHLI and APXS calibration targets. The focus stack images were also merged.
Heading towards the Sequoia/ Sequoia2 drill site	01 Oct 23	3964	8	64	6	MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed targets Cloudripper and White Pass. The focus stack images were also merged.
	03 Oct 23	3966	7	46	0	MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed target Burnt Mountain and the target Bearpaw Meadow.
	04 Oct 23	3967	0	0	4	Focus stack images from Sol 3966 were merged.
	05 Oct 23	3968	7	54	0	MAHLI imaged the targets Helen_Lake and Marion Peak.
	06 Oct 23	3969	0	0	5	Focus stack images from Sol 3968 were merged.
	08 Oct 23	3971	11	86	0	MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed target Helen_Lake and the targets Feather_Peak and Heart_Lake.
	09 Oct 23	3972	0	8	16	Focus stack images from Sol 3971 were merged.
At the Sequoia/ Sequoia2 drill site	12 Oct 23	3975	8	48	4	MAHLI imaged the intended drill target Sequoia before and after DRT and after a drill bit preload test. The focus stack images were merged as well.
	15 Oct 23	3978	6	44	4	MAHLI imaged the intended drill target Sequoia2 before and after a drill bit preload test. The focus stack images were merged as well.

3 Helpful tips

3.1 MAHLI instrument and investigation

Please refer to Edgett *et al.* (2012) for a description of the MAHLI instrument and investigation, Edgett *et al.* (2015) for information about the characterization and calibration of the instrument, and Yingst *et al.* (2016) for some of the lessons learned after ~1.5 Mars years of surface operations. Additional information on how the instrument and data have been used is in the paper by Minitti *et al.* (2013) and the extended abstract by Garvin *et al.* (2017).

3.2 MAHLI image IDs

MAHLI images and onboard focus merge products are identified by their image IDs. The following figure describes the information content of these IDs.

Note that raw images released within minutes of receipt on Earth to the public via the JPL-Caltech web site (<http://mars.jpl.nasa.gov/msl/multimedia/raw/>) do not necessarily have the correct, final, archival image IDs.

MAHLI Image IDs

- This is the only official, correct, archival image ID scheme.
- Raw Images released rapidly at <http://mars.jpl.nasa.gov/msl/multimedia/raw/> do not always give you the correct, archival image ID.

0132MH001580010101221C00

sol → 0132
camera (MH = MAHLI) → MH
CDPID (a.k.a. MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID) → 001580010101
product type (as received from Mars) → C00

sequence ID → 001580010101
order in sequence (usually, first = 0, second = 1, etc.) → 001580010101
CDPID counter (How many times the following CDPID has been used since landing) → 001580010101
version (version received on Earth, 0 = parent image on Mars) → 001580010101
GOP counter (for video Group of Pictures (JPEG video frames)) → 001580010101

Note that, for onboard focus merge products, the sol is the sol that the merge took place. This is **not** always on the same sol that the parent images were acquired.

The MAHLI team pays most attention to the items in yellow. In a focus stack, the images are acquired in order of increasing CDPID.

Product type tells you about the image as received from Mars; not necessarily the image you are looking at, if it has been further processed, uncompressed, or recompressed on Earth.

The NASA PDS archives include documentation that describes the MAHLI image ID and file naming scheme and the nature of the archived Experiment Data Record (EDR) and Reduced Data Record (RDR) products (Malin *et al.*, 2013).

The EDR products, the raw data product, have the following file name scheme:

- 1 **[Image ID]_XXXX** – these are always 8-bit images except for the 16-bit products (type A) returned from MAHLI for calibration purposes.

The RDR products are of the following nature:

- 2 **[Image ID]_DRXX** – 16-bit depth (per band) relative radiometric calibrated color images,
- 3 **[Image ID]_DRLX** – 16-bit depth (per band) relative radiometric calibrated and geometric calibrated color images,
- 4 **[Image ID]_DRCX** – 8-bit relative radiometric calibrated images for which a color correction has been applied, and
- 5 **[Image ID]_DRCL** – 8-bit relative radiometric and geometric calibrated images for which a color correction has been applied.

The following table describes the variety of image types (raw, lossless, JPEG, focus merge, thumbnail, *etc.*). Malin *et al.* (2013) described these in greater detail.

product type	product format
A	raster 16-bit image
B	raster 8-bit image
C	lossless compressed image
D	JPEG grayscale image
E	JPEG 4:2:2 color image
F	JPEG 4:4:4 color image
G	raster thumbnail of parent image
H	JPEG gray thumbnail of parent image
I	JPEG 4:4:4 thumbnail of parent image
J	raster 8-bit video frame
K	lossless compressed video frame
L	JPEG grayscale video frame
M	JPEG 4:2:2 color video frame
N	JPEG 4:4:4 color video frame
O	raster 8-bit thumbnail of video frame
P	JPEG gray thumbnail of video frame
Q	JPEG 4:4:4 thumbnail of video frame
R	focus merge best focus image product
S	focus merge range map product
T	focus merge best focus thumbnail
U	focus merge range map thumbnail

Types R and T are JPEG 4:4:4; S and U are JPEG grayscale products.

3.3 MAHLI LED positions

The MAHLI camera head has two groups of two white light LEDs (Edgett *et al.* 2012), called Group 1 and Group 2. For reference, the figure below shows their location on the camera head and how these locations translate to positions relative to pixel 0,0 (column 0, row 0) on the MAHLI CCD. In addition, MAHLI has two 365 nm ultraviolet (UV) LEDs, also shown in the figure. Each group of two LEDs (Group 1, Group 2, and UV) can be operated together or independently with each of the other two groups. When the LEDs are used, which group was operated is reported in the RATIONALE_DESC description of the image intent and purpose (Section 6).

MAHLI image TVC_MH0809080020000032B00, left, shows the violet and white reflections of the UV and Group 1 and Group 2 white light LEDs, indicating their location in relation to the CCD's pixel at column 0, row 0. The photograph on the right shows the camera head with its dust cover open and LEDs labeled.

4 Camera range and scale information

4.1 Purpose and description

MAHLI *Range and Scale Information Sheets* (or “Distance and Scale Information Sheets”) describe **(a)** the distance between the MAHLI camera and an imaged target, and **(b)** the scale of in-focus features in the image, based on knowledge of that distance. Usually, these are determined using the camera’s stepper motor count focus position (Edgett *et al.* 2015).

These information sheets were created only for cases in which there was a need. Cases for which they are not usually created include those when the only MAHLI image(s) acquired on a given sol are **(a)** views of the landscape, focused at infinity; **(b)** intended to make a rover self-portrait mosaic; **(c)** sky flat field calibration data; or **(d)** routinely-acquired images of the rover wheels for inspection purposes.

For the Sol 3903–3999 period, *Range and Scale Information Sheets* were created for the following **Sols: 3905, 3906, 3907, 3909, 3912, 3914, 3916, 3921, 3926, 3928, 3930, 3934, 3937, 3943, 3946, 3948, 3955, 3960, 3962, 3964, 3966, 3968, 3971, 3975, 3978.**

The origin of the MAHLI *Range and Scale Information Sheets* was in the need for a rapid, tactical response from the MAHLI team to the Curiosity Rover Planners—the engineers tasked with operating the rover’s mobility and robotic arm systems—for range-finding and image scale information derived from MAHLI’s autofocus and focus merge capabilities. As described by Minitti *et al.* (2013), during the rover’s first sample extraction campaign, conducted at the Rocknest eolian sand deposit in October–November 2012, the engineers elected to use MAHLI autofocus sub-frames to confirm their estimates of the range to the sand surface for subsequent scoop placement (Anderson *et al.* 2015). These *Range and Scale Information Sheets* were borne of that effort to provide the information almost as soon as the data arrived on Earth.

Presented in this section are the latest versions of the *Range and Scale Information Sheets*, for the above stated sols, as of the date of this *MAHLI Technical Report* publication. Most of these sheets were actively used during the MSL mission for tactical and strategic planning, as well as for the scientific analyses. Note that some of the sheets exhibit slightly different formatting from each other, as the formatting and content evolved over time.

The image IDs presented in these Information Sheets are the identifiers of the best, least-compressed version of the image received from Mars for a given camera position for the stated purpose (autofocus, imaging, range-finding, etc.). In cases for which only a thumbnail version of the image was received, the image ID is colored orange.

4.2 Formulae

4.2.1 Working distance

The working distance (d_w , in centimeters) presented in the *Range and Scale Information Sheets* was computed from the empirical relationship between working distance and motor count for the flight unit MAHLI when the dust cover is open (m_{open}) described by Edgett *et al.* (2015):

$$d_w = (am_{open}^{-1} + b + cm_{open} + dm_{open}^2 + em_{open}^3)^{-1}, \quad (1)$$

in which $a = 0.576786$, $b = -11.8479$, $c = 2.80153 \times 10^{-3}$, $d = -2.266488 \times 10^{-7}$, and $e = 6.26666 \times 10^{-12}$.

For the dust cover closed case (m_{closed}), Edgett *et al.* (2015) found that m_{closed} is related to m_{open} as follows:

$$m_{closed} = 17075 - m_{open}. \quad (2)$$

4.2.2 Standoff distance (RP distance; MAHLI toolframe +X distance)

The standoff distance (d_s , in centimeters) presented in the *Range and Scale Information Sheets* is 1.9 cm less than the MAHLI working distance (Edgett *et al.* 2015). Note that “standoff distance” is equivalent to “RP distance” and “MAHLI toolframe +X distance”; see **Section 7.1**). It is determined by subtracting 1.9 cm from the working distance (d_w) computed from motor count:

$$d_s = d_w - 1.9 \text{ cm} \quad (3)$$

4.2.3 Distance or range uncertainty estimate

Estimation approach applied to the Sol 0–945 *Range and Scale Information Sheets*

For the Sol 0–945 period (except Sol 687), the uncertainty in distance (whether expressed as d_w or d_s) was estimated using an early version of our team’s understanding (Edgett *et al.* 2013) of the flight unit MAHLI depth of field (DOF; d_{old_DOF} , in centimeters) as a function of working distance (d_w).

The method for estimating the far range of the DOF, d_{old_far} , was:

$$d_{old_far} = ad_w^5 - bd_w^4 + cd_w^3 + dd_w^2 + ed_w - f \quad (4)$$

in which $a = 2.067963396 \times 10^{-10}$, $b = 5.81503025785 \times 10^{-8}$, $c = 1.55563715379086 \times 10^{-5}$, $d = 1.78558768966003 \times 10^{-3}$, $e = 7.87243271888297 \times 10^{-3}$, and $f = 3.57047935299353 \times 10^{-2}$.

The method for estimating the near range of the DOF, d_{old_near} , was:

$$d_{old_near} = -(ad_w^5 + bd_w^4 - cd_w^3 + dd_w^2 - ed_w + f) \quad (5)$$

in which $a = -9.6497783 \times 10^{-12}$, $b = 1.06050131902 \times 10^{-8}$, $c = 5.8615047292452 \times 10^{-6}$, $d = 2.42284468424977 \times 10^{-3}$, $e = 4.28714139095939 \times 10^{-3}$, and $f = 7.534391000189 \times 10^{-4}$.

The MAHLI *Range and Scale Information Sheets* added the absolute values of the near and far DOF, then divided by two, to provide an overall uncertainty, $\pm d_{old_DOF}$, in centimeters:

$$\pm d_{old_DOF} = ((-d_{old_near}) + d_{old_far})/2 \quad (6)$$

The $\pm d_{old_DOF}$ estimate was sufficient for using MAHLI as a range finder for subsequent scoop placement during the Rocknest sample extraction campaign (Minitti *et al.* 2013; Anderson *et al.* 2015).

Improved estimation method, used for Sol 687 and after Sol 945 *Range and Scale Information Sheets*

Later analysis refined our DOF estimate (Edgett *et al.* 2015), but these results arrived too late to be incorporated into most of the Sol 0–945 *Range and Scale Information Sheets*. That said, for small working distances (e.g., < 20 cm), the results are about the same. As a function of dust cover open focus motor count (m_{open}), the near (d_{near}) and far (d_{far}) depth of field can be expressed, in centimeters, as:

$$d_{near} \text{ or } d_{far} = (am_{open}^{-1} + b + cm_{open} + dm_{open}^2 + em_{open}^3)^{-1}, \quad (7)$$

in which, for d_{near} , $a = 1.03565$, $b = -11.9083$, $c = 2.82403 \times 10^{-3}$, $d = -2.29003 \times 10^{-7}$, and $e = 6.34332 \times 10^{-12}$; and, for d_{far} , $a = 1.03438$, $b = -11.4118$, $c = 2.69297 \times 10^{-3}$, $d = -2.17752 \times 10^{-7}$, and $e = 6.02494 \times 10^{-12}$.

4.2.4 Pixel scale

The estimated pixel scale (p , in μm per pixel) is based on working distance (d_w) and applies only to the in-focus portions of a given image. We estimate the scale from the working distance (d_w) as described by Edgett *et al.* (2012):

$$p = 6.9001 + 3.5201d_w. \quad (8)$$

4.2.5 Pixel scale uncertainty estimate

No estimation applied to the Sol 0–998 range and scale information sheets

No estimate of pixel scale uncertainty was applied to the MAHLI *Range and Scale Information Sheets* until Sol 999.

Estimation approach

Pixel scale uncertainty (p_{far} , p_{near} , $\pm p_{uncertainty}$, in μm per pixel) can be estimated based on the depth of field (d_{far} , d_{near} , in centimeters; **Equation 7**) and pixel scale (p , in μm per pixel, **Equation 8**) as determined from working distance (d_w , in centimeters; **Equation 1**). The uncertainty applies only to the in-focus portions of a given image. The uncertainty can be estimated as follows (please round $\pm p_{uncertainty}$ to the nearest 0.1 μm per pixel):

$$p_{far} = (6.9001 + 3.5201(d_w + d_{far})) - p, \quad (9)$$

$$p_{near} = p - (6.9001 + 3.5201(d_w + d_{near})), \text{ and} \quad (10)$$

$$\pm p_{\text{uncertainty}} = (p_{\text{far}} + p_{\text{near}})/2. \quad (11)$$

4.2.6 Image dimensions estimate

The image dimension estimates described in the MAHLI *Range and Scale Information Sheets* are computed by multiplying the estimated pixel scale (p) by the number of horizontal (columns) and vertical (rows) covered by the image. This simplistic approach, of course, assumes that the target is a plane parallel to the CCD.

UPDATED: 01_August_2023

SOL 3905 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA _PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE ($\mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY ($\pm \mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ- ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named Novo_Paraiso														
mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm											
	3905MH0001900011401666C00	1666	13019	26.4	24.5	-1.8	2.0	99.8	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0	
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm											
	3905MH0001680011401668C00	1668	14017	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			3905MH0002650001401689R00			RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					3905MH0002650001401690S00
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm											
	3905MH0001680011401678C00	1678	14039	6.6	4.7	-0.2	0.1	30.1	0.5	1608	1198	4.8	3.6	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			3905MH0002650001401687R00			RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					3905MH0002650001401688S00

UPDATED: 02_August_2023

SOL 3906 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGEY ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA _PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE ($\mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY ($\pm \mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ- ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named Kefalonia – after DRT															
mhlI00190	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm												
	3906MH0001900011401692C00	1692	13019	26.4	24.5	-1.8	2.0	99.8	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0		
mhlI00168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	3906MH0001680011401694C00	1694	14004	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3906MH0001930001401727R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3906MH0001930001401726S00
mhlI00168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	3906MH0001680011401704C00	1704	14008	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3906MH0001930001401725R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3906MH0001930001401726S00
mhlI00743	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 1 cm												
	3906MH0007430011401714C00	1714	15122	2.8	0.9	-0.1	0.1	16.7	0.2	1608	1198	2.7	2.0		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3906MH0001930001401723R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3906MH0001930001401724S00

SOL 3907 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named Samaria – after DRT

mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm											
	3907MH0001900011401730C00	1730	13020	26.3	24.4	-1.7	2.0	99.6	6.5	1608	1198	16.0	11.9	
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm											
	3907MH0001680011401732C00	1732	14015	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3908MH0001630001401803R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3908MH0001630001401804S00
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm											
	3907MH0001680011401742C00	1742	14015	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3908MH0001630001401801R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3908MH0001630001401802S00
mhl100743	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 15 mm											
	3907MH0007430011401752C00	1752	14928	3.2	1.3	-0.1	0.1	18.2	0.2	1608	1198	2.9	2.2	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3908MH0001630001401799R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3908MH0001630001401800S00

target named Kythira

mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm											
	3907MH0001900011401762C00	1762	13016	26.6	24.7	-1.8	2.0	100.5	6.7	1608	1198	16.2	12.0	
mhl100182	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm											
	3907MH0001820011401764C00	1764	13999	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3908MH0001630001401797R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3908MH0001630001401798S00
mhl100182	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm											
	3907MH0001820011401774C00	1774	14003	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3908MH0001630001401795R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3908MH0001630001401796S00
mhl100426	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 1 cm											
	3907MH0004260011401784C00	1784	15154	2.7	0.8	0.0	0.1	16.5	0.2	1608	1198	2.7	2.0	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3908MH0001630001401793R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3908MH0001630001401794S00

SOL 3909 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named **Kolpos_Megaron**

mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm												
	3909MH0001900011401806C00	1806	13022	26.2	24.3	-1.7	2.0	99.2	6.5	1608	1198	16.0	11.9		
mhl100224	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	3909MH0002240011401808C00	1808	14076	6.4	4.5	-0.1	0.1	29.3	0.5	1608	1198	4.7	3.5		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3910MH0002270001401867R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3910MH0002270001401868S00	
mhl100224	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	3909MH0002240011401818C00	1818	14140	6.0	4.1	-0.1	0.1	28.0	0.5	1608	1198	4.5	3.4		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3910MH0002270001401865R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3910MH0002270001401866S00	

target named **Sopoto – after DRT**

mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm												
	3909MH0001900011401828C00	1828	13015	26.6	24.7	-1.8	2.0	100.7	6.7	1608	1198	16.2	12.1		
mhl100182	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	3909MH0001820011401830C00	1830	13963	7.1	5.2	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.1	3.8		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3910MH0002270001401863R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3910MH0002270001401864S00	
mhl100182	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	3909MH0001820011401840C00	1840	13981	7.0	5.1	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	1608	1198	5.1	3.8		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3910MH0002270001401861R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3910MH0002270001401862S00	
mhl100426	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 15 mm												
	3909MH0004260011401850C00	1850	14795	3.5	1.6	-0.1	0.1	19.3	0.2	1608	1198	3.1	2.3		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3910MH0002270001401859R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3910MH0002270001401860S00	

UPDATED: 09_August_2023

SOL 3912 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named Ouranoupoli – after DRT															
mhl00190	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm												
	3912MH0001900011401870C00	1870	13015	26.6	24.7	-1.8	2.0	100.7	6.7	1608	1198	16.2	12.1		
mhl00182	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	3912MH0001820011401872C00	1872	13968	7.1	5.2	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	1608	1198	5.1	3.8		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3912MH0001930001401905R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3912MH0001930001401906S00
mhl00182	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	3912MH0001820011401882C00	1882	13962	7.1	5.2	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.1	3.8		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3912MH0001930001401903R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3912MH0001930001401904S00
mhl00796	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 1 cm												
	3912MH0007960011401892C00	1892	14979	3.1	1.2	-0.1	0.1	17.8	0.2	1608	1198	2.9	2.1		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3912MH0001930001401901R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3912MH0001930001401902S00

UPDATED: 10_August_2023

SOL 3914 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA _PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE ($\mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY ($\pm \mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ- ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named <i>Skepasto</i> – after DRT															
mhl00190	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm												
	3914MH0001900011401908C00	1908	13018	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.0	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0		
mhl00168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	3914MH0001680011401910C00	1910	13990	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			3914MH0001930001401943R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					3914MH0001930001401944S00	
mhl00168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	3914MH0001680011401920C00	1920	13992	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			3914MH0001930001401941R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					3914MH0001930001401942S00	
mhl00743	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 1 cm												
	3914MH0007430011401930C00	1930	15085	2.9	1.0	-0.1	0.1	17.0	0.2	1608	1198	2.7	2.0		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			3914MH0001930001401939R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					3914MH0001930001401940S00	

SOL 3916 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named Ntourntourvana – before DRT

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)	PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)
mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW			INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm									
	3916MH0001900011401946C00	1946	13019	26.4	24.5	-1.8	2.0	99.8	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0
mhl100122	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION VIEW			INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm									
	3916MH0001220011401948C00	1948	14016	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7

target named Ntourntourvana – after DRT

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)	PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)
mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW			INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm									
	3916MH0001900011401950C00	1950	13019	26.4	24.5	-1.8	2.0	99.8	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1			INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm									
	APXS RASTER SPOT 2												
	3916MH0001680011401952C00	1952	14016	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3917MH0001530001402005R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		3917MH0001530001402006S00					
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2			INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm									
	APXS RASTER SPOT 2												
	3916MH0001680011401962C00	1962	14015	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3917MH0001530001402003R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		3917MH0001530001402004S00					
mhl100864	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW			INTENDED STANDOFF – 1 cm									
	APXS RASTER SPOT 2												
	3916MH0008640011401972C00	1972	15164	2.7	0.8	0.0	0.1	16.4	0.2	1608	1198	2.6	2.0
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3917MH0001530001402001R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		3917MH0001530001402002S00					
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION VIEW			INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm									
	APXS RASTER SPOT 1												
	3916MH0001680011401982C00	1982	14007	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3917MH0001530001401999R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		3917MH0001530001402000S00					

target named Ntourntourvana – a 4 x 1 mosaic

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)	PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)
mhl100148	POSITION 1 OF 4			INTENDED STANDOFF – 10 cm									
	3916MH0001480011401992C00	1992	13576	10.8	8.9	-0.3	0.3	44.8	1.2	1608	1198	7.2	5.4
mhl100148	POSITION 2 OF 4			INTENDED STANDOFF – 10 cm									
	3916MH0001480011401994C00	1994	13614	10.3	8.4	-0.3	0.3	43.2	1.1	1608	1198	6.9	5.2
mhl100148	POSITION 3 OF 4			INTENDED STANDOFF – 10 cm									
	3916MH0001480011401996C00	1996	13612	10.3	8.4	-0.3	0.3	43.2	1.1	1608	1198	7.0	5.2
mhl100148	POSITION 4 OF 4			INTENDED STANDOFF – 10 cm									
	3916MH0001480011401998C00	1998	13618	10.3	8.4	-0.3	0.3	43.0	1.1	1608	1198	6.9	5.1

SOL 3921 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGEETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named **Kamenianoi**

mhli00865	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 25 cm											
	3921MH0008650011402008C00	2008	13015	26.6	24.7	-1.8	2.0	100.7	6.7	1608	1198	16.2	12.1
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3921MH0001630001402079R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3921MH0001630001402080S00	
mhli00308	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 5 cm											
	3921MH0003080011402018C00	2018	13972	7.0	5.1	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	1608	1198	5.1	3.8
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3921MH0001630001402077R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3921MH0001630001402078S00	
mhli00308	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 5 cm											
	3921MH0003080011402028C00	2028	13987	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3921MH0001630001402075R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3921MH0001630001402076S00	
mhli00405	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 3 cm											
	3921MH0004050011402038C00	2038	14338	5.1	3.2	-0.1	0.1	24.7	0.4	1608	1198	4.0	3.0
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3921MH0001630001402073R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3921MH0001630001402074S00	

target named **Eleftheroupoli**

mhli00190	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 25 cm											
	3921MH0001900011402048C00	2048	13022	26.2	24.3	-1.7	2.0	99.2	6.5	1608	1198	16.0	11.9
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3921MH0001630001402071R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3921MH0001630001402072S00	
mhli00168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 5 cm											
	3921MH0001680011402050C00	2050	14071	6.4	4.5	-0.1	0.1	29.4	0.5	1608	1198	4.7	3.5
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3921MH0001630001402071R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3921MH0001630001402072S00	
mhli00168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 5 cm											
	3921MH0001680011402060C00	2060	14069	6.4	4.5	-0.1	0.1	29.5	0.5	1608	1198	4.7	3.5
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3921MH0001630001402069R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3921MH0001630001402070S00	

SOL 3926 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

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 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named Mytikas – after DRT

mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm											
	3926MH0001900011402082C00	2082	13018	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.0	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0
mhl100182	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm											
	3926MH0001820011402084C00	2084	13996	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT: 3926MH0003690001402203R00			RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 3926MH0003690001402204S00								
mhl100182	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm											
	3926MH0001820011402094C00	2094	13995	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT: 3926MH0003690001402201R00			RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 3926MH0003690001402202S00								
mhl100386	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 1 cm											
	3926MH0003860011402104C00	2104	15077	2.9	1.0	-0.1	0.1	17.0	0.2	1608	1198	2.7	2.0
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT: 3926MH0003690001402199R00			RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 3926MH0003690001402200S00								

target named Mytikas – a 1 x 4 mosaic

mhl100152	POSITION 1 OF 4	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm											
	3926MH0001520011402114C00	2114	14120	6.1	4.2	-0.1	0.1	28.4	0.5	1608	1198	4.6	3.4
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT: 3926MH0003690001402197R00			RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 3926MH0003690001402198S00								
mhl100152	POSITION 2 OF 4	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm											
	3926MH0001520011402124C00	2124	14120	6.1	4.2	-0.1	0.1	28.4	0.5	1608	1198	4.6	3.4
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT: 3926MH0003690001402195R00			RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 3926MH0003690001402196S00								
mhl100152	POSITION 3 OF 4	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm											
	3926MH0001520011402134C00	2134	14164	5.9	4.0	-0.1	0.1	27.6	0.4	1608	1198	4.4	3.3
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT: 3926MH0003690001402193R00			RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 3926MH0003690001402194S00								
mhl100152	POSITION 4 OF 4	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm											
	3926MH0001520011402144C00	2144	14224	5.6	3.7	-0.1	0.1	26.5	0.4	1608	1198	4.3	3.2
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT: 3926MH0003690001402191R00			RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 3926MH0003690001402192S00								

target named Helmos

mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm											
	3926MH0001900011402154C00	2154	13018	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.0	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0
mhl100299	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm											
	3926MH0002990011402156C00	2156	13994	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT: 3926MH0003690001402189R00			RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 3926MH0003690001402190S00								
mhl100299	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm											
	3926MH0002990011402166C00	2166	13998	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT: 3926MH0003690001402187R00			RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 3926MH0003690001402188S00								
mhl100176	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 2 cm											
	3926MH0001760011402176C00	2176	14674	3.9	2.0	-0.1	0.1	20.5	0.3	1608	1198	3.3	2.5
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT: 3926MH0003690001402185R00			RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 3926MH0003690001402186S00								

SOL 3928 - MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

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 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named Epidaurus

mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF - 25 cm													
	3928MH0001900011402206C00	2206	13016	26.6	24.7	-1.8	2.0	100.5	6.7	1608	1198	16.2	12.0		
mhl100173	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm													
	3928MH0001730011402208C00	2208	13994	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			3928MH0002270001402267R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					3928MH0002270001402268S00	
mhl100173	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm													
	3928MH0001730011402218C00	2218	13998	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			3928MH0002270001402265R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					3928MH0002270001402266S00	
mhl100176	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF - 2 cm													
	3928MH0001760011402228C00	2228	14686	3.8	1.9	-0.1	0.1	20.4	0.3	1608	1198	3.3	2.4		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			3928MH0002270001402263R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					3928MH0002270001402264S00	

target named Limni_Stymfalia

mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF - 25 cm													
	3928MH0001900011402238C00	2238	13036	25.4	23.5	-1.6	1.8	96.3	6.1	1608	1198	15.5	11.5		
mhl100173	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm													
	3928MH0001730011402240C00	2240	14220	5.6	3.7	-0.1	0.1	26.6	0.4	1608	1198	4.3	3.2		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			3928MH0002270001402261R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					3928MH0002270001402262S00	
mhl100173	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm													
	3928MH0001730011402250C00	2250	14220	5.6	3.7	-0.1	0.1	26.6	0.4	1608	1198	4.3	3.2		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			3928MH0002270001402259R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					3928MH0002270001402260S00	

SOL 3930 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

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SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named Meteora															
mhl00148	INTERMEDIATE-RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 10 cm													
	3930MH0001480011402270C00	2270	13508	11.7	9.8	-0.4	0.4	48.2	1.4	1608	1198	7.7	5.8		
mhl00173	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	3930MH0001730011402272C00	2272	14029	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.1	30.3	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.6		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			3931MH0001700001402369R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					3931MH0001700001402370S00	
mhl00173	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	3930MH0001730011402282C00	2282	14034	6.6	4.7	-0.2	0.1	30.2	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.6		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			3931MH0001700001402367R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					3931MH0001700001402368S00	
mhl00716	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 1 cm													
	3930MH0007160011402292C00	2292	15174	2.7	0.8	0.0	0.1	16.4	0.2	1608	1198	2.6	2.0		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			3931MH0001700001402365R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					3931MH0001700001402365S00	

target named Styx															
mhl00190	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm													
	3930MH0001900011402302C00	2302	13032	25.6	23.7	-1.7	1.9	97.1	6.2	1608	1198	15.6	11.6		
mhl00849	INTERMEDIATE-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF – 15 cm													
	3930MH0008490011402304C00	2304	13340	14.8	12.9	-0.6	0.6	58.9	2.1	1608	1198	9.5	7.1		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			3931MH0001700001402369R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					3931MH0001700001402364S00	
mhl00849	INTERMEDIATE-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF – 15 cm													
	3930MH0008490011402314C00	2314	13309	15.5	13.6	-0.6	0.7	61.4	2.3	1608	1198	9.9	7.3		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			3931MH0001700001402361R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					3931MH0001700001402362S00	

target named Knossos															
mhl00190	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm													
	3930MH0001900011402324C00	2324	13010	27.0	25.1	-1.8	2.1	101.8	6.9	1608	1198	16.4	12.2		
mhl00182	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	3930MH0001820011402326C00	2326	13975	7.0	5.1	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	1608	1198	5.1	3.8		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			3931MH0001700001402359R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					3931MH0001700001402360S00	
mhl00182	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	3930MH0001820011402336C00	2336	13962	7.1	5.2	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.1	3.8		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			3931MH0001700001402357R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					3931MH0001700001402358S00	
mhl00864	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 1 cm													
	3930MH0008640011402346C00	2346	14972	3.1	1.2	-0.1	0.1	17.8	0.2	1608	1198	2.9	2.1		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			3931MH0001700001402355R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					3931MH0001700001402356S00	

UPDATED: 01_September_2023

SOL 3934 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

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 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGEY ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA _PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE ($\mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY ($\pm \mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ- ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named Paion															
mhl00190	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm													
	3934MH001900011402372C00	2372	13020	26.3	24.4	-1.7	2.0	99.6	6.5	1608	1198	16.0	11.9		
mhl00182	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	3934MH001820011402374C00	2374	14058	6.5	4.6	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	1608	1198	4.8	3.6		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:	3934MH002650001402395R00					RANGE MAP PRODUCT:							3934MH002650001402396S00
mhl00182	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	3934MH001820011402384C00	2384	14059	6.5	4.6	-0.1	0.1	29.7	0.5	1608	1198	4.8	3.6		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:	3934MH002650001402393R00					RANGE MAP PRODUCT:							3934MH002650001402394S00

SOL 3937 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

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 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named **Areopoli** – before DRT

mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm										
	3937MH0001900011402398C00	2398	13016	26.6	24.7	-1.8	2.0	100.5	6.7	1608	1198	16.2	12.0
mhl100122	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm										
	3937MH0001220011402400C00	2400	13952	7.2	5.3	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	1608	1198	5.2	3.9

target named **Areopoli** – after DRT – quantitative relief model (QRM) data

mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm												
	3937MH0001900011402402C00	2402	13015	26.6	24.7	-1.8	2.0	100.7	6.7	1608	1198	16.2	12.1		
mhl100168	MED RES – STEREO-2 & RELIEF MODEL POSITION 1		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	3937MH0001680011402404C00	2404	13950	7.2	5.3	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	1608	1198	5.2	3.9		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3938MH0001630001402481R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3938MH0001630001402482S00	
mhl100168	MED RES – STEREO-2 & RELIEF MODEL POSITION 2		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	3937MH0001680011402414C00	2414	13962	7.1	5.2	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.1	3.8		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3938MH0001630001402479R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3938MH0001630001402480S00	
mhl100705	MED RES – RELIEF MODEL POSITION 3		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	3937MH0007050011402424C00	2424	13957	7.1	5.2	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	1608	1198	5.1	3.8		
mhl100705	MED RES – RELIEF MODEL POSITION 4		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	3937MH0007050011402426C00	2426	13948	7.2	5.3	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	1608	1198	5.2	3.9		
mhl100705	MED RES – RELIEF MODEL POSITION 5		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	3937MH0007050011402428C00	2428	13956	7.1	5.2	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	1608	1198	5.2	3.8		
mhl100743	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 1 cm												
	3937MH0007430011402430C00	2430	14963	3.1	1.2	-0.1	0.1	17.9	0.2	1608	1198	2.9	2.1		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3938MH0001630001402477R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3938MH0001630001402478S00	

target named **Artemisio** – after DRT

mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm												
	3937MH0001900011402440C00	2440	13011	26.9	25.0	-1.8	2.1	101.6	6.8	1608	1198	16.3	12.2		
mhl100182	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	3937MH0001820011402442C00	2442	13955	7.1	5.2	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	1608	1198	5.2	3.8		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3938MH0001630001402475R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3938MH0001630001402476S00	
mhl100182	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	3937MH0001820011402452C00	2452	13956	7.1	5.2	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	1608	1198	5.2	3.8		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3938MH0001630001402473R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3938MH0001630001402474S00	
mhl100426	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 1 cm												
	3937MH0004260011402462C00	2462	14973	3.1	1.2	-0.1	0.1	17.8	0.2	1608	1198	2.9	2.1		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3938MH0001630001402471R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3938MH0001630001402472S00	

SOL 3943 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named Hydra – after DRT

mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm												
	3943MH0001900011402484C00	2484	13018	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.0	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0		
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	3943MH0001680011402486C00	2486	14039	6.6	4.7	-0.2	0.1	30.1	0.5	1608	1198	4.8	3.6		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3943MH0002270001402545R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3943MH0002270001402546S00	
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	3943MH0001680011402496C00	2496	14007	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3943MH0002270001402543R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3943MH0002270001402544S00	
mhl100302	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 2 cm												
	3943MH0003020011402506C00	2506	14679	3.8	1.9	-0.1	0.1	20.4	0.3	1608	1198	3.3	2.4		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3943MH0002270001402541R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3943MH0002270001402542S00	

target named Dodoni

mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm												
	3943MH0001900011402516C00	2516	13011	26.9	25.0	-1.8	2.1	101.6	6.8	1608	1198	16.3	12.2		
mhl100306	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	3943MH0003060011402518C00	2518	14002	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3943MH0002270001402539R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3943MH0002270001402540S00	
mhl100306	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	3943MH0003060011402528C00	2528	14003	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3943MH0002270001402537R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3943MH0002270001402538S00	

UPDATED: 14_September_2023

SOL 3946 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA _PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE ($\mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY ($\pm \mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ- ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named <i>Antikythera</i> – after DRT													
mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW			INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm									
	3946MH0001900011402548C00	2548	13016	26.6	24.7	-1.8	2.0	100.5	6.7	1608	1198	16.2	12.0
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1			INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm									
	3946MH0001680011402550C00	2550	13999	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:	3946MH0001930001402583R00	RANGE MAP PRODUCT:									
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2			INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm									
	3946MH0001680011402560C00	2560	14005	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:	3946MH0001930001402581R00	RANGE MAP PRODUCT:									
mhl100302	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW			INTENDED STANDOFF – 2 cm									
	3946MH0003020011402570C00	2570	14700	3.8	1.9	-0.1	0.1	20.2	0.3	1608	1198	3.3	2.4
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:	3946MH0001930001402579R00	RANGE MAP PRODUCT:									

UPDATED: 20_September_2023

SOL 3948 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3790.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA _PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE ($\mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY ($\pm \mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ- ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named Mosquito_Flat – after DRT														
mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm											
	3948MH0001900011402586C00	2586	13017	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.3	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0	
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm											
	3948MH0001680011402588C00	2588	13994	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3948MH0001930001402621R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:				3948MH0001930001402622S00	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3953MH0001930001402627R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:				3953MH0001930001402628S00	
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm											
	3948MH0001680011402598C00	2598	13993	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3948MH0001930001402619R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:				3948MH0001930001402620S00	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3953MH0001930001402625R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:				3953MH0001930001402626S00	
mhl100864	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 15 mm											
	3948MH0008640011402608C00	2608	14852	3.4	1.5	-0.1	0.1	18.8	0.2	1608	1198	3.0	2.3	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3948MH0001930001402617R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:				3948MH0001930001402618S00	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3953MH0001930001402623R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:				3953MH0001930001402624S00	

SOL 3955 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named **Sugarloaf** – after DRT

mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm												
	3955MH0001900011402630C00	2630	13019	26.4	24.5	-1.8	2.0	99.8	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0	
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	3955MH0001680011402632C00	2632	14026	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.1	30.4	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.6	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3955MH0002270001402689R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3955MH0002270001402690S00
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	3955MH0001680011402642C00	2642	14023	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.1	30.5	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3955MH0002270001402687R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3955MH0002270001402688S00
mhl100743	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 1 cm												
	3955MH0007430011402652C00	2652	15184	2.7	0.8	0.0	0.1	16.3	0.2	1608	1198	2.6	2.0	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3955MH0002270001402685R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3955MH0002270001402686S00

target named **Toms_Place** – a 2 x 1 mosaic

mhl100865	POSITION 1 OF 2	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm												
	3955MH0008650011402662C00	2662	13017	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.3	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3955MH0002270001402683R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3955MH0002270001402684S00
mhl100865	POSITION 2 OF 2	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm												
	3955MH0008650011402672C00	2672	12985	28.6	26.7	-2.0	2.3	107.6	7.7	1608	1198	17.3	12.9	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3955MH0002270001402681R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3955MH0002270001402682S00

UPDATED: 27_September_2023

SOL 3960 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA _PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE ($\mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY ($\pm \mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ- ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named Silver_Spur

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA _PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)	PIXEL SCALE ($\mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY ($\pm \mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$)	HORIZ- ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)	
mhl00190	CONTEXT VIEW			INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 25 cm										
	3960MH0001900011402692C00	2692	13019	26.4	24.5	-1.8	2.0	99.8	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0	
mhl00182	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1			INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 5 cm										
	3960MH0001820011402694C00	2694	14014	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3960MH0002650001402717R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3960MH0002650001402718S00
mhl00182	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2			INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 5 cm										
	3960MH0001820011402704C00	2704	14030	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.1	30.3	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.6	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3960MH0002650001402715R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3960MH0002650001402716S00

REMS UV sensor

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA _PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)	PIXEL SCALE ($\mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY ($\pm \mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$)	HORIZ- ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)
mhl00095	STANDARD VIEWING POSITION			INTENDED STANDOFF: ~15 cm									
	3960MH0000950011402714C00	2714	13260	16.7	14.8	-0.7	0.8	65.7	2.7	1608	1198	10.6	7.9

SOL 3962 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named **Burnt_Mountain** – before DRT

mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm												
	3962MH0001900011402720C00	2720	13019	26.4	24.5	-1.8	2.0	99.8	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0		
mhl100173	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	3962MH0001730011402722C00	2722	14025	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.1	30.4	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.6		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3962MH0001530001402778R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3962MH0001530001402779S00	
mhl100173	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	3962MH0001730011402732C00	2732	14016	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3962MH0001530001402776R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3962MH0001530001402775S00	

target named **Blackcap_Mountain**

mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm												
	3962MH0001900011402742C00	2742	13017	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.3	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0		
mhl100224	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	3962MH0002240011402744C00	2744	13990	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3962MH0001530001402774R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3962MH0001530001402775S00	
mhl100224	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	3962MH0002240011402754C00	2754	13994	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3962MH0001530001402772R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3962MH0001530001402773S00	

MAHLI calibration target

NOTE: ONE CAN ALSO USE FEATURES IN THESE IMAGES TO DETERMINE SCALE; THE SCALE INFORMATION PRESENTED HERE IS BASED ON MOTOR COUNT, NOT ANALYSIS OF THE IMAGES.

mhl100371	BAR TARGET – 5 cm WORKING DISTANCE												
	3962MH0003710011402764C00	2764	14375	4.9	3.0	-0.1	0.1	24.1	0.4	1608	1198	3.9	2.9
mhl100372	CENT TARGET – 5 cm WORKING DISTANCE												
	3962MH0003720011402766C00	2766	14368	4.9	3.0	-0.1	0.1	24.2	0.4	1608	1198	3.9	2.9
mhl100374	CALIBRATION TARGET + FRONT LEFT WHEEL + SURFACE – 30 cm WORKING DISTANCE												
	AUTOFOCUS ON CALIBRATION TARGET												
	3962MH0003740011402768C00	2768	12963	30.2	28.3	-2.3	2.6	113.3	8.6	1608	1198	18.2	13.6
mhl100374	MANUAL INFINITY FOCUS												
	3962MH0003740021402769C00	2769	12552	(INFINITY)	(INFINITY)	(INFINITY)	(INFINITY)	(INFINITY)	(INFINITY)	1608	1198	(INFINITY)	(INFINITY)

APXS calibration target

NOTE: ONE CAN ALSO USE FEATURES IN THESE IMAGE(S) TO DETERMINE SCALE; THE SCALE INFORMATION PRESENTED HERE IS BASED ON MOTOR COUNT, NOT ANALYSIS OF THE IMAGE(S).

mhl100373	6.9 cm WORKING DISTANCE												
	3962MH0003730011402771C00	2771	13946	7.2	5.3	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	1608	1198	5.2	3.9

SOL 3964 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named **Clouddripper** – after DRT

mhlI00190	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm										
	3964MH0001900011402781C00	2781	13019	26.4	24.5	-1.8	2.0	99.8	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0
mhlI00336	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm										
	3964MH0003360011402783C00	2783	14009	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:	3964MH0001630001402854R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:								
mhlI00336	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm										
	3964MH0003360011402793C00	2793	14017	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:	3964MH0001630001402852R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:								
mhlI00848	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 1 cm										
	3964MH0008480011402803C00	2803	15134	2.8	0.9	-0.1	0.1	16.6	0.2	1608	1198	2.7	2.0
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:	3964MH0001630001402850R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:								

target named **White Pass** – after DRT

mhlI00190	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm										
	3964MH0001900011402813C00	2813	13019	26.4	24.5	-1.8	2.0	99.8	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0
mhlI00168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm										
	3964MH0001680011402815C00	2815	14016	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:	3964MH0001630001402848R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:								
mhlI00168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm										
	3964MH0001680011402825C00	2825	14018	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:	3964MH0001630001402846R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:								
mhlI00743	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 1 cm										
	3964MH0007430011402835C00	2835	15142	2.8	0.9	0.0	0.1	16.6	0.2	1608	1198	2.7	2.0
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:	3964MH0001630001402844R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:								

UPDATED: 04_October_2023

SOL 3966 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGEY ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13148/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named **Burnt_Mountain** – before DRT

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE	PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)
mhl00190	CONTEXT VIEW			INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm								
	3966MH0001900011402857C00	2857	13021	26.3	24.4	-1.7	2.0	99.4	6.5	1608	1198	16.0
mhl00122	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION VIEW			INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm								
	3966MH0001220011402859C00	2859	14050	6.5	4.6	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	1608	1198	4.8

target named **Burnt_Mountain** – after DRT

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE	PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)	
mhl00190	CONTEXT VIEW			INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm									
	3966MH0001900011402861C00	2861	13020	26.3	24.4	-1.7	2.0	99.6	6.5	1608	1198	16.0	11.9
mhl00168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1			INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm									
	3966MH0001680011402863C00	2863	14044	6.6	4.7	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	1608	1198	4.8	3.6
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:				BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3967MH0001530001402908R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		3967MH0001530001402909S00			
mhl00168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2			INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm									
	3966MH0001680011402873C00	2873	14042	6.6	4.7	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	1608	1198	4.8	3.6
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:				BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3967MH0001530001402906R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		3967MH0001530001402907S00			
mhl00743	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW			INTENDED STANDOFF – 1 cm									
	3966MH0007430011402883C00	2883	15233	2.6	0.7	0.0	0.1	16.0	0.2	1608	1198	2.6	1.9
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:				BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3967MH0001530001402904R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		3967MH0001530001402905S00			

target named **Bearpaw_Meadow**

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE	PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)	
mhl00168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION VIEW			INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm									
	3966MH0001680011402893C00	2893	13994	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:				BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3967MH0001530001402902R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		3967MH0001530001402903S00			

SOL 3968 - MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

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 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named **Helen_Lake** - before DRT

mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF - 25 cm												
	3968MH0001900011402911C00	2911	13017	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.3	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0	
mhl100182	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm												
	3968MH0001820011402913C00	2913	13986	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.8	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3969MH0002270001402972R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3969MH0002270001402973S00
mhl100182	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm												
	3968MH0001820011402923C00	2923	13989	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3969MH0002270001402970R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3969MH0002270001402971S00
mhl100337	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF - 2 cm												
	3968MH0003370011402933C00	2933	14642	4.0	2.1	-0.1	0.1	20.8	0.3	1608	1198	3.3	2.5	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3969MH0002270001402968R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3969MH0002270001402969S00

target named **Marion_Peak**

mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF - 25 cm												
	3968MH0001900011402943C00	2943	13024	26.1	24.2	-1.7	1.9	98.8	6.4	1608	1198	15.9	11.8	
mhl100182	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm												
	3968MH0001820011402945C00	2945	14095	6.3	4.4	-0.1	0.1	28.9	0.5	1608	1198	4.7	3.5	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3969MH0002270001402966R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3969MH0002270001402967S00
mhl100182	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm												
	3968MH0001820011402955C00	2955	14099	6.2	4.3	-0.1	0.1	28.9	0.5	1608	1198	4.6	3.5	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3969MH0002270001402964R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3969MH0002270001402965S00

SOL 3971 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named **Helen_Lake** – after DRT

mhl00190	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm													
	3971MH0001900011402975C00	2975	13017	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.3	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0		
mhl00168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	3971MH0001680011402977C00	2977	13985	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.8		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3972MH0001700001403074R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3972MH0001700001403075S00	
mhl00168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	3971MH0001680011402987C00	2987	13989	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3972MH0001700001403072R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3972MH0001700001403073S00	
mhl00302	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 2 cm													
	3971MH0003020011402997C00	2997	14644	3.9	2.0	-0.1	0.1	20.8	0.3	1608	1198	3.3	2.5		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3972MH0001700001403070R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3972MH0001700001403071S00	

target named **Feather_Peak**

mhl00190	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm													
	3971MH0001900011403007C00	3007	13027	25.9	24.0	-1.7	1.9	98.2	6.3	1608	1198	15.8	11.8		
mhl00168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	3971MH0001680011403009C00	3009	14128	6.1	4.2	-0.1	0.1	28.3	0.5	1608	1198	4.5	3.4		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3972MH0001700001403068R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3972MH0001700001403069S00	
mhl00168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	3971MH0001680011403019C00	3019	14127	6.1	4.2	-0.1	0.1	28.3	0.5	1608	1198	4.6	3.4		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3972MH0001700001403066R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3972MH0001700001403067S00	

target named **Heart_Lake**

mhl00190	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm													
	3971MH0001900011403029C00	3029	13020	26.3	24.4	-1.7	2.0	99.6	6.5	1608	1198	16.0	11.9		
mhl00168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	3971MH0001680011403031C00	3031	14009	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3972MH0001700001403064R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3972MH0001700001403065S00	
mhl00168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	3971MH0001680011403041C00	3041	14008	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3972MH0001700001403062R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3972MH0001700001403063S00	
mhl00743	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 1 cm													
	3971MH0007430011403051C00	3051	15148	2.7	0.8	0.0	0.1	16.6	0.2	1608	1198	2.7	2.0		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3972MH0001700001403060R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3972MH0001700001403061S00	

SOL 3975 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

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 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13148/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

intended drill target named Sequoia – before DRT

intended drill target named Sequoia – before DRT													
mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm											
	3975MH0001900011403077C00	3077	13016	26.6	24.7	-1.8	2.0	100.5	6.7	1608	1198	16.2	12.0
mhl100122	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm											
	3975MH0001220011403079C00	3079	13988	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7

intended drill target named Sequoia – after DRT

intended drill target named Sequoia – after DRT															
mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm													
	3975MH0001900011403081C00	3081	13015	26.6	24.7	-1.8	2.0	100.7	6.7	1608	1198	16.2	12.1		
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	APXS RASTER SPOT 2														
	3975MH0001680011403083C00	3083	13987	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3975MH0001530001403130R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3975MH0001530001403131S00	
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	APXS RASTER SPOT 2														
	3975MH0001680011403093C00	3093	13988	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3975MH0001530001403128R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3975MH0001530001403129S00	
mhl100302	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 2 cm													
	APXS RASTER SPOT 2														
	3975MH0003020011403103C00	3103	14648	3.9	2.0	-0.1	0.1	20.8	0.3	1608	1198	3.3	2.5		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3975MH0001530001403126R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3975MH0001530001403127S00	
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	APXS RASTER SPOT 1														
	3975MH0001680011403113C00	3113	13978	7.0	5.1	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	1608	1198	5.1	3.8		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3975MH0001530001403124R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3975MH0001530001403125S00	

intended drill target named Sequoia – after drill bit pre-load test

intended drill target named Sequoia – after drill bit pre-load test													
mhl100465	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 35 cm											
	3975MH0004650011403123C00	3123	12895	36.5	34.6	-3.3	3.9	135.3	12.7	1608	1198	21.8	16.2

UPDATED: 16_October_2023

SOL 3978 - MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13148/R6.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

intended drill target named Sequoia2 - after sol 3975 DRT - after sol 3975 drill bit pre-load test

mhl00190	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF - 25 cm													
	3978MH0001900011403133C00	3133	13018	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.0	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0		
mhl00168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm													
	APXS RASTER SPOT 2														
	3978MH0001680011403135C00	3135	13992	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3978MH0001530001403182R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3978MH0001530001403183S00	
mhl00168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm													
	APXS RASTER SPOT 2														
	3978MH0001680011403145C00	3145	13993	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3978MH0001530001403180R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3978MH0001530001403181S00	
mhl00302	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF - 2 cm													
	APXS RASTER SPOT 2														
	3978MH0003020011403155C00	3155	14666	3.9	2.0	-0.1	0.1	20.6	0.3	1608	1198	3.3	2.5		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3978MH0001530001403178R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3978MH0001530001403179S00	
mhl00168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm													
	APXS RASTER SPOT 1														
	3978MH0001680011403165C00	3165	13998	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		3978MH0001530001403176R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						3978MH0001530001403177S00	

intended drill target named Sequoia2 - after sol 3978 drill bit pre-load test

mhl00465	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF - 35 cm											
	3978MH0004650011403175C00	3175	12895	36.5	34.6	-3.3	3.9	135.3	12.7	1608	1198	21.8	16.2

5 Focus merge product information

5.1 Purpose and description

The MAHLI *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets* provide information about the best focus and range map products created by focus merges performed onboard the MAHLI instrument.

The information includes:

1. thumbnail images representing the appearance of each best focus and range map product;
2. a brief title or description of the image target and purpose;
3. the Sol and date (UTC) that the merged parent images were acquired;
4. the Sol on which the focus merge took place,
5. image IDs for the focus merge products and a corresponding full-frame image;
6. the MAHLI command sequence that acquired the parent images and the command sequence that created the focus merge products;
7. the commanded stack depth; that is, the number of parent images acquired in a given focus stack;
8. the type of focus stack (relative or absolute; see definitions in **Section 7**);
9. a list of the thumbnail image IDs for the parent images acquired in the focus stack (because, in some cases, these are the only versions of the focus stack images that are received on Earth);
10. the focus position (stepper motor count) for each parent image in the focus stack;
11. the range and range uncertainty determined from the focus position (motor count) of each parent image; and
12. the grayscale DN value corresponding to each parent image motor count and range in the focus merge range map product.

Further, for each parent image, the *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets* state whether any of the full-size images (Individual Focus Stack Images) were received on Earth, listing:

13. the image ID of the full-size parent or child image, if received on Earth;
14. the date on which the full-size image was received (applicable only to *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets* for the period between Sol 0 and 946 after that, with the exception of Sol 930, this practice was abandoned as unnecessary);

15. the compression quality of the best version of the image, if received on Earth (this practice was later abandoned as unnecessary); and
16. a statement regarding the fate of parent images not received on Earth; that is, the Sol on which the parent was deleted from the data storage inside the instrument’s digital electronics assembly (DEA).

Each MAHLI *Focus Merge Product Information Sheet* is identified by the Sol on which the parent images were acquired. The onboard merge, in some cases, might have been performed on a later sol.

The parent images identified in rows that are colored orange, if they have a corresponding DN value in a yellow-colored column, are those that participated in the creation of the focus merge product. In other words, those that are in white rows (for which there is a corresponding DN in the yellow column) had no in-focus elements and thus were not incorporated into the merged product, even if they had been commanded to be merged. Which images were commanded to be merged can be determined by the yellow-colored column that indicates the corresponding DN values in the range map image product; for cases in which the commanded focus stack depth is > 8 , the corresponding DN values (yellow-colored column) will indicate the 8 commanded to be merged (the instrument cannot merge > 8 but it can acquire > 8 images in a focus stack).

In cases in which the focus stack parent images were returned to Earth, the data user has the option to perform a new focus merge using software approaches available on Earth, now or in the future, which might outperform the MAHLI onboard algorithm. The user also has the opportunity, in these cases, to improve each parent image before performing the merge (e.g., remove blemishes, perform flat field correction, etc.).

When a > 8 image focus stack has been acquired, the orange-colored rows can *also* indicate recommendations for images that would contain in-focus elements and could be added to a future focus merge product, whether performed onboard MAHLI or on Earth after receipt of the full-size images. Those images that are recommended, but were not merged onboard, have no “Corresponding DN in Range Map” in the yellow, rightmost columns of the *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets*.

For the Sol 3903–3999 period, focus stacks that were merged onboard the instrument were acquired on **Sols 3905, 3906, 3907, 3909, 3912, 3914, 3916, 3921, 3926, 3928, 3930, 3934, 3937, 3943, 3946, 3948, 3955, 3960, 3962, 3964, 3966, 3968, 3971, 3975, 3978**. Unless otherwise stated, the onboard focus merges performed during this period were all of the “basic” type (see Edgett *et al.* 2012; Edgett *et al.* 2015).

5.2 Formulae

5.2.1 Range

When acquiring a focus stack, the MAHLI camera head is held in a fixed position. This means that the working distance (d_w) — and corresponding standoff distance (d_s) — is constant (see **Section 5.2.5**). However, each image acquired in a focus stack is done so at a different focus position; that is, a different stepper motor count position (m_{open} or m_{closed} ; usually m_{open}). That

motor count is related to the range (r_{fm}) between the front lens element of the camera and the in-focus elements of the image by the same empirical formula (**Equation 1**) as applied to determine working distance from motor count. In centimeters,

$$r_{fm} = (am_{open}^{-1} + b + cm_{open} + dm_{open}^2 + em_{open}^3)^{-1}, \quad (12)$$

in which $a = 0.576786$, $b = -11.8479$, $c = 2.80153 \times 10^{-3}$, $d = -2.266488 \times 10^{-7}$, and $e = 6.26666 \times 10^{-12}$.

For each parent image in a given focus stack, this range is given in the green-colored column on the right side of each MAHLI *Focus Merge Product Information Sheet*.

5.2.2 Range uncertainty estimate

The uncertainty ($\pm r_{uncertainty}$, in centimeters) in the computed range (r_{fm}) is estimated using depth of field as related to the corresponding range (via motor count; **Equation 12**) for each merged parent image. The range uncertainty estimate is noted in the light green column on the lower right side of each MAHLI *Focus Merge Product Information Sheet*.

Focus Merge Product Information Sheets in which the relevant column is labeled “Estimated Range Uncertainty”

For MAHLI *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets* created before Sol 942, our estimate of range uncertainty was based on the older (Edgett *et al.* 2013) depth of field equations described in **Section 4.2.3, Equations 4, 5, and 6**, in which we substituted r_{fm} for d_w .

Focus Merge Product Information Sheets in which the relevant column is labeled “Depth of Field”

For MAHLI *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets* created starting with Sol 942, we used the refined knowledge of MAHLI depth of field, described by Edgett *et al.* (2015) and in **Equation 7** of **Section 4.2.3** to determine d_{far} and d_{near} for each focus stack parent image motor count. The resulting range uncertainty estimate ($\pm r_{uncertainty}$, in centimeters) reported in the light green column on the lower right side of the corresponding *Focus Merge Product Information Sheet* is estimated by the average of the absolute values of d_{far} and d_{near} :

$$\pm r_{uncertainty} = ((-d_{near}) + d_{far})/2. \quad (13)$$

Alternatively, particularly after Sol 1000, the depth of field is reported in the form of both the near and far (d_{far} and d_{near}) depths of field, per **Equation 7**.

5.2.3 Corresponding DN in range map product

Focus merge range map products created onboard MAHLI are returned as grayscale JPEG compressed images. The pixel values (DN) range from 0 to 255. These are assigned by the onboard software on the basis of commanded focus stack depth. The table below, from Edgett *et al.* (2015), shows the relationship between each image commanded to be focus merged and its corresponding grayscale DN value in a MAHLI range map product. In other words, if the instrument is commanded to merge eight images, DN values are assigned according to the second column in the table; if commanded to merge only four images, the corresponding DN

values are those in the sixth column. Thus, each DN in a range map product can be related to a motor count position and a corresponding range via linear interpolation between these values.

Relation between commanded image participant in an onboard MAHLI focus merge and range map grayscale data value (DN)							
image commanded to be merged	DN for 8-image merge	DN for 7-image merge	DN for 6-image merge	DN for 5-image merge	DN for 4-image merge	DN for 3-image merge	DN for 2-image merge
1st	255	255	255	255	255	255	255
2nd	223	218	212	204	191	170	127
3rd	191	182	170	153	127	84	—
4th	159	145	127	102	63	—	—
5th	127	109	84	51	—	—	—
6th	95	72	42	—	—	—	—
7th	63	36	—	—	—	—	—
8th	31	—	—	—	—	—	—

5.2.4 Determination of which parent images participated in a given focus merge product (orange rows)

Focus merge parent images in the orange-colored rows on each of the *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets* are an indicator of the images that were actually merged. A merge of up to 8 images might be commanded, but perhaps only 3, 4, or 5 of them actually exhibit in-focus elements the get incorporated into the best focus image product.

As discussed by Edgett *et al.* (2015), the parent images that were actually merged, relative to the number commanded to be merged (indicated by the number of yellow-colored rows regarding the corresponding DN in the range map products on the right side of each *Focus Merge Product Information Sheet*), are determined by the range of grayscale DN, between 0 and 255, in the focus merge range map product. For example, if the DN range of this product is 71 to 138, then only four of 8 images commanded to be merged participated in that merge, per the DN values corresponding to an 8-image focus merge, per the table above.

5.2.5 Camera working distance and standoff distance

For a given focus stack, the distance between the MAHLI camera head and an imaged target can be determined from a corresponding image acquired via autofocusing (assuming the autofocus effort found focus). In other words, while the range between the camera and the in-focus elements of a parent image are captured by the individual parent images in the focus stack (**Section 5.2.1**), the camera acquired the stack from a fixed working distance. On the MAHLI *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets*, the corresponding autofocused image, and its stepper motor count focus position, are stated on the left side of the sheet, beneath the thumbnail images, in rows and columns colored light blue.

For some *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets*, the working distance (d_w) and standoff distance (d_s) are provided in these blue rows and columns. These were computed from the motor count position using the same formulae for d_w and d_s described in **Section 4.2**

(**Equations 1 and 3**, respectively). Where these values are not given, the data user can apply **Equations 1 and 3** to the motor count, or use the corresponding full-frame image ID to identify the working distance and standoff distance using the *Range and Scale Information Sheets* for that Sol. We began to regularly provide a result for d_w and d_s starting with Sol 694; before that, the cases in which these values are not given are a reflection of the evolution of the production and content of the MAHLI *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets* over time.

UPDATED: 03_August_2023

SOL 3905 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Novo_Paraiso - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3905MH0001680011401668C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3905MH0002650001401689R00	1689	MOTOR COUNT:		14017	RANGE (cm):	6.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3905MH0002650001401690S00	1690	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	1-Aug-23	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00265	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3905	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3905	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3905MH0001680021401669C00	1669	13945	7.22	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	255	1
3905MH0001680021401670C00	1670	13963	7.09	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	223	2
3905MH0001680021401671C00	1671	13981	6.97	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	191	3
3905MH0001680021401672C00	1672	13999	6.85	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	159	4
3905MH0001680021401673C00	1673	14017	6.73	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	127	5
3905MH0001680021401674C00	1674	14035	6.62	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	95	6
3905MH0001680021401675C00	1675	14053	6.51	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	63	7
3905MH0001680021401676C00	1676	14071	6.40	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 03_August_2023

SOL 3905 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Novo_Paraiso - stereo-2 - ~45 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3905MH0001680011401678C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3905MH0002650001401687R00	1687	MOTOR COUNT:		14039	RANGE (cm):	6.6		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3905MH0002650001401688S00	1688	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	1-Aug-23	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00265	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3905	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3905	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3905MH0001680021401679C00	1679	13967	7.07	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	255	1
3905MH0001680021401680C00	1680	13985	6.94	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	223	2
3905MH0001680021401681C00	1681	14003	6.82	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	191	3
3905MH0001680021401682C00	1682	14021	6.71	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	159	4
3905MH0001680021401683C00	1683	14039	6.59	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	127	5
3905MH0001680021401684C00	1684	14057	6.48	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	95	6
3905MH0001680021401685C00	1685	14075	6.38	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	63	7
3905MH0001680021401686C00	1686	14093	6.27	-0.1	0.1	29.0	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 03_August_2023

SOL 3906 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Kefalonia - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3906MH0001680011401694C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3906MH0001930001401727R00	1727	MOTOR COUNT:		14004	RANGE (cm):	6.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3906MH0001930001401728S00	1728	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	2-Aug-23	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3906	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3906	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3906MH0001680021401695C00	1695	13932	7.31	-0.2	0.2	32.6	0.6	255	1
3906MH0001680021401696C00	1696	13950	7.18	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	223	2
3906MH0001680021401697C00	1697	13968	7.06	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	191	3
3906MH0001680021401698C00	1698	13986	6.94	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	159	4
3906MH0001680021401699C00	1699	14004	6.82	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	127	5
3906MH0001680021401700C00	1700	14022	6.70	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	95	6
3906MH0001680021401701C00	1701	14040	6.59	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	63	7
3906MH0001680021401702C00	1702	14058	6.48	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 03_August_2023

SOL 3906 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Kefalonia - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3906MH0001680011401704C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3906MH0001930001401725R00	1725	MOTOR COUNT:		14008	RANGE (cm):	6.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3906MH0001930001401726S00	1726	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	2-Aug-23	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3906	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3906	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3906MH0001680021401705C00	1705	13936	7.28	-0.2	0.2	32.5	0.6	255	1
3906MH0001680021401706C00	1706	13954	7.16	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	223	2
3906MH0001680021401707C00	1707	13972	7.03	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	191	3
3906MH0001680021401708C00	1708	13990	6.91	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	159	4
3906MH0001680021401709C00	1709	14008	6.79	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	127	5
3906MH0001680021401710C00	1710	14026	6.68	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	95	6
3906MH0001680021401711C00	1711	14044	6.56	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	63	7
3906MH0001680021401712C00	1712	14062	6.45	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 03_August_2023

SOL 3906 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Kefalonia – after DRT – ~1 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3906MH0007430011401714C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3906MH0001930001401723R00	1723	MOTOR COUNT:		15122	RANGE (cm):		2.8	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3906MH0001930001401724S00	1724	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00743	STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	2-Aug-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		36	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3906	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3906	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3906MH0007430021401715C00	1715	14978	3.09	-0.1	0.1	17.8	0.2	255	1
3906MH0007430021401716C00	1716	15014	3.01	-0.1	0.1	17.5	0.2	223	2
3906MH0007430021401717C00	1717	15050	2.93	-0.1	0.1	17.2	0.2	191	3
3906MH0007430021401718C00	1718	15086	2.86	-0.1	0.1	17.0	0.2	159	4
3906MH0007430021401719C00	1719	15122	2.79	-0.1	0.1	16.7	0.2	127	5
3906MH0007430021401720C00	1720	15158	2.72	-0.1	0.1	16.5	0.2	95	6
3906MH0007430021401721C00	1721	15194	2.66	-0.1	0.1	16.3	0.2	63	7
3906MH0007430021401722C00	1722	15230	2.59	-0.1	0.1	16.0	0.2	31	8

UPDATED: 07_August_2023

SOL 3907 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Samaria - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3907MH0001680011401732C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3908MH0001630001401803R00	1803	MOTOR COUNT:		14015	RANGE (cm):	6.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3908MH0001630001401804S00	1804	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	3-Aug-23	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	3907	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3908		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3907MH0001680021401733C00	1733	13943	7.23	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	255	1
3907MH0001680021401734C00	1734	13961	7.11	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	223	2
3907MH0001680021401735C00	1735	13979	6.98	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	191	3
3907MH0001680021401736C00	1736	13997	6.86	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	159	4
3907MH0001680021401737C00	1737	14015	6.75	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	127	5
3907MH0001680021401738C00	1738	14033	6.63	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	95	6
3907MH0001680021401739C00	1739	14051	6.52	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	63	7
3907MH0001680021401740C00	1740	14069	6.41	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	31	8

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SOL 3907 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Samaria - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3907MH0001680011401742C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3908MH0001630001401801R00	1801	MOTOR COUNT:		14015	RANGE (cm):	6.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3908MH0001630001401802S00	1802	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	3-Aug-23	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	3907	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3908		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3907MH0001680021401743C00	1743	13943	7.23	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	255	1
3907MH0001680021401744C00	1744	13961	7.11	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	223	2
3907MH0001680021401745C00	1745	13979	6.98	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	191	3
3907MH0001680021401746C00	1746	13997	6.86	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	159	4
3907MH0001680021401747C00	1747	14015	6.75	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	127	5
3907MH0001680021401748C00	1748	14033	6.63	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	95	6
3907MH0001680021401749C00	1749	14051	6.52	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	63	7
3907MH0001680021401750C00	1750	14069	6.41	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	31	8

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SOL 3907 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Samaria - after DRT - ~15 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3907MH0007430011401752C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3908MH0001630001401799R00	1799	MOTOR COUNT:		14928	RANGE (cm):	3.2		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3908MH0001630001401800S00	1800	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00743	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	3-Aug-23	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		36	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	3907	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3908		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3907MH0007430021401753C00	1753	14784	3.55	-0.1	0.1	19.4	0.3	255	1
3907MH0007430021401754C00	1754	14820	3.46	-0.1	0.1	19.1	0.3	223	2
3907MH0007430021401755C00	1755	14856	3.37	-0.1	0.1	18.8	0.2	191	3
3907MH0007430021401756C00	1756	14892	3.28	-0.1	0.1	18.5	0.2	159	4
3907MH0007430021401757C00	1757	14928	3.20	-0.1	0.1	18.2	0.2	127	5
3907MH0007430021401758C00	1758	14964	3.12	-0.1	0.1	17.9	0.2	95	6
3907MH0007430021401759C00	1759	15000	3.04	-0.1	0.1	17.6	0.2	63	7
3907MH0007430021401760C00	1760	15036	2.96	-0.1	0.1	17.3	0.2	31	8

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SOL 3907 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Kythira - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3907MH0001820011401764C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3908MH0001630001401797R00	1797	MOTOR COUNT:		13999	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3908MH0001630001401798S00	1798	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00182	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	3-Aug-23	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	3907	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3908		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3907MH0001820021401765C00	1765	13903	7.53	-0.2	0.2	33.4	0.7	255	1
3907MH0001820021401766C00	1766	13927	7.35	-0.2	0.2	32.8	0.6	223	2
3907MH0001820021401767C00	1767	13951	7.18	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	191	3
3907MH0001820021401768C00	1768	13975	7.01	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	159	4
3907MH0001820021401769C00	1769	13999	6.85	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	127	5
3907MH0001820021401770C00	1770	14023	6.70	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	95	6
3907MH0001820021401771C00	1771	14047	6.55	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	63	7
3907MH0001820021401772C00	1772	14071	6.40	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	31	8

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SOL 3907 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Kythira - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3907MH0001820011401774C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3908MH0001630001401795R00	1795	MOTOR COUNT:		14003	RANGE (cm):	6.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3908MH0001630001401796S00	1796	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00182	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	3-Aug-23	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	3907	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3908		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3907MH0001820021401775C00	1775	13907	7.50	-0.2	0.2	33.3	0.7	255	1
3907MH0001820021401776C00	1776	13931	7.32	-0.2	0.2	32.7	0.6	223	2
3907MH0001820021401777C00	1777	13955	7.15	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	191	3
3907MH0001820021401778C00	1778	13979	6.98	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	159	4
3907MH0001820021401779C00	1779	14003	6.82	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	127	5
3907MH0001820021401780C00	1780	14027	6.67	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	95	6
3907MH0001820021401781C00	1781	14051	6.52	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	63	7
3907MH0001820021401782C00	1782	14075	6.38	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	31	8

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SOL 3907 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Kythira - ~1 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3907MH0004260011401784C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3908MH0001630001401793R00	1793	MOTOR COUNT:		15154	RANGE (cm):	2.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3908MH0001630001401794S00	1794	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00426	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	3-Aug-23	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		48	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	3907	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3908		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3907MH0004260021401785C00	1785	14962	3.12	-0.1	0.1	17.9	0.2	255	1
3907MH0004260021401786C00	1786	15010	3.02	-0.1	0.1	17.5	0.2	223	2
3907MH0004260021401787C00	1787	15058	2.92	-0.1	0.1	17.2	0.2	191	3
3907MH0004260021401788C00	1788	15106	2.82	-0.1	0.1	16.8	0.2	159	4
3907MH0004260021401789C00	1789	15154	2.73	-0.1	0.1	16.5	0.2	127	5
3907MH0004260021401790C00	1790	15202	2.64	-0.1	0.1	16.2	0.2	95	6
3907MH0004260021401791C00	1791	15250	2.56	-0.1	0.1	15.9	0.2	63	7
3907MH0004260021401792C00	1792	15298	2.48	0.0	0.1	15.6	0.2	31	8

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SOL 3909 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Kolpos_Megaron - stereo-1 - ~45 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3909MH0002240011401808C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3910MH0002270001401867R00	1867	MOTOR COUNT:		14076	RANGE (cm):	6.4		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3910MH0002270001401868S00	1868	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00224	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	5-Jul-23	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		42	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3909	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3910	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3909MH0002240021401809C00	1809	13908	7.49	-0.2	0.2	33.3	0.7	255	1
3909MH0002240021401810C00	1810	13950	7.18	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	223	2
3909MH0002240021401811C00	1811	13992	6.90	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	191	3
3909MH0002240021401812C00	1812	14034	6.63	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	159	4
3909MH0002240021401813C00	1813	14076	6.37	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	127	5
3909MH0002240021401814C00	1814	14118	6.13	-0.1	0.1	28.5	0.5	95	6
3909MH0002240021401815C00	1815	14160	5.90	-0.1	0.1	27.7	0.4	63	7
3909MH0002240021401816C00	1816	14202	5.68	-0.1	0.1	26.9	0.4	31	8

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SOL 3909 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Kolpos_Megaron - stereo-2 - ~4 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3909MH0002240011401818C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3910MH0002270001401865R00	1865	MOTOR COUNT:		14140	RANGE (cm):	6.0		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3910MH0002270001401866S00	1866	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00224	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	5-Jul-23	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		42	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3909	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3910	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3909MH0002240021401819C00	1819	13972	7.03	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	255	1
3909MH0002240021401820C00	1820	14014	6.75	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	223	2
3909MH0002240021401821C00	1821	14056	6.49	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	191	3
3909MH0002240021401822C00	1822	14098	6.24	-0.1	0.1	28.9	0.5	159	4
3909MH0002240021401823C00	1823	14140	6.01	-0.1	0.1	28.0	0.5	127	5
3909MH0002240021401824C00	1824	14182	5.78	-0.1	0.1	27.3	0.4	95	6
3909MH0002240021401825C00	1825	14224	5.57	-0.1	0.1	26.5	0.4	63	7
3909MH0002240021401826C00	1826	14266	5.37	-0.1	0.1	25.8	0.4	31	8

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SOL 3909 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Sopoto – after DRT – stereo-1 – ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3909MH0001820011401830C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3910MH0002270001401863R00	1863	MOTOR COUNT:		13963	RANGE (cm):		7.1	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3910MH0002270001401864S00	1864	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00182	STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	5-Jul-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3909	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3910	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3909MH0001820021401831C00	1831	13867	7.81	-0.2	0.2	34.4	0.7	255	1
3909MH0001820021401832C00	1832	13891	7.62	-0.2	0.2	33.7	0.7	223	2
3909MH0001820021401833C00	1833	13915	7.44	-0.2	0.2	33.1	0.6	191	3
3909MH0001820021401834C00	1834	13939	7.26	-0.2	0.2	32.5	0.6	159	4
3909MH0001820021401835C00	1835	13963	7.09	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	127	5
3909MH0001820021401836C00	1836	13987	6.93	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	95	6
3909MH0001820021401837C00	1837	14011	6.77	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	63	7
3909MH0001820021401838C00	1838	14035	6.62	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	31	8

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SOL 3909 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Sopoto – after DRT – stereo-2 – ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3909MH0001820011401840C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3910MH0002270001401861R00	1861	MOTOR COUNT:		13981	RANGE (cm):		7.0	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3910MH0002270001401862S00	1862	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00182	STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	5-Jul-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3909	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3910	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3909MH0001820021401841C00	1841	13885	7.66	-0.2	0.2	33.9	0.7	255	1
3909MH0001820021401842C00	1842	13909	7.48	-0.2	0.2	33.2	0.7	223	2
3909MH0001820021401843C00	1843	13933	7.31	-0.2	0.2	32.6	0.6	191	3
3909MH0001820021401844C00	1844	13957	7.14	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	159	4
3909MH0001820021401845C00	1845	13981	6.97	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	127	5
3909MH0001820021401846C00	1846	14005	6.81	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	95	6
3909MH0001820021401847C00	1847	14029	6.66	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	63	7
3909MH0001820021401848C00	1848	14053	6.51	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	31	8

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SOL 3909 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Sopoto – after DRT – ~15 mm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3909MH0004260011401850C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		3910MH0002270001401859R00		1859		MOTOR COUNT:		14795		RANGE (cm): 3.5	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		3910MH0002270001401860S00		1860		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00426		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		5-Jul-23				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227		MERGE TYPE: BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:			48	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3909		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3910	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
3909MH0004260021401851C00	1851	14603	4.08	-0.1	0.1	21.3	0.3	255	1		
3909MH0004260021401852C00	1852	14651	3.93	-0.1	0.1	20.7	0.3	223	2		
3909MH0004260021401853C00	1853	14699	3.79	-0.1	0.1	20.2	0.3	191	3		
3909MH0004260021401854C00	1854	14747	3.65	-0.1	0.1	19.8	0.3	159	4		
3909MH0004260021401855C00	1855	14795	3.52	-0.1	0.1	19.3	0.3	127	5		
3909MH0004260021401856C00	1856	14843	3.40	-0.1	0.1	18.9	0.2	95	6		
3909MH0004260021401857C00	1857	14891	3.28	-0.1	0.1	18.5	0.2	63	7		
3909MH0004260021401858C00	1858	14939	3.17	-0.1	0.1	18.1	0.2	31	8		

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SOL 3912 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

	target Ouranoupoli - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3912MH0001820011401872C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3912MH0001930001401905R00	1905	MOTOR COUNT:		13968	RANGE (cm):	7.1		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3912MH0001930001401906S00	1906	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00182	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	8-Aug-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3912	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3912	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3912MH0001820021401873C00	1873	13872	7.77	-0.2	0.2	34.2	0.7	255	1
3912MH0001820021401874C00	1874	13896	7.58	-0.2	0.2	33.6	0.7	223	2
3912MH0001820021401875C00	1875	13920	7.40	-0.2	0.2	32.9	0.6	191	3
3912MH0001820021401876C00	1876	13944	7.23	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	159	4
3912MH0001820021401877C00	1877	13968	7.06	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	127	5
3912MH0001820021401878C00	1878	13992	6.90	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	95	6
3912MH0001820021401879C00	1879	14016	6.74	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	63	7
3912MH0001820021401880C00	1880	14040	6.59	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	31	8

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SOL 3912 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

	target Ouranoupoli - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3912MH0001820011401882C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3912MH0001930001401903R00	1903	MOTOR COUNT:		13962	RANGE (cm):	7.1		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3912MH0001930001401904S00	1904	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00182	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	8-Aug-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3912	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3912	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3912MH0001820021401883C00	1883	13866	7.81	-0.2	0.2	34.4	0.7	255	1
3912MH0001820021401884C00	1884	13890	7.63	-0.2	0.2	33.7	0.7	223	2
3912MH0001820021401885C00	1885	13914	7.44	-0.2	0.2	33.1	0.7	191	3
3912MH0001820021401886C00	1886	13938	7.27	-0.2	0.2	32.5	0.6	159	4
3912MH0001820021401887C00	1887	13962	7.10	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	127	5
3912MH0001820021401888C00	1888	13986	6.94	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	95	6
3912MH0001820021401889C00	1889	14010	6.78	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	63	7
3912MH0001820021401890C00	1890	14034	6.63	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	31	8

UPDATED: 10_August_2023

SOL 3912 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Ouranoupoli - after DRT - ~1 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3912MH0007960011401892C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3912MH0001930001401901R00	1901	MOTOR COUNT:		14979	RANGE (cm):		3.1	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3912MH0001930001401902S00	1902	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00796		STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	8-Aug-23		MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193		MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		42	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3912		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3912
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3912MH0007960021401893C00	1893	14811	3.48	-0.1	0.1	19.2	0.3	255	1
3912MH0007960021401894C00	1894	14853	3.38	-0.1	0.1	18.8	0.2	223	2
3912MH0007960021401895C00	1895	14895	3.28	-0.1	0.1	18.4	0.2	191	3
3912MH0007960021401896C00	1896	14937	3.18	-0.1	0.1	18.1	0.2	159	4
3912MH0007960021401897C00	1897	14979	3.08	-0.1	0.1	17.8	0.2	127	5
3912MH0007960021401898C00	1898	15021	2.99	-0.1	0.1	17.4	0.2	95	6
3912MH0007960021401899C00	1899	15063	2.91	-0.1	0.1	17.1	0.2	63	7
3912MH0007960021401900C00	1900	15105	2.82	-0.1	0.1	16.8	0.2	31	8

UPDATED: 11_August_2023

SOL 3914 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Skepasta - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3914MH0001680011401910C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3914MH0001930001401943R00	1943	MOTOR COUNT:		13990	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3914MH0001930001401944S00	1944	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	10-Aug-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3914	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3914	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3914MH0001680021401911C00	1911	13918	7.42	-0.2	0.2	33.0	0.6	255	1
3914MH0001680021401912C00	1912	13936	7.28	-0.2	0.2	32.5	0.6	223	2
3914MH0001680021401913C00	1913	13954	7.16	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	191	3
3914MH0001680021401914C00	1914	13972	7.03	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	159	4
3914MH0001680021401915C00	1915	13990	6.91	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	127	5
3914MH0001680021401916C00	1916	14008	6.79	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	95	6
3914MH0001680021401917C00	1917	14026	6.68	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	63	7
3914MH0001680021401918C00	1918	14044	6.56	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 11_August_2023

SOL 3914 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Skepasta - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3914MH0001680011401920C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3914MH0001930001401941R00	1941	MOTOR COUNT:		13992	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3914MH0001930001401942S00	1942	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	10-Aug-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3914	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3914	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3914MH0001680021401921C00	1921	13920	7.40	-0.2	0.2	32.9	0.6	255	1
3914MH0001680021401922C00	1922	13938	7.27	-0.2	0.2	32.5	0.6	223	2
3914MH0001680021401923C00	1923	13956	7.14	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	191	3
3914MH0001680021401924C00	1924	13974	7.02	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	159	4
3914MH0001680021401925C00	1925	13992	6.90	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	127	5
3914MH0001680021401926C00	1926	14010	6.78	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	95	6
3914MH0001680021401927C00	1927	14028	6.66	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	63	7
3914MH0001680021401928C00	1928	14046	6.55	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 11_August_2023

SOL 3914 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Skepasto - after DRT - ~1 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3914MH0007430011401930C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3914MH0001930001401939R00	1939	MOTOR COUNT:		15085	RANGE (cm):		2.9	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3914MH0001930001401940S00	1940	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00743		STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	10-Aug-23		MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193		MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		36	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3914		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3914
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3914MH0007430021401931C00	1931	14941	3.17	-0.1	0.1	18.1	0.2	255	1
3914MH0007430021401932C00	1932	14977	3.09	-0.1	0.1	17.8	0.2	223	2
3914MH0007430021401933C00	1933	15013	3.01	-0.1	0.1	17.5	0.2	191	3
3914MH0007430021401934C00	1934	15049	2.94	-0.1	0.1	17.2	0.2	159	4
3914MH0007430021401935C00	1935	15085	2.86	-0.1	0.1	17.0	0.2	127	5
3914MH0007430021401936C00	1936	15121	2.79	-0.1	0.1	16.7	0.2	95	6
3914MH0007430021401937C00	1937	15157	2.73	-0.1	0.1	16.5	0.2	63	7
3914MH0007430021401938C00	1938	15193	2.66	-0.1	0.1	16.3	0.2	31	8

UPDATED: 15_August_2023

SOL 3916 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Ntourntourvana - after DRT - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3916MH0001680011401952C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		3917MH0001530001402005R00		2005		MOTOR COUNT:		14016	RANGE (cm):	6.7
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		3917MH0001530001402006S00		2006		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		12-Aug-23				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00153	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3916		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3917
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8	
				NEAR	FAR					
3916MH0001680021401953C00	1953	13944	7.23	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	255	1	
3916MH0001680021401954C00	1954	13962	7.10	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	223	2	
3916MH0001680021401955C00	1955	13980	6.98	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	191	3	
3916MH0001680021401956C00	1956	13998	6.86	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	159	4	
3916MH0001680021401957C00	1957	14016	6.74	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	127	5	
3916MH0001680021401958C00	1958	14034	6.63	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	95	6	
3916MH0001680021401959C00	1959	14052	6.51	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	63	7	
3916MH0001680021401960C00	1960	14070	6.41	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	31	8	

UPDATED: 15_August_2023

SOL 3916 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Ntourntourvana - after DRT - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3916MH0001680011401962C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		3917MH0001530001402003R00		2003		MOTOR COUNT:		14015	RANGE (cm):	6.7
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		3917MH0001530001402004S00		2004		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		12-Aug-23				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00153	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3916		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3917
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8	
				NEAR	FAR					
3916MH0001680021401963C00	1963	13943	7.23	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	255	1	
3916MH0001680021401964C00	1964	13961	7.11	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	223	2	
3916MH0001680021401965C00	1965	13979	6.98	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	191	3	
3916MH0001680021401966C00	1966	13997	6.86	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	159	4	
3916MH0001680021401967C00	1967	14015	6.75	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	127	5	
3916MH0001680021401968C00	1968	14033	6.63	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	95	6	
3916MH0001680021401969C00	1969	14051	6.52	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	63	7	
3916MH0001680021401970C00	1970	14069	6.41	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	31	8	

UPDATED: 15_August_2023

SOL 3916 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

	target Ntourntourvana - after DRT - APXS spot 2 - ~1 cm standoff								
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3916MH0008640011401972C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3917MH0001530001402001R00	2001	MOTOR COUNT:		15164	RANGE (cm):	2.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3917MH0001530001402002S00	2002	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00864	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	12-Aug-23	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00153	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3916	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3917	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3916MH0008640021401973C00	1973	15044	2.95	-0.1	0.1	17.3	0.2	255	1
3916MH0008640021401974C00	1974	15074	2.89	-0.1	0.1	17.1	0.2	223	2
3916MH0008640021401975C00	1975	15104	2.83	-0.1	0.1	16.8	0.2	191	3
3916MH0008640021401976C00	1976	15134	2.77	-0.1	0.1	16.6	0.2	159	4
3916MH0008640021401977C00	1977	15164	2.71	-0.1	0.1	16.4	0.2	127	5
3916MH0008640021401978C00	1978	15194	2.66	-0.1	0.1	16.3	0.2	95	6
3916MH0008640021401979C00	1979	15224	2.60	-0.1	0.1	16.1	0.2	63	7
3916MH0008640021401980C00	1980	15254	2.55	-0.1	0.1	15.9	0.2	31	8

UPDATED: 15_August_2023

SOL 3916 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

	target Ntourntourvana - after DRT - APXS spot 1 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3916MH0001680011401982C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3917MH0001530001401999R00	1999	MOTOR COUNT:		14007	RANGE (cm):	6.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3917MH0001530001402000S00	2000	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	12-Aug-23	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00153	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3916	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3917	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3916MH0001680021401983C00	1983	13935	7.29	-0.2	0.2	32.6	0.6	255	1
3916MH0001680021401984C00	1984	13953	7.16	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	223	2
3916MH0001680021401985C00	1985	13971	7.04	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	191	3
3916MH0001680021401986C00	1986	13989	6.92	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	159	4
3916MH0001680021401987C00	1987	14007	6.80	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	127	5
3916MH0001680021401988C00	1988	14025	6.68	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	95	6
3916MH0001680021401989C00	1989	14043	6.57	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	63	7
3916MH0001680021401990C00	1990	14061	6.46	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 21_August_2023

SOL 3921 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Kamenianoi - ~25 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3921MH0008650011402008C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3921MH0001630001402079R00	2079	MOTOR COUNT:		13015	RANGE (cm):	26.6		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3921MH0001630001402080S00	2080	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00865	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	17-Aug-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3921	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3921	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3921MH0008650021402009C00	2009	12919	34.02	-2.9	3.4	126.6	11.0	255	1
3921MH0008650021402010C00	2010	12943	31.85	-2.5	2.9	119.0	9.6	223	2
3921MH0008650021402011C00	2011	12967	29.92	-2.2	2.6	112.2	8.5	191	3
3921MH0008650021402012C00	2012	12991	28.19	-2.0	2.3	106.1	7.5	159	4
3921MH0008650021402013C00	2013	13015	26.64	-1.8	2.0	100.7	6.7	127	5
3921MH0008650021402014C00	2014	13039	25.24	-1.6	1.8	95.8	6.0	95	6
3921MH0008650021402015C00	2015	13063	23.97	-1.5	1.6	91.3	5.4	63	7
3921MH0008650021402016C00	2016	13087	22.81	-1.3	1.5	87.2	4.9	31	8

UPDATED: 21_August_2023

SOL 3921 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Kamenianoi - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3921MH0003080011402018C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3921MH0001630001402077R00	2077	MOTOR COUNT:		13972	RANGE (cm):	7.0		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3921MH0001630001402078S00	2078	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00308	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	17-Aug-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		66	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3921	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3921	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3921MH0003080021402019C00	2019	13708	9.25	-0.3	0.3	39.4	0.9	255	1
3921MH0003080021402020C00	2020	13774	8.60	-0.2	0.2	37.2	0.8	223	2
3921MH0003080021402021C00	2021	13840	8.03	-0.2	0.2	35.2	0.7	191	3
3921MH0003080021402022C00	2022	13906	7.50	-0.2	0.2	33.3	0.7	159	4
3921MH0003080021402023C00	2023	13972	7.03	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	127	5
3921MH0003080021402024C00	2024	14038	6.60	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	95	6
3921MH0003080021402025C00	2025	14104	6.21	-0.1	0.1	28.8	0.5	63	7
3921MH0003080021402026C00	2026	14170	5.85	-0.1	0.1	27.5	0.4	31	8

UPDATED: 21_August_2023

SOL 3921 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Kamenianoi - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3921MH0003080011402028C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3921MH0001630001402075R00	2075	MOTOR COUNT:		13987	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3921MH0001630001402076S00	2076	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00308	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	17-Aug-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		66	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3921	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3921	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3921MH0003080021402029C00	2029	13723	9.09	-0.3	0.2	38.9	0.9	255	1
3921MH0003080021402030C00	2030	13789	8.47	-0.2	0.2	36.7	0.8	223	2
3921MH0003080021402031C00	2031	13855	7.90	-0.2	0.2	34.7	0.7	191	3
3921MH0003080021402032C00	2032	13921	7.39	-0.2	0.2	32.9	0.6	159	4
3921MH0003080021402033C00	2033	13987	6.93	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	127	5
3921MH0003080021402034C00	2034	14053	6.51	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	95	6
3921MH0003080021402035C00	2035	14119	6.12	-0.1	0.1	28.5	0.5	63	7
3921MH0003080021402036C00	2036	14185	5.77	-0.1	0.1	27.2	0.4	31	8

UPDATED: 21_August_2023

SOL 3921 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Kamenianoi - ~3 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3921MH0004050011402038C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3921MH0001630001402073R00	2073	MOTOR COUNT:		14338	RANGE (cm):	5.1		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3921MH0001630001402074S00	2074	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00405	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	17-Aug-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		78	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3921	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3921	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3921MH0004050021402039C00	2039	14026	6.68	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	255	1
3921MH0004050021402040C00	2040	14104	6.21	-0.1	0.1	28.8	0.5	223	2
3921MH0004050021402041C00	2041	14182	5.78	-0.1	0.1	27.3	0.4	191	3
3921MH0004050021402042C00	2042	14260	5.40	-0.1	0.1	25.9	0.4	159	4
3921MH0004050021402043C00	2043	14338	5.05	-0.1	0.1	24.7	0.4	127	5
3921MH0004050021402044C00	2044	14416	4.74	-0.1	0.1	23.6	0.3	95	6
3921MH0004050021402045C00	2045	14494	4.44	-0.1	0.1	22.5	0.3	63	7
3921MH0004050021402046C00	2046	14572	4.18	-0.1	0.1	21.6	0.3	31	8

UPDATED: 21_August_2023

SOL 3921 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Eleftheroupoli - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3921MH0001680011402050C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3921MH0001630001402071R00	2071	MOTOR COUNT:		14071	RANGE (cm):	6.4		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3921MH0001630001402072S00	2072	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	17-Aug-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3921	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3921	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3921MH0001680021402051C00	2051	13999	6.85	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	255	1
3921MH0001680021402052C00	2052	14017	6.73	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	223	2
3921MH0001680021402053C00	2053	14035	6.62	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	191	3
3921MH0001680021402054C00	2054	14053	6.51	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	159	4
3921MH0001680021402055C00	2055	14071	6.40	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	127	5
3921MH0001680021402056C00	2056	14089	6.29	-0.1	0.1	29.1	0.5	95	6
3921MH0001680021402057C00	2057	14107	6.19	-0.1	0.1	28.7	0.5	63	7
3921MH0001680021402058C00	2058	14125	6.09	-0.1	0.1	28.3	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 21_August_2023

SOL 3921 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Eleftheroupoli - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3921MH0001680011402060C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3921MH0001630001402069R00	2069	MOTOR COUNT:		14069	RANGE (cm):	6.4		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3921MH0001630001402070S00	2070	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	17-Aug-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3921	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3921	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3921MH0001680021402061C00	2061	13997	6.86	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	255	1
3921MH0001680021402062C00	2062	14015	6.75	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	223	2
3921MH0001680021402063C00	2063	14033	6.63	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	191	3
3921MH0001680021402064C00	2064	14051	6.52	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	159	4
3921MH0001680021402065C00	2065	14069	6.41	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	127	5
3921MH0001680021402066C00	2066	14087	6.31	-0.1	0.1	29.1	0.5	95	6
3921MH0001680021402067C00	2067	14105	6.20	-0.1	0.1	28.7	0.5	63	7
3921MH0001680021402068C00	2068	14123	6.10	-0.1	0.1	28.4	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 31_August_2023

SOL 3926 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Mytikas - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3926MH0001820011402084C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3926MH0003690001402203R00	2203	MOTOR COUNT:		13996	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3926MH0003690001402204S00	2204	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00182	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	23-Aug-23	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00369	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3926	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3926	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3926MH0001820021402085C00	2085	13900	7.55	-0.2	0.2	33.5	0.7	255	1
3926MH0001820021402086C00	2086	13924	7.37	-0.2	0.2	32.8	0.6	223	2
3926MH0001820021402087C00	2087	13948	7.20	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	191	3
3926MH0001820021402088C00	2088	13972	7.03	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	159	4
3926MH0001820021402089C00	2089	13996	6.87	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	127	5
3926MH0001820021402090C00	2090	14020	6.71	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	95	6
3926MH0001820021402091C00	2091	14044	6.56	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	63	7
3926MH0001820021402092C00	2092	14068	6.42	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 31_August_2023

SOL 3926 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Mytikas - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3926MH0001820011402094C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3926MH0003690001402201R00	2201	MOTOR COUNT:		13995	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3926MH0003690001402202S00	2202	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00182	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	23-Aug-23	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00369	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3926	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3926	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3926MH0001820021402095C00	2095	13899	7.56	-0.2	0.2	33.5	0.7	255	1
3926MH0001820021402096C00	2096	13923	7.38	-0.2	0.2	32.9	0.6	223	2
3926MH0001820021402097C00	2097	13947	7.21	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	191	3
3926MH0001820021402098C00	2098	13971	7.04	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	159	4
3926MH0001820021402099C00	2099	13995	6.88	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	127	5
3926MH0001820021402100C00	2100	14019	6.72	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	95	6
3926MH0001820021402101C00	2101	14043	6.57	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	63	7
3926MH0001820021402102C00	2102	14067	6.42	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	31	8

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SOL 3926 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Mytikas - after DRT - ~1 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3926MH0003860011402104C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3926MH0003690001402199R00	2199	MOTOR COUNT:		15077	RANGE (cm):	2.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3926MH0003690001402200S00	2200	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00386	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	23-Aug-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00369	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		54	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3926	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3926	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3926MH0003860021402105C00	2105	14861	3.36	-0.1	0.1	18.7	0.2	255	1
3926MH0003860021402106C00	2106	14915	3.23	-0.1	0.1	18.3	0.2	223	2
3926MH0003860021402107C00	2107	14969	3.11	-0.1	0.1	17.8	0.2	191	3
3926MH0003860021402108C00	2108	15023	2.99	-0.1	0.1	17.4	0.2	159	4
3926MH0003860021402109C00	2109	15077	2.88	-0.1	0.1	17.0	0.2	127	5
3926MH0003860021402110C00	2110	15131	2.77	-0.1	0.1	16.7	0.2	95	6
3926MH0003860021402111C00	2111	15185	2.67	-0.1	0.1	16.3	0.2	63	7
3926MH0003860021402112C00	2112	15239	2.58	-0.1	0.1	16.0	0.2	31	8

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SOL 3926 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Mytikas - mosaic position 1 of 4 - ~4 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3926MH0001520011402114C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3926MH0003690001402197R00	2197	MOTOR COUNT:		14120	RANGE (cm):	6.1		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3926MH0003690001402198S00	2198	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00152	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	23-Aug-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00369	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		48	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3926	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3926	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3926MH0001520021402115C00	2115	13928	7.34	-0.2	0.2	32.7	0.6	255	1
3926MH0001520021402116C00	2116	13976	7.00	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	223	2
3926MH0001520021402117C00	2117	14024	6.69	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	191	3
3926MH0001520021402118C00	2118	14072	6.39	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	159	4
3926MH0001520021402119C00	2119	14120	6.12	-0.1	0.1	28.4	0.5	127	5
3926MH0001520021402120C00	2120	14168	5.86	-0.1	0.1	27.5	0.4	95	6
3926MH0001520021402121C00	2121	14216	5.61	-0.1	0.1	26.7	0.4	63	7
3926MH0001520021402122C00	2122	14264	5.38	-0.1	0.1	25.8	0.4	31	8

UPDATED: 31_August_2023

SOL 3926 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Mytikas - mosaic position 2 of 4 - ~4 cm standoff							
				CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3926MH0001520011402124C00		
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3926MH0003690001402195R00			2195	MOTOR COUNT:		14120	RANGE (cm):	6.1
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3926MH0003690001402196S00			2196	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00152	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	23-Aug-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00369	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		48		ACQUIRED ON SOL:	3926		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3926
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3926MH0001520021402125C00	2125	13928	7.34	-0.2	0.2	32.7	0.6	255	1
3926MH0001520021402126C00	2126	13976	7.00	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	223	2
3926MH0001520021402127C00	2127	14024	6.69	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	191	3
3926MH0001520021402128C00	2128	14072	6.39	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	159	4
3926MH0001520021402129C00	2129	14120	6.12	-0.1	0.1	28.4	0.5	127	5
3926MH0001520021402130C00	2130	14168	5.86	-0.1	0.1	27.5	0.4	95	6
3926MH0001520021402131C00	2131	14216	5.61	-0.1	0.1	26.7	0.4	63	7
3926MH0001520021402132C00	2132	14264	5.38	-0.1	0.1	25.8	0.4	31	8

UPDATED: 31_August_2023

SOL 3926 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Mytikas - mosaic position 3 of 4 - ~4 cm standoff							
				CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3926MH0001520011402134C00		
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3926MH0003690001402193R00			2193	MOTOR COUNT:		14164	RANGE (cm):	5.9
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3926MH0003690001402194S00			2194	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00152	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	23-Aug-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00369	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		48		ACQUIRED ON SOL:	3926		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3926
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3926MH0001520021402135C00	2135	13972	7.03	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	255	1
3926MH0001520021402136C00	2136	14020	6.71	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	223	2
3926MH0001520021402137C00	2137	14068	6.42	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	191	3
3926MH0001520021402138C00	2138	14116	6.14	-0.1	0.1	28.5	0.5	159	4
3926MH0001520021402139C00	2139	14164	5.88	-0.1	0.1	27.6	0.4	127	5
3926MH0001520021402140C00	2140	14212	5.63	-0.1	0.1	26.7	0.4	95	6
3926MH0001520021402141C00	2141	14260	5.40	-0.1	0.1	25.9	0.4	63	7
3926MH0001520021402142C00	2142	14308	5.18	-0.1	0.1	25.1	0.4	31	8

UPDATED: 31_August_2023

SOL 3926 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Mytikas - mosaic position 4 of 4 - ~35 mm standoff							
				CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3926MH0001520011402144C00		
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3926MH0003690001402191R00			2191	MOTOR COUNT:		14224	RANGE (cm):	5.6
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3926MH0003690001402192S00			2192	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00152	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	23-Aug-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00369	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		48		ACQUIRED ON SOL:	3926		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3926
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3926MH0001520021402145C00	2145	14032	6.64	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	255	1
3926MH0001520021402146C00	2146	14080	6.35	-0.2	0.1	29.2	0.5	223	2
3926MH0001520021402147C00	2147	14128	6.07	-0.1	0.1	28.3	0.5	191	3
3926MH0001520021402148C00	2148	14176	5.82	-0.1	0.1	27.4	0.4	159	4
3926MH0001520021402149C00	2149	14224	5.57	-0.1	0.1	26.5	0.4	127	5
3926MH0001520021402150C00	2150	14272	5.35	-0.1	0.1	25.7	0.4	95	6
3926MH0001520021402151C00	2151	14320	5.13	-0.1	0.1	25.0	0.4	63	7
3926MH0001520021402152C00	2152	14368	4.93	-0.1	0.1	24.2	0.4	31	8

UPDATED: 31_August_2023

SOL 3926 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Helmos - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
				CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3926MH0002990011402156C00		
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3926MH0003690001402189R00			2189	MOTOR COUNT:		13994	RANGE (cm):	6.9
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3926MH0003690001402190S00			2190	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00299	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	23-Aug-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00369	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		36		ACQUIRED ON SOL:	3926		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3926
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3926MH0002990021402157C00	2157	13850	7.94	-0.2	0.2	34.9	0.7	255	1
3926MH0002990021402158C00	2158	13886	7.66	-0.2	0.2	33.9	0.7	223	2
3926MH0002990021402159C00	2159	13922	7.39	-0.2	0.2	32.9	0.6	191	3
3926MH0002990021402160C00	2160	13958	7.13	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	159	4
3926MH0002990021402161C00	2161	13994	6.88	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	127	5
3926MH0002990021402162C00	2162	14030	6.65	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	95	6
3926MH0002990021402163C00	2163	14066	6.43	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	63	7
3926MH0002990021402164C00	2164	14102	6.22	-0.1	0.1	28.8	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 31_August_2023

SOL 3926 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Helmos - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3926MH0002990011402166C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3926MH0003690001402187R00	2187	MOTOR COUNT:		13998	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3926MH0003690001402188S00	2188	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00299	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	23-Aug-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00369	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		36	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3926	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3926	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3926MH0002990021402167C00	2167	13854	7.91	-0.2	0.2	34.7	0.7	255	1
3926MH0002990021402168C00	2168	13890	7.63	-0.2	0.2	33.7	0.7	223	2
3926MH0002990021402169C00	2169	13926	7.36	-0.2	0.2	32.8	0.6	191	3
3926MH0002990021402170C00	2170	13962	7.10	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	159	4
3926MH0002990021402171C00	2171	13998	6.86	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	127	5
3926MH0002990021402172C00	2172	14034	6.63	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	95	6
3926MH0002990021402173C00	2173	14070	6.41	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	63	7
3926MH0002990021402174C00	2174	14106	6.20	-0.1	0.1	28.7	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 31_August_2023

SOL 3926 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Helmos - ~2 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3926MH0001760011402176C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3926MH0003690001402185R00	2185	MOTOR COUNT:		14674	RANGE (cm):	3.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3926MH0003690001402186S00	2186	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00176	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	23-Aug-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00369	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		48	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3926	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3926	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3926MH0001760021402177C00	2177	14482	4.49	-0.1	0.1	22.7	0.3	255	1
3926MH0001760021402178C00	2178	14530	4.32	-0.1	0.1	22.1	0.3	223	2
3926MH0001760021402179C00	2179	14578	4.16	-0.1	0.1	21.5	0.3	191	3
3926MH0001760021402180C00	2180	14626	4.00	-0.1	0.1	21.0	0.3	159	4
3926MH0001760021402181C00	2181	14674	3.86	-0.1	0.1	20.5	0.3	127	5
3926MH0001760021402182C00	2182	14722	3.72	-0.1	0.1	20.0	0.3	95	6
3926MH0001760021402183C00	2183	14770	3.59	-0.1	0.1	19.5	0.3	63	7
3926MH0001760021402184C00	2184	14818	3.46	-0.1	0.1	19.1	0.3	31	8

UPDATED: 06_September_2023

SOL 3928 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Epidaurus - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3928MH0001730011402208C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3928MH0002270001402267R00	2267	MOTOR COUNT:		13994	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3928MH0002270001402268S00	2268	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00173	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	25-Aug-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00227	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3928	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3928	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3928MH0001730021402209C00	2209	13874	7.75	-0.2	0.2	34.2	0.7	255	1
3928MH0001730021402210C00	2210	13904	7.52	-0.2	0.2	33.4	0.7	223	2
3928MH0001730021402211C00	2211	13934	7.30	-0.2	0.2	32.6	0.6	191	3
3928MH0001730021402212C00	2212	13964	7.09	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	159	4
3928MH0001730021402213C00	2213	13994	6.88	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	127	5
3928MH0001730021402214C00	2214	14024	6.69	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	95	6
3928MH0001730021402215C00	2215	14054	6.50	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	63	7
3928MH0001730021402216C00	2216	14084	6.32	-0.1	0.1	29.2	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 06_September_2023

SOL 3928 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Epidaurus - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3928MH0001730011402218C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3928MH0002270001402265R00	2265	MOTOR COUNT:		13998	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3928MH0002270001402266S00	2266	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00173	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	25-Aug-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00227	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3928	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3928	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3928MH0001730021402219C00	2219	13878	7.72	-0.2	0.2	34.1	0.7	255	1
3928MH0001730021402220C00	2220	13908	7.49	-0.2	0.2	33.3	0.7	223	2
3928MH0001730021402221C00	2221	13938	7.27	-0.2	0.2	32.5	0.6	191	3
3928MH0001730021402222C00	2222	13968	7.06	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	159	4
3928MH0001730021402223C00	2223	13998	6.86	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	127	5
3928MH0001730021402224C00	2224	14028	6.66	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	95	6
3928MH0001730021402225C00	2225	14058	6.48	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	63	7
3928MH0001730021402226C00	2226	14088	6.30	-0.1	0.1	29.1	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 06_September_2023

SOL 3928 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Epidaurus - ~2 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3928MH0001760011402228C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3928MH0002270001402263R00	2263	MOTOR COUNT:		14686	RANGE (cm):	3.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3928MH0002270001402264S00	2264	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00176	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	25-Aug-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00227	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		48	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3928	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3928	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3928MH0001760021402229C00	2229	14494	4.44	-0.1	0.1	22.5	0.3	255	1
3928MH0001760021402230C00	2230	14542	4.28	-0.1	0.1	22.0	0.3	223	2
3928MH0001760021402231C00	2231	14590	4.12	-0.1	0.1	21.4	0.3	191	3
3928MH0001760021402232C00	2232	14638	3.97	-0.1	0.1	20.9	0.3	159	4
3928MH0001760021402233C00	2233	14686	3.82	-0.1	0.1	20.4	0.3	127	5
3928MH0001760021402234C00	2234	14734	3.69	-0.1	0.1	19.9	0.3	95	6
3928MH0001760021402235C00	2235	14782	3.56	-0.1	0.1	19.4	0.3	63	7
3928MH0001760021402236C00	2236	14830	3.43	-0.1	0.1	19.0	0.2	31	8

UPDATED: 06_September_2023

SOL 3928 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Limni_Stymfalia - stereo-1 - ~35 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3928MH0001730011402240C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3928MH0002270001402261R00	2261	MOTOR COUNT:		14220	RANGE (cm):	5.6		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3928MH0002270001402262S00	2262	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00173	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	25-Aug-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00227	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3928	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3928	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3928MH0001730021402241C00	2241	14100	6.23	-0.1	0.1	28.8	0.5	255	1
3928MH0001730021402242C00	2242	14130	6.06	-0.1	0.1	28.2	0.5	223	2
3928MH0001730021402243C00	2243	14160	5.90	-0.1	0.1	27.7	0.4	191	3
3928MH0001730021402244C00	2244	14190	5.74	-0.1	0.1	27.1	0.4	159	4
3928MH0001730021402245C00	2245	14220	5.59	-0.1	0.1	26.6	0.4	127	5
3928MH0001730021402246C00	2246	14250	5.45	-0.1	0.1	26.1	0.4	95	6
3928MH0001730021402247C00	2247	14280	5.31	-0.1	0.1	25.6	0.4	63	7
3928MH0001730021402248C00	2248	14310	5.17	-0.1	0.1	25.1	0.4	31	8

UPDATED: 06_September_2023

SOL 3928 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Limni_Stymfalia - stereo-2 - ~35 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3928MH0001730011402250C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3928MH0002270001402259R00	2259	MOTOR COUNT:		14220	RANGE (cm):		5.6	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3928MH0002270001402260S00	2260	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00173		STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	25-Aug-23		MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227		MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3928		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3928
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3928MH0001730021402251C00	2251	14100	6.23	-0.1	0.1	28.8	0.5	255	1
3928MH0001730021402252C00	2252	14130	6.06	-0.1	0.1	28.2	0.5	223	2
3928MH0001730021402253C00	2253	14160	5.90	-0.1	0.1	27.7	0.4	191	3
3928MH0001730021402254C00	2254	14190	5.74	-0.1	0.1	27.1	0.4	159	4
3928MH0001730021402255C00	2255	14220	5.59	-0.1	0.1	26.6	0.4	127	5
3928MH0001730021402256C00	2256	14250	5.45	-0.1	0.1	26.1	0.4	95	6
3928MH0001730021402257C00	2257	14280	5.31	-0.1	0.1	25.6	0.4	63	7
3928MH0001730021402258C00	2258	14310	5.17	-0.1	0.1	25.1	0.4	31	8

UPDATED: 31_August_2023

SOL 3930 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Meteora - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3930MH0001730011402272C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3931MH0001700001402369R00	2369	MOTOR COUNT:		14029	RANGE (cm):	6.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3931MH0001700001402370S00	2370	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00173	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	27-Aug-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00170	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3930	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3931	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3930MH0001730021402273C00	2273	13909	7.48	-0.2	0.2	33.2	0.7	255	1
3930MH0001730021402274C00	2274	13939	7.26	-0.2	0.2	32.5	0.6	223	2
3930MH0001730021402275C00	2275	13969	7.05	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	191	3
3930MH0001730021402276C00	2276	13999	6.85	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	159	4
3930MH0001730021402277C00	2277	14029	6.66	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	127	5
3930MH0001730021402278C00	2278	14059	6.47	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	95	6
3930MH0001730021402279C00	2279	14089	6.29	-0.1	0.1	29.1	0.5	63	7
3930MH0001730021402280C00	2280	14119	6.12	-0.1	0.1	28.5	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 31_August_2023

SOL 3930 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Meteora - stereo-2 - ~45 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3930MH0001730011402282C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3931MH0001700001402367R00	2367	MOTOR COUNT:		14034	RANGE (cm):	6.6		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3931MH0001700001402368S00	2368	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00173	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	27-Aug-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00170	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3930	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3931	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3930MH0001730021402283C00	2283	13914	7.44	-0.2	0.2	33.1	0.7	255	1
3930MH0001730021402284C00	2284	13944	7.23	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	223	2
3930MH0001730021402285C00	2285	13974	7.02	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	191	3
3930MH0001730021402286C00	2286	14004	6.82	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	159	4
3930MH0001730021402287C00	2287	14034	6.63	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	127	5
3930MH0001730021402288C00	2288	14064	6.44	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	95	6
3930MH0001730021402289C00	2289	14094	6.27	-0.1	0.1	29.0	0.5	63	7
3930MH0001730021402290C00	2290	14124	6.10	-0.1	0.1	28.4	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 31_August_2023

SOL 3930 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Meteora - ~1 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3930MH0007160011402292C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3931MH0001700001402365R00	2365	MOTOR COUNT:		15174	RANGE (cm):	2.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3931MH0001700001402366S00	2366	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00716	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	27-Aug-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00170	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		60	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3930	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3931	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3930MH0007160021402293C00	2293	14934	3.18	-0.1	0.1	18.1	0.2	255	1
3930MH0007160021402294C00	2294	14994	3.05	-0.1	0.1	17.6	0.2	223	2
3930MH0007160021402295C00	2295	15054	2.93	-0.1	0.1	17.2	0.2	191	3
3930MH0007160021402296C00	2296	15114	2.81	-0.1	0.1	16.8	0.2	159	4
3930MH0007160021402297C00	2297	15174	2.69	-0.1	0.1	16.4	0.2	127	5
3930MH0007160021402298C00	2298	15234	2.59	-0.1	0.1	16.0	0.2	95	6
3930MH0007160021402299C00	2299	15294	2.49	0.0	0.1	15.7	0.2	63	7
3930MH0007160021402300C00	2300	15354	2.39	0.0	0.1	15.3	0.2	31	8

UPDATED: 31_August_2023

SOL 3930 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Styx - stereo-1 - ~13 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3930MH0008490011402304C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3931MH0001700001402363R00	2363	MOTOR COUNT:		13340	RANGE (cm):	14.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3931MH0001700001402364S00	2364	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00849	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	27-Aug-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00170	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		36	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3930	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3931	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3930MH0008490021402305C00	2305	13196	18.59	-0.9	1.0	72.3	3.3	255	1
3930MH0008490021402306C00	2306	13232	17.49	-0.8	0.8	68.4	2.9	223	2
3930MH0008490021402307C00	2307	13268	16.49	-0.7	0.8	64.9	2.6	191	3
3930MH0008490021402308C00	2308	13304	15.59	-0.7	0.7	61.8	2.3	159	4
3930MH0008490021402309C00	2309	13340	14.76	-0.6	0.6	58.9	2.1	127	5
3930MH0008490021402310C00	2310	13376	14.01	-0.5	0.5	56.2	1.9	95	6
3930MH0008490021402311C00	2311	13412	13.32	-0.5	0.5	53.8	1.7	63	7
3930MH0008490021402312C00	2312	13448	12.69	-0.5	0.5	51.6	1.6	31	8

UPDATED: 31_August_2023

SOL 3930 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Styx - stereo-2 - ~14 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3930MH0008490011402314C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3931MH0001700001402361R00	2361	MOTOR COUNT:		13309	RANGE (cm):	15.5		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3931MH0001700001402362S00	2362	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00849	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	27-Aug-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00170	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		36	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3930	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3931	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3930MH0008490021402315C00	2315	13165	19.64	-1.0	1.1	76.0	3.6	255	1
3930MH0008490021402316C00	2316	13201	18.43	-0.9	0.9	71.8	3.2	223	2
3930MH0008490021402317C00	2317	13237	17.34	-0.8	0.8	67.9	2.9	191	3
3930MH0008490021402318C00	2318	13273	16.36	-0.7	0.7	64.5	2.6	159	4
3930MH0008490021402319C00	2319	13309	15.47	-0.6	0.7	61.4	2.3	127	5
3930MH0008490021402320C00	2320	13345	14.66	-0.6	0.6	58.5	2.1	95	6
3930MH0008490021402321C00	2321	13381	13.91	-0.5	0.5	55.9	1.9	63	7
3930MH0008490021402322C00	2322	13417	13.23	-0.5	0.5	53.5	1.7	31	8

UPDATED: 31_August_2023

SOL 3930 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Knossos - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3930MH0001820011402326C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3931MH0001700001402359R00	2359	MOTOR COUNT:		13975	RANGE (cm):	7.0		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3931MH0001700001402360S00	2360	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00182	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	27-Aug-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00170	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3930	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3931	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3930MH0001820021402327C00	2327	13879	7.71	-0.2	0.2	34.0	0.7	255	1
3930MH0001820021402328C00	2328	13903	7.53	-0.2	0.2	33.4	0.7	223	2
3930MH0001820021402329C00	2329	13927	7.35	-0.2	0.2	32.8	0.6	191	3
3930MH0001820021402330C00	2330	13951	7.18	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	159	4
3930MH0001820021402331C00	2331	13975	7.01	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	127	5
3930MH0001820021402332C00	2332	13999	6.85	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	95	6
3930MH0001820021402333C00	2333	14023	6.70	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	63	7
3930MH0001820021402334C00	2334	14047	6.55	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 31_August_2023

SOL 3930 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Knossos - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3930MH0001820011402336C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3931MH0001700001402357R00	2357	MOTOR COUNT:		13962	RANGE (cm):	7.1		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3931MH0001700001402358S00	2358	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00182	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	27-Aug-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00170	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3930	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3931	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3930MH0001820021402337C00	2337	13866	7.81	-0.2	0.2	34.4	0.7	255	1
3930MH0001820021402338C00	2338	13890	7.63	-0.2	0.2	33.7	0.7	223	2
3930MH0001820021402339C00	2339	13914	7.44	-0.2	0.2	33.1	0.7	191	3
3930MH0001820021402340C00	2340	13938	7.27	-0.2	0.2	32.5	0.6	159	4
3930MH0001820021402341C00	2341	13962	7.10	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	127	5
3930MH0001820021402342C00	2342	13986	6.94	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	95	6
3930MH0001820021402343C00	2343	14010	6.78	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	63	7
3930MH0001820021402344C00	2344	14034	6.63	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	31	8

UPDATED: 31_August_2023

SOL 3930 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Knossos - ~1 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3930MH0008640011402346C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3931MH0001700001402355R00	2355	MOTOR COUNT:		14972	RANGE (cm):	3.1		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3931MH0001700001402356S00	2356	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00864	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	27-Aug-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00170	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3930	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3931	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3930MH0008640021402347C00	2347	14852	3.38	-0.1	0.1	18.8	0.2	255	1
3930MH0008640021402348C00	2348	14882	3.31	-0.1	0.1	18.5	0.2	223	2
3930MH0008640021402349C00	2349	14912	3.24	-0.1	0.1	18.3	0.2	191	3
3930MH0008640021402350C00	2350	14942	3.17	-0.1	0.1	18.0	0.2	159	4
3930MH0008640021402351C00	2351	14972	3.10	-0.1	0.1	17.8	0.2	127	5
3930MH0008640021402352C00	2352	15002	3.03	-0.1	0.1	17.6	0.2	95	6
3930MH0008640021402353C00	2353	15032	2.97	-0.1	0.1	17.4	0.2	63	7
3930MH0008640021402354C00	2354	15062	2.91	-0.1	0.1	17.1	0.2	31	8

UPDATED: 06_September_2023

SOL 3934 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Paion - stereo-1 - ~45 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3934MH0001820011402374C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3934MH0002650001402395R00	2395	MOTOR COUNT:		14058	RANGE (cm):	6.5		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3934MH0002650001402396S00	2396	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00182	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	31-Aug-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00265	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3934	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3934	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3934MH0001820021402375C00	2375	13962	7.10	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	255	1
3934MH0001820021402376C00	2376	13986	6.94	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	223	2
3934MH0001820021402377C00	2377	14010	6.78	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	191	3
3934MH0001820021402378C00	2378	14034	6.63	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	159	4
3934MH0001820021402379C00	2379	14058	6.48	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	127	5
3934MH0001820021402380C00	2380	14082	6.33	-0.2	0.1	29.2	0.5	95	6
3934MH0001820021402381C00	2381	14106	6.20	-0.1	0.1	28.7	0.5	63	7
3934MH0001820021402382C00	2382	14130	6.06	-0.1	0.1	28.2	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 06_September_2023

SOL 3934 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Paion - stereo-2 - ~45 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3934MH0001820011402384C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3934MH0002650001402393R00	2393	MOTOR COUNT:		14059	RANGE (cm):	6.5		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3934MH0002650001402394S00	2394	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00182	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	31-Aug-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00265	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3934	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3934	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3934MH0001820021402385C00	2385	13963	7.09	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	255	1
3934MH0001820021402386C00	2386	13987	6.93	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	223	2
3934MH0001820021402387C00	2387	14011	6.77	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	191	3
3934MH0001820021402388C00	2388	14035	6.62	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	159	4
3934MH0001820021402389C00	2389	14059	6.47	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	127	5
3934MH0001820021402390C00	2390	14083	6.33	-0.2	0.1	29.2	0.5	95	6
3934MH0001820021402391C00	2391	14107	6.19	-0.1	0.1	28.7	0.5	63	7
3934MH0001820021402392C00	2392	14131	6.06	-0.1	0.1	28.2	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 19_September_2023

SOL 3937 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Areopoli - after DRT - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - ~55 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3937MH0001680011402404C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3938MH0001630001402481R00	2481	MOTOR COUNT:		13950	RANGE (cm):	7.2		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3938MH0001630001402482S00	2482	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	3-Sep-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	3937	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3938		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3937MH0001680021402405C00	2405	13878	7.72	-0.2	0.2	34.1	0.7	255	1
3937MH0001680021402406C00	2406	13896	7.58	-0.2	0.2	33.6	0.7	223	2
3937MH0001680021402407C00	2407	13914	7.44	-0.2	0.2	33.1	0.7	191	3
3937MH0001680021402408C00	2408	13932	7.31	-0.2	0.2	32.6	0.6	159	4
3937MH0001680021402409C00	2409	13950	7.18	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	127	5
3937MH0001680021402410C00	2410	13968	7.06	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	95	6
3937MH0001680021402411C00	2411	13986	6.94	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	63	7
3937MH0001680021402412C00	2412	14004	6.82	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	31	8

UPDATED: 19_September_2023

SOL 3937 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Areopoli - after DRT - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3937MH0001680011402414C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3938MH0001630001402479R00	2479	MOTOR COUNT:		13962	RANGE (cm):	7.1		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3938MH0001630001402480S00	2480	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	3-Sep-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	3937	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3938		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3937MH0001680021402415C00	2415	13890	7.63	-0.2	0.2	33.7	0.7	255	1
3937MH0001680021402416C00	2416	13908	7.49	-0.2	0.2	33.3	0.7	223	2
3937MH0001680021402417C00	2417	13926	7.36	-0.2	0.2	32.8	0.6	191	3
3937MH0001680021402418C00	2418	13944	7.23	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	159	4
3937MH0001680021402419C00	2419	13962	7.10	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	127	5
3937MH0001680021402420C00	2420	13980	6.98	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	95	6
3937MH0001680021402421C00	2421	13998	6.86	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	63	7
3937MH0001680021402422C00	2422	14016	6.74	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	31	8

UPDATED: 19_September_2023

SOL 3937 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Areopoli - after DRT - ~1 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3937MH0007430011402430C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3938MH0001630001402477R00	2477	MOTOR COUNT:		14963	RANGE (cm):		3.1	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3938MH0001630001402478S00	2478	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00743	STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	3-Sep-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		36	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3937	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3938	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3937MH0007430021402431C00	2431	14819	3.46	-0.1	0.1	19.1	0.3	255	1
3937MH0007430021402432C00	2432	14855	3.37	-0.1	0.1	18.8	0.2	223	2
3937MH0007430021402433C00	2433	14891	3.28	-0.1	0.1	18.5	0.2	191	3
3937MH0007430021402434C00	2434	14927	3.20	-0.1	0.1	18.2	0.2	159	4
3937MH0007430021402435C00	2435	14963	3.12	-0.1	0.1	17.9	0.2	127	5
3937MH0007430021402436C00	2436	14999	3.04	-0.1	0.1	17.6	0.2	95	6
3937MH0007430021402437C00	2437	15035	2.96	-0.1	0.1	17.3	0.2	63	7
3937MH0007430021402438C00	2438	15071	2.89	-0.1	0.1	17.1	0.2	31	8

UPDATED: 19_September_2023

SOL 3937 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Artemisio - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3937MH0001820011402442C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3938MH0001630001402475R00	2475	MOTOR COUNT:		13955	RANGE (cm):		7.1	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3938MH0001630001402476S00	2476	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00182	STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	3-Sep-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3937	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3938	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3937MH0001820021402443C00	2443	13859	7.87	-0.2	0.2	34.6	0.7	255	1
3937MH0001820021402444C00	2444	13883	7.68	-0.2	0.2	33.9	0.7	223	2
3937MH0001820021402445C00	2445	13907	7.50	-0.2	0.2	33.3	0.7	191	3
3937MH0001820021402446C00	2446	13931	7.32	-0.2	0.2	32.7	0.6	159	4
3937MH0001820021402447C00	2447	13955	7.15	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	127	5
3937MH0001820021402448C00	2448	13979	6.98	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	95	6
3937MH0001820021402449C00	2449	14003	6.82	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	63	7
3937MH0001820021402450C00	2450	14027	6.67	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	31	8

UPDATED: 19_September_2023

SOL 3937 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Artemisio - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3937MH0001820011402452C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3938MH0001630001402473R00	2473	MOTOR COUNT:		13956	RANGE (cm):	7.1		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3938MH0001630001402474S00	2474	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00182	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	3-Sep-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3937	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3938	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3937MH0001820021402453C00	2453	13860	7.86	-0.2	0.2	34.6	0.7	255	1
3937MH0001820021402454C00	2454	13884	7.67	-0.2	0.2	33.9	0.7	223	2
3937MH0001820021402455C00	2455	13908	7.49	-0.2	0.2	33.3	0.7	191	3
3937MH0001820021402456C00	2456	13932	7.31	-0.2	0.2	32.6	0.6	159	4
3937MH0001820021402457C00	2457	13956	7.14	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	127	5
3937MH0001820021402458C00	2458	13980	6.98	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	95	6
3937MH0001820021402459C00	2459	14004	6.82	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	63	7
3937MH0001820021402460C00	2460	14028	6.66	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	31	8

UPDATED: 19_September_2023

SOL 3937 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Artemisio - after DRT - ~1 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3937MH0004260011402462C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3938MH0001630001402471R00	2471	MOTOR COUNT:		14973	RANGE (cm):	3.1		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3938MH0001630001402472S00	2472	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00426	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	3-Sep-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		48	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3937	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3938	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3937MH0004260021402463C00	2463	14781	3.56	-0.1	0.1	19.4	0.3	255	1
3937MH0004260021402464C00	2464	14829	3.44	-0.1	0.1	19.0	0.2	223	2
3937MH0004260021402465C00	2465	14877	3.32	-0.1	0.1	18.6	0.2	191	3
3937MH0004260021402466C00	2466	14925	3.21	-0.1	0.1	18.2	0.2	159	4
3937MH0004260021402467C00	2467	14973	3.10	-0.1	0.1	17.8	0.2	127	5
3937MH0004260021402468C00	2468	15021	2.99	-0.1	0.1	17.4	0.2	95	6
3937MH0004260021402469C00	2469	15069	2.90	-0.1	0.1	17.1	0.2	63	7
3937MH0004260021402470C00	2470	15117	2.80	-0.1	0.1	16.8	0.2	31	8

UPDATED: 20_September_2023

SOL 3943 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

	target Hydra – after DRT – stereo-1 – ~45 mm standoff								
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3943MH0001680011402486C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3943MH0002270001402545R00	2545	MOTOR COUNT:		14039	RANGE (cm):	6.6		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3943MH0002270001402546S00	2546	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	9-Sep-23	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3943	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3943	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3943MH0001680021402487C00	2487	13967	7.07	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	255	1
3943MH0001680021402488C00	2488	13985	6.94	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	223	2
3943MH0001680021402489C00	2489	14003	6.82	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	191	3
3943MH0001680021402490C00	2490	14021	6.71	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	159	4
3943MH0001680021402491C00	2491	14039	6.59	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	127	5
3943MH0001680021402492C00	2492	14057	6.48	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	95	6
3943MH0001680021402493C00	2493	14075	6.38	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	63	7
3943MH0001680021402494C00	2494	14093	6.27	-0.1	0.1	29.0	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 20_September_2023

SOL 3943 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

	target Hydra – after DRT – stereo-2 – ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3943MH0001680011402496C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3943MH0002270001402543R00	2543	MOTOR COUNT:		14007	RANGE (cm):	6.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3943MH0002270001402544S00	2544	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	9-Sep-23	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3943	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3943	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3943MH0001680021402497C00	2497	13935	7.29	-0.2	0.2	32.6	0.6	255	1
3943MH0001680021402498C00	2498	13953	7.16	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	223	2
3943MH0001680021402499C00	2499	13971	7.04	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	191	3
3943MH0001680021402500C00	2500	13989	6.92	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	159	4
3943MH0001680021402501C00	2501	14007	6.80	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	127	5
3943MH0001680021402502C00	2502	14025	6.68	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	95	6
3943MH0001680021402503C00	2503	14043	6.57	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	63	7
3943MH0001680021402504C00	2504	14061	6.46	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	31	8

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SOL 3943 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Hydra – after DRT – ~2 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3943MH0003020011402506C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3943MH0002270001402541R00	2541	MOTOR COUNT:		14679	RANGE (cm):		3.8	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3943MH0002270001402542S00	2542	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00302	STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	9-Sep-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3943	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3943	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3943MH0003020021402507C00	2507	14559	4.22	-0.1	0.1	21.8	0.3	255	1
3943MH0003020021402508C00	2508	14589	4.12	-0.1	0.1	21.4	0.3	223	2
3943MH0003020021402509C00	2509	14619	4.03	-0.1	0.1	21.1	0.3	191	3
3943MH0003020021402510C00	2510	14649	3.93	-0.1	0.1	20.7	0.3	159	4
3943MH0003020021402511C00	2511	14679	3.84	-0.1	0.1	20.4	0.3	127	5
3943MH0003020021402512C00	2512	14709	3.76	-0.1	0.1	20.1	0.3	95	6
3943MH0003020021402513C00	2513	14739	3.67	-0.1	0.1	19.8	0.3	63	7
3943MH0003020021402514C00	2514	14769	3.59	-0.1	0.1	19.5	0.3	31	8

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SOL 3943 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Dodoni – stereo-1 – ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3943MH0003060011402518C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3943MH0002270001402539R00	2539	MOTOR COUNT:		14002	RANGE (cm):		6.8	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3943MH0002270001402540S00	2540	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00306	STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	9-Sep-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		54	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3943	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3943	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3943MH0003060021402519C00	3519	13786	8.49	-0.2	0.2	36.8	0.8	255	1
3943MH0003060021402520C00	3520	13840	8.03	-0.2	0.2	35.2	0.7	223	2
3943MH0003060021402521C00	3521	13894	7.60	-0.2	0.2	33.6	0.7	191	3
3943MH0003060021402522C00	3522	13948	7.20	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	159	4
3943MH0003060021402523C00	3523	14002	6.83	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	127	5
3943MH0003060021402524C00	3524	14056	6.49	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	95	6
3943MH0003060021402525C00	3525	14110	6.17	-0.1	0.1	28.6	0.5	63	7
3943MH0003060021402526C00	3526	14164	5.88	-0.1	0.1	27.6	0.4	31	8

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SOL 3943 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Dodoni – stereo-2 – ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3943MH0003060011402528C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3943MH0002270001402537R00	2537	MOTOR COUNT:		14003	RANGE (cm):		6.8	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3943MH0002270001402538S00	2538	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00306		STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	9-Sep-23		MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227		MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		54	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3943		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3943
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3943MH0003060021402529C00	2529	13787	8.48	-0.2	0.2	36.8	0.8	255	1
3943MH0003060021402530C00	2530	13841	8.02	-0.2	0.2	35.1	0.7	223	2
3943MH0003060021402531C00	2531	13895	7.59	-0.2	0.2	33.6	0.7	191	3
3943MH0003060021402532C00	2532	13949	7.19	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	159	4
3943MH0003060021402533C00	2533	14003	6.82	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	127	5
3943MH0003060021402534C00	2534	14057	6.48	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	95	6
3943MH0003060021402535C00	2535	14111	6.17	-0.1	0.1	28.6	0.5	63	7
3943MH0003060021402536C00	2536	14165	5.87	-0.1	0.1	27.6	0.4	31	8

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SOL 3946 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Antikythera – after DRT – stereo-1 – ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3946MH0001680011402550C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3946MH0001930001402583R00	2583	MOTOR COUNT:		13999	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3946MH0001930001402584S00	2584	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	12-Sep-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3946	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3946	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3946MH0001680021402551C00	2551	13927	7.35	-0.2	0.2	32.8	0.6	255	1
3946MH0001680021402552C00	2552	13945	7.22	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	223	2
3946MH0001680021402553C00	2553	13963	7.09	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	191	3
3946MH0001680021402554C00	2554	13981	6.97	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	159	4
3946MH0001680021402555C00	2555	13999	6.85	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	127	5
3946MH0001680021402556C00	2556	14017	6.73	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	95	6
3946MH0001680021402557C00	2557	14035	6.62	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	63	7
3946MH0001680021402558C00	2558	14053	6.51	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	31	8

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SOL 3946 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Antikythera – after DRT – stereo-2 – ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3946MH0001680011402560C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3946MH0001930001402581R00	2581	MOTOR COUNT:		14005	RANGE (cm):	6.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3946MH0001930001402582S00	2582	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	12-Sep-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3946	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3946	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3946MH0001680021402561C00	2561	13933	7.31	-0.2	0.2	32.6	0.6	255	1
3946MH0001680021402562C00	2562	13951	7.18	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	223	2
3946MH0001680021402563C00	2563	13969	7.05	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	191	3
3946MH0001680021402564C00	2564	13987	6.93	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	159	4
3946MH0001680021402565C00	2565	14005	6.81	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	127	5
3946MH0001680021402566C00	2566	14023	6.70	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	95	6
3946MH0001680021402567C00	2567	14041	6.58	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	63	7
3946MH0001680021402568C00	2568	14059	6.47	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	31	8

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SOL 3946 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Antikythera – after DRT – ~2 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3946MH0003020011402570C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3946MH0001930001402579R00	2579	MOTOR COUNT:		14700	RANGE (cm):		3.8	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3946MH0001930001402580S00	2580	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00302	STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	12-Sep-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3946	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3946	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3946MH0003020021402571C00	2571	14580	4.15	-0.1	0.1	21.5	0.3	255	1
3946MH0003020021402572C00	2572	14610	4.05	-0.1	0.1	21.2	0.3	223	2
3946MH0003020021402573C00	2573	14640	3.96	-0.1	0.1	20.8	0.3	191	3
3946MH0003020021402574C00	2574	14670	3.87	-0.1	0.1	20.5	0.3	159	4
3946MH0003020021402575C00	2575	14700	3.78	-0.1	0.1	20.2	0.3	127	5
3946MH0003020021402576C00	2576	14730	3.70	-0.1	0.1	19.9	0.3	95	6
3946MH0003020021402577C00	2577	14760	3.62	-0.1	0.1	19.6	0.3	63	7
3946MH0003020021402578C00	2578	14790	3.54	-0.1	0.1	19.4	0.3	31	8

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SOL 3948 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

	first merge of: target Mosquito_Flat – after DRT – stereo-1 – ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3948MH0001680011402588C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3948MH0001930001402621R00	2621	MOTOR COUNT:		13994	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3948MH0001930001402622S00	2622	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	14-Sep-23	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3948	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3948	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3948MH0001680021402589C00	2589	13922	7.39	-0.2	0.2	32.9	0.6	255	1
3948MH0001680021402590C00	2590	13940	7.26	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	223	2
3948MH0001680021402591C00	2591	13958	7.13	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	191	3
3948MH0001680021402592C00	2592	13976	7.00	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	159	4
3948MH0001680021402593C00	2593	13994	6.88	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	127	5
3948MH0001680021402594C00	2594	14012	6.77	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	95	6
3948MH0001680021402595C00	2595	14030	6.65	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	63	7
3948MH0001680021402596C00	2596	14048	6.54	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 21_September_2023

SOL 3948 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

	second merge of: target Mosquito_Flat – after DRT – stereo-1 – ~5 cm standoff – merge was performed after a fault occurred onboard the rover that prevented a new focus stack acquisition on Sol 3953								
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3948MH0001680011402588C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3953MH0001930001402627R00	2627	MOTOR COUNT:		13994	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3953MH0001930001402628S00	2628	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	14-Sep-23	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3948	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3953	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3948MH0001680021402589C00	2589	13922	7.39	-0.2	0.2	32.9	0.6	255	1
3948MH0001680021402590C00	2590	13940	7.26	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	223	2
3948MH0001680021402591C00	2591	13958	7.13	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	191	3
3948MH0001680021402592C00	2592	13976	7.00	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	159	4
3948MH0001680021402593C00	2593	13994	6.88	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	127	5
3948MH0001680021402594C00	2594	14012	6.77	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	95	6
3948MH0001680021402595C00	2595	14030	6.65	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	63	7
3948MH0001680021402596C00	2596	14048	6.54	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	31	8

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SOL 3948 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

	first merge of: target Mosquito_Flat – after DRT – stereo-2 – ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3948MH0001680011402598C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3948MH0001930001402619R00	2619	MOTOR COUNT:		13993	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3948MH0001930001402620S00	2620	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	14-Sep-23	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3948	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3948	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3948MH0001680021402599C00	2599	13921	7.39	-0.2	0.2	32.9	0.6	255	1
3948MH0001680021402600C00	2600	13939	7.26	-0.2	0.2	32.5	0.6	223	2
3948MH0001680021402601C00	2601	13957	7.14	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	191	3
3948MH0001680021402602C00	2602	13975	7.01	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	159	4
3948MH0001680021402603C00	2603	13993	6.89	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	127	5
3948MH0001680021402604C00	2604	14011	6.77	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	95	6
3948MH0001680021402605C00	2605	14029	6.66	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	63	7
3948MH0001680021402606C00	2606	14047	6.55	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 21_September_2023

SOL 3948 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

	second merge of: target Mosquito_Flat – after DRT – stereo-2 – ~5 cm standoff – merge was performed after a fault occurred onboard the rover that prevented a new focus stack acquisition on Sol 3953								
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3948MH0001680011402598C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3953MH0001930001402625R00	2625	MOTOR COUNT:		13993	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3953MH0001930001402626S00	2626	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	14-Sep-23	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3948	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3953	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3948MH0001680021402599C00	2599	13921	7.39	-0.2	0.2	32.9	0.6	255	1
3948MH0001680021402600C00	2600	13939	7.26	-0.2	0.2	32.5	0.6	223	2
3948MH0001680021402601C00	2601	13957	7.14	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	191	3
3948MH0001680021402602C00	2602	13975	7.01	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	159	4
3948MH0001680021402603C00	2603	13993	6.89	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	127	5
3948MH0001680021402604C00	2604	14011	6.77	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	95	6
3948MH0001680021402605C00	2605	14029	6.66	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	63	7
3948MH0001680021402606C00	2606	14047	6.55	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	31	8

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SOL 3948 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

	first merge of: target Mosquito_Flat – after DRT – ~15 mm standoff								
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3948MH0008640011402608C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3948MH0001930001402617R00	2617	MOTOR COUNT:		14852	RANGE (cm):	3.4		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3948MH0001930001402618S00	2618	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00864	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	14-Sep-23	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3948	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3948	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3948MH0008640021402609C00	2609	14732	3.69	-0.1	0.1	19.9	0.3	255	1
3948MH0008640021402610C00	2610	14762	3.61	-0.1	0.1	19.6	0.3	223	2
3948MH0008640021402611C00	2611	14792	3.53	-0.1	0.1	19.3	0.3	191	3
3948MH0008640021402612C00	2612	14822	3.45	-0.1	0.1	19.1	0.3	159	4
3948MH0008640021402613C00	2613	14852	3.38	-0.1	0.1	18.8	0.2	127	5
3948MH0008640021402614C00	2614	14882	3.31	-0.1	0.1	18.5	0.2	95	6
3948MH0008640021402615C00	2615	14912	3.24	-0.1	0.1	18.3	0.2	63	7
3948MH0008640021402616C00	2616	14942	3.17	-0.1	0.1	18.0	0.2	31	8

UPDATED: 21_September_2023

SOL 3948 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

	second merge of: target Mosquito_Flat – after DRT – ~15 mm standoff – merge was performed after a fault occurred onboard the rover that prevented a new focus stack acquisition on Sol 3953								
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3948MH0008640011402608C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3953MH0001930001402623R00	2623	MOTOR COUNT:		14852	RANGE (cm):	3.4		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3953MH0001930001402624S00	2624	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00864	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	14-Sep-23	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3948	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3953	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3948MH0008640021402609C00	2609	14732	3.69	-0.1	0.1	19.9	0.3	255	1
3948MH0008640021402610C00	2610	14762	3.61	-0.1	0.1	19.6	0.3	223	2
3948MH0008640021402611C00	2611	14792	3.53	-0.1	0.1	19.3	0.3	191	3
3948MH0008640021402612C00	2612	14822	3.45	-0.1	0.1	19.1	0.3	159	4
3948MH0008640021402613C00	2613	14852	3.38	-0.1	0.1	18.8	0.2	127	5
3948MH0008640021402614C00	2614	14882	3.31	-0.1	0.1	18.5	0.2	95	6
3948MH0008640021402615C00	2615	14912	3.24	-0.1	0.1	18.3	0.2	63	7
3948MH0008640021402616C00	2616	14942	3.17	-0.1	0.1	18.0	0.2	31	8

UPDATED: 22_September_2023

SOL 3955 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Sugarloaf - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3955MH0001680011402632C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3955MH0002270001402689R00	2689	MOTOR COUNT:		14026	RANGE (cm):		6.7	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3955MH0002270001402690S00	2690	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168		STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	21-Sep-23		MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227		MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3955		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3955
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3955MH0001680021402633C00	2633	13954	7.16	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	255	1
3955MH0001680021402634C00	2634	13972	7.03	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	223	2
3955MH0001680021402635C00	2635	13990	6.91	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	191	3
3955MH0001680021402636C00	2636	14008	6.79	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	159	4
3955MH0001680021402637C00	2637	14026	6.68	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	127	5
3955MH0001680021402638C00	2638	14044	6.56	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	95	6
3955MH0001680021402639C00	2639	14062	6.45	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	63	7
3955MH0001680021402640C00	2640	14080	6.35	-0.2	0.1	29.2	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 22_September_2023

SOL 3955 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Sugarloaf - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3955MH0001680011402642C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3955MH0002270001402687R00	2687	MOTOR COUNT:		14023	RANGE (cm):		6.7	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3955MH0002270001402688S00	2688	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168		STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	21-Sep-23		MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227		MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3955		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3955
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3955MH0001680021402643C00	2643	13951	7.18	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	255	1
3955MH0001680021402644C00	2644	13969	7.05	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	223	2
3955MH0001680021402645C00	2645	13987	6.93	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	191	3
3955MH0001680021402646C00	2646	14005	6.81	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	159	4
3955MH0001680021402647C00	2647	14023	6.70	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	127	5
3955MH0001680021402648C00	2648	14041	6.58	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	95	6
3955MH0001680021402649C00	2649	14059	6.47	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	63	7
3955MH0001680021402650C00	2650	14077	6.36	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 22_September_2023

SOL 3955 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Sugarloaf – after DRT – ~1 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3955MH0007430011402652C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3955MH0002270001402685R00	2685	MOTOR COUNT:		15184	RANGE (cm):	2.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3955MH0002270001402686S00	2686	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00743	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	21-Sep-23	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		36	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3955	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3955	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3955MH0007430021402653C00	2653	15040	2.95	-0.1	0.1	17.3	0.2	255	1
3955MH0007430021402654C00	2654	15076	2.88	-0.1	0.1	17.0	0.2	223	2
3955MH0007430021402655C00	2655	15112	2.81	-0.1	0.1	16.8	0.2	191	3
3955MH0007430021402656C00	2656	15148	2.74	-0.1	0.1	16.6	0.2	159	4
3955MH0007430021402657C00	2657	15184	2.68	-0.1	0.1	16.3	0.2	127	5
3955MH0007430021402658C00	2658	15220	2.61	-0.1	0.1	16.1	0.2	95	6
3955MH0007430021402659C00	2659	15256	2.55	-0.1	0.1	15.9	0.2	63	7
3955MH0007430021402660C00	2660	15292	2.49	0.0	0.1	15.7	0.2	31	8

UPDATED: 22_September_2023

SOL 3955 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Toms_Place – mosaic position 1 of 2 – ~25 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3955MH0008650011402662C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3955MH0002270001402683R00	2683	MOTOR COUNT:		13017	RANGE (cm):	26.5		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3955MH0002270001402684S00	2684	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00865	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	21-Sep-23	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3955	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3955	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3955MH0008650021402663C00	2663	12921	33.82	-2.8	3.4	126.0	10.9	255	1
3955MH0008650021402664C00	2664	12945	31.68	-2.5	2.9	118.4	9.5	223	2
3955MH0008650021402665C00	2665	12969	29.77	-2.2	2.6	111.7	8.4	191	3
3955MH0008650021402666C00	2666	12993	28.06	-2.0	2.3	105.7	7.4	159	4
3955MH0008650021402667C00	2667	13017	26.52	-1.8	2.0	100.3	6.6	127	5
3955MH0008650021402668C00	2668	13041	25.13	-1.6	1.8	95.4	6.0	95	6
3955MH0008650021402669C00	2669	13065	23.87	-1.5	1.6	90.9	5.4	63	7
3955MH0008650021402670C00	2670	13089	22.71	-1.3	1.4	86.9	4.9	31	8

UPDATED: 22_September_2023

SOL 3955 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Toms_Place – mosaic position 2 of 2 – ~27 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3955MH0008650011402672C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3955MH0002270001402681R00	2681	MOTOR COUNT:		12985	RANGE (cm):	28.6		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3955MH0002270001402682S00	2682	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00865	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	21-Sep-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3955	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3955	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3955MH0008650021402673C00	2673	12889	37.15	-3.4	4.1	137.7	13.2	255	1
3955MH0008650021402674C00	2674	12913	34.60	-3.0	3.5	128.7	11.4	223	2
3955MH0008650021402675C00	2675	12937	32.36	-2.6	3.1	120.8	9.9	191	3
3955MH0008650021402676C00	2676	12961	30.38	-2.3	2.7	113.8	8.7	159	4
3955MH0008650021402677C00	2677	12985	28.61	-2.1	2.3	107.6	7.7	127	5
3955MH0008650021402678C00	2678	13009	27.02	-1.8	2.1	102.0	6.9	95	6
3955MH0008650021402679C00	2679	13033	25.58	-1.7	1.9	96.9	6.2	63	7
3955MH0008650021402680C00	2680	13057	24.28	-1.5	1.7	92.4	5.6	31	8

UPDATED: 02_October_2023

SOL 3960 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Silver_Spur - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3960MH0001820011402694C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3960MH0002650001402717R00	2717	MOTOR COUNT:		14014	RANGE (cm):	6.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3960MH0002650001402718S00	2718	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00182	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	26-Sep-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00265	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3960	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3960	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3960MH0001820021402695C00	2695	13918	7.42	-0.2	0.2	33.0	0.6	255	1
3960MH0001820021402696C00	2696	13942	7.24	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	223	2
3960MH0001820021402697C00	2697	13966	7.07	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	191	3
3960MH0001820021402698C00	2698	13990	6.91	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	159	4
3960MH0001820021402699C00	2699	14014	6.75	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	127	5
3960MH0001820021402700C00	2700	14038	6.60	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	95	6
3960MH0001820021402701C00	2701	14062	6.45	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	63	7
3960MH0001820021402702C00	2702	14086	6.31	-0.1	0.1	29.1	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 02_October_2023

SOL 3960 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Silver_Spur - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3960MH0001820011402704C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3960MH0002650001402715R00	2715	MOTOR COUNT:		14030	RANGE (cm):	6.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3960MH0002650001402716S00	2716	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00182	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	26-Sep-23/27-Sep-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00265	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3960	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3960	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3960MH0001820021402705C00	2705	13934	7.30	-0.2	0.2	32.6	0.6	255	1
3960MH0001820021402706C00	2706	13958	7.13	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	223	2
3960MH0001820021402707C00	2707	13982	6.96	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	191	3
3960MH0001820021402708C00	2708	14006	6.80	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	159	4
3960MH0001820021402709C00	2709	14030	6.65	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	127	5
3960MH0001820021402710C00	2710	14054	6.50	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	95	6
3960MH0001820021402711C00	2711	14078	6.36	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	63	7
3960MH0001820021402712C00	2712	14102	6.22	-0.1	0.1	28.8	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 03_October_2023

SOL 3962 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Burnt_Mountain - before DRT - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3962MH0001730011402722C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3962MH0001530001402778R00	2778	MOTOR COUNT:	14025	RANGE (cm):	6.7			
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3962MH0001530001402779S00	2779	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:	mhli00173	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE			
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	29-Sep-23	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00153	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	3962	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:	3962			
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3962MH0001730021402723C00	2723	13905	7.51	-0.2	0.2	33.3	0.7	255	1
3962MH0001730021402724C00	2724	13935	7.29	-0.2	0.2	32.6	0.6	223	2
3962MH0001730021402725C00	2725	13965	7.08	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	191	3
3962MH0001730021402726C00	2726	13995	6.88	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	159	4
3962MH0001730021402727C00	2727	14025	6.68	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	127	5
3962MH0001730021402728C00	2728	14055	6.50	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	95	6
3962MH0001730021402729C00	2729	14085	6.32	-0.1	0.1	29.1	0.5	63	7
3962MH0001730021402730C00	2730	14115	6.15	-0.1	0.1	28.5	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 03_October_2023

SOL 3962 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Burnt_Mountain - before DRT - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3962MH0001730011402732C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3962MH0001530001402776R00	2776	MOTOR COUNT:	14016	RANGE (cm):	6.7			
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3962MH0001530001402777S00	2777	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:	mhli00173	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE			
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	29-Sep-23	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00153	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	3962	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:	3962			
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3962MH0001730021402733C00	2733	13896	7.58	-0.2	0.2	33.6	0.7	255	1
3962MH0001730021402734C00	2734	13926	7.36	-0.2	0.2	32.8	0.6	223	2
3962MH0001730021402735C00	2735	13956	7.14	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	191	3
3962MH0001730021402736C00	2736	13986	6.94	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	159	4
3962MH0001730021402737C00	2737	14016	6.74	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	127	5
3962MH0001730021402738C00	2738	14046	6.55	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	95	6
3962MH0001730021402739C00	2739	14076	6.37	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	63	7
3962MH0001730021402740C00	2740	14106	6.20	-0.1	0.1	28.7	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 03_October_2023

SOL 3962 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Blackcap_Mountain - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3962MH0002240011402744C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3962MH0001530001402774R00	2774	MOTOR COUNT:		13990	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3962MH0001530001402775S00	2775	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00224	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	29-Sep-23	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00153	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		42	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3962	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3962	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3962MH0002240021402745C00	2745	13822	8.18	-0.2	0.2	35.7	0.7	255	1
3962MH0002240021402746C00	2746	13864	7.83	-0.2	0.2	34.5	0.7	223	2
3962MH0002240021402747C00	2747	13906	7.50	-0.2	0.2	33.3	0.7	191	3
3962MH0002240021402748C00	2748	13948	7.20	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	159	4
3962MH0002240021402749C00	2749	13990	6.91	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	127	5
3962MH0002240021402750C00	2750	14032	6.64	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	95	6
3962MH0002240021402751C00	2751	14074	6.38	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	63	7
3962MH0002240021402752C00	2752	14116	6.14	-0.1	0.1	28.5	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 03_October_2023

SOL 3962 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Blackcap_Mountain - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3962MH0002240011402754C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3962MH0001530001402772R00	2772	MOTOR COUNT:		13994	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3962MH0001530001402773S00	2773	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00224	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	29-Sep-23	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00153	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		42	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3962	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3962	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3962MH0002240021402755C00	2755	13826	8.14	-0.2	0.2	35.6	0.7	255	1
3962MH0002240021402756C00	2756	13868	7.80	-0.2	0.2	34.4	0.7	223	2
3962MH0002240021402757C00	2757	13910	7.47	-0.2	0.2	33.2	0.7	191	3
3962MH0002240021402758C00	2758	13952	7.17	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	159	4
3962MH0002240021402759C00	2759	13994	6.88	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	127	5
3962MH0002240021402760C00	2760	14036	6.61	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.5	95	6
3962MH0002240021402761C00	2761	14078	6.36	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	63	7
3962MH0002240021402762C00	2762	14120	6.12	-0.1	0.1	28.4	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 14_November_2023

SOL 3964 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Clouddripper - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3964MH0003360011402783C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3964MH0001630001402854R00	2854	MOTOR COUNT:		14009	RANGE (cm):	6.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3964MH0001630001402855S00	2855	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	1-Oct-23	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3964	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3964	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3964MH0003360021402784C00	2784	13961	7.11	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	255	1
3964MH0003360021402785C00	2785	13973	7.02	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	223	2
3964MH0003360021402786C00	2786	13985	6.94	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	191	3
3964MH0003360021402787C00	2787	13997	6.86	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	159	4
3964MH0003360021402788C00	2788	14009	6.79	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	127	5
3964MH0003360021402789C00	2789	14021	6.71	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	95	6
3964MH0003360021402790C00	2790	14033	6.63	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	63	7
3964MH0003360021402791C00	2791	14045	6.56	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 14_November_2023

SOL 3964 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Clouddripper - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3964MH0003360011402793C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3964MH0001630001402852R00	2852	MOTOR COUNT:		14017	RANGE (cm):	6.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3964MH0001630001402853S00	2853	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	1-Oct-23	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3964	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3964	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3964MH0003360021402794C00	2794	13969	7.05	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	255	1
3964MH0003360021402795C00	2795	13981	6.97	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	223	2
3964MH0003360021402796C00	2796	13993	6.89	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	191	3
3964MH0003360021402797C00	2797	14005	6.81	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	159	4
3964MH0003360021402798C00	2798	14017	6.73	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	127	5
3964MH0003360021402799C00	2799	14029	6.66	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	95	6
3964MH0003360021402800C00	2800	14041	6.58	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	63	7
3964MH0003360021402801C00	2801	14053	6.51	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 14_November_2023

SOL 3964 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Cloudripper - after DRT - ~1 cm standoff											
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3964MH0008480011402803C00							
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		3964MH0001630001402850R00		2850		MOTOR COUNT:		15134		RANGE (cm):		2.8	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		3964MH0001630001402851S00		2851		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00848		STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		1-Oct-23				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163		MERGE TYPE:		BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3964		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3964			
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8				
				NEAR	FAR								
3964MH0008480021402804C00	2804	15038	2.96	-0.1	0.1	17.3	0.2	255	1				
3964MH0008480021402805C00	2805	15062	2.91	-0.1	0.1	17.1	0.2	223	2				
3964MH0008480021402806C00	2806	15086	2.86	-0.1	0.1	17.0	0.2	191	3				
3964MH0008480021402807C00	2807	15110	2.81	-0.1	0.1	16.8	0.2	159	4				
3964MH0008480021402808C00	2808	15134	2.77	-0.1	0.1	16.6	0.2	127	5				
3964MH0008480021402809C00	2809	15158	2.72	-0.1	0.1	16.5	0.2	95	6				
3964MH0008480021402810C00	2810	15182	2.68	-0.1	0.1	16.3	0.2	63	7				
3964MH0008480021402811C00	2811	15206	2.64	-0.1	0.1	16.2	0.2	31	8				

UPDATED: 14_November_2023

SOL 3964 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target White_Pass - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff											
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3964MH0001680011402815C00							
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		3964MH0001630001402848R00		2848		MOTOR COUNT:		14016		RANGE (cm):		6.7	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		3964MH0001630001402849S00		2849		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168		STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		1-Oct-23				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163		MERGE TYPE:		BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3964		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3964			
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8				
				NEAR	FAR								
3964MH0001680021402816C00	2816	13944	7.23	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	255	1				
3964MH0001680021402817C00	2817	13962	7.10	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	223	2				
3964MH0001680021402818C00	2818	13980	6.98	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	191	3				
3964MH0001680021402819C00	2819	13998	6.86	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	159	4				
3964MH0001680021402820C00	2820	14016	6.74	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	127	5				
3964MH0001680021402821C00	2821	14034	6.63	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	95	6				
3964MH0001680021402822C00	2822	14052	6.51	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	63	7				
3964MH0001680021402823C00	2823	14070	6.41	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	31	8				

UPDATED: 14_November_2023

SOL 3964 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target White_Pass - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3964MH0001680011402825C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3964MH0001630001402846R00	2846	MOTOR COUNT:		14018	RANGE (cm):	6.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3964MH0001630001402847S00	2847	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	1-Oct-23	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	3964	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3964		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3964MH0001680021402826C00	2826	13946	7.21	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	255	1
3964MH0001680021402827C00	2827	13964	7.09	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	223	2
3964MH0001680021402828C00	2828	13982	6.96	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	191	3
3964MH0001680021402829C00	2829	14000	6.84	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	159	4
3964MH0001680021402830C00	2830	14018	6.73	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	127	5
3964MH0001680021402831C00	2831	14036	6.61	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.5	95	6
3964MH0001680021402832C00	2832	14054	6.50	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	63	7
3964MH0001680021402833C00	2833	14072	6.39	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 14_November_2023

SOL 3964 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target White_Pass - after DRT - ~1 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3964MH0007430011402835C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3964MH0001630001402844R00	2844	MOTOR COUNT:		15142	RANGE (cm):	2.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3964MH0001630001402845S00	2845	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00743	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	1-Oct-23	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		36	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	3964	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3964		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3964MH0007430021402836C00	2836	14998	3.04	-0.1	0.1	17.6	0.2	255	1
3964MH0007430021402837C00	2837	15034	2.97	-0.1	0.1	17.3	0.2	223	2
3964MH0007430021402838C00	2838	15070	2.89	-0.1	0.1	17.1	0.2	191	3
3964MH0007430021402839C00	2839	15106	2.82	-0.1	0.1	16.8	0.2	159	4
3964MH0007430021402840C00	2840	15142	2.75	-0.1	0.1	16.6	0.2	127	5
3964MH0007430021402841C00	2841	15178	2.69	-0.1	0.1	16.4	0.2	95	6
3964MH0007430021402842C00	2842	15214	2.62	-0.1	0.1	16.1	0.2	63	7
3964MH0007430021402843C00	2843	15250	2.56	-0.1	0.1	15.9	0.2	31	8

UPDATED: 04_October_2023

SOL 3966 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Burnt_Mountain - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~45 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3966MH0001680011402863C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3967MH0001530001402908R00	2908	MOTOR COUNT:		14044	RANGE (cm):	6.6		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3967MH0001530001402909S00	2909	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	3-Oct-23	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00153	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3966	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3967	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3966MH0001680021402864C00	2864	13972	7.03	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	255	1
3966MH0001680021402865C00	2865	13990	6.91	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	223	2
3966MH0001680021402866C00	2866	14008	6.79	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	191	3
3966MH0001680021402867C00	2867	14026	6.68	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	159	4
3966MH0001680021402868C00	2868	14044	6.56	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	127	5
3966MH0001680021402869C00	2869	14062	6.45	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	95	6
3966MH0001680021402870C00	2870	14080	6.35	-0.2	0.1	29.2	0.5	63	7
3966MH0001680021402871C00	2871	14098	6.24	-0.1	0.1	28.9	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 04_October_2023

SOL 3966 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Burnt_Mountain - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~45 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3966MH0001680011402873C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3967MH0001530001402906R00	2906	MOTOR COUNT:		14042	RANGE (cm):	6.6		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3967MH0001530001402907S00	2907	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	3-Oct-23	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00153	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3966	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3967	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3966MH0001680021402874C00	2874	13970	7.05	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	255	1
3966MH0001680021402875C00	2875	13988	6.92	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	223	2
3966MH0001680021402876C00	2876	14006	6.80	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	191	3
3966MH0001680021402877C00	2877	14024	6.69	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	159	4
3966MH0001680021402878C00	2878	14042	6.58	-0.2	0.2	30.0	0.5	127	5
3966MH0001680021402879C00	2879	14060	6.47	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	95	6
3966MH0001680021402880C00	2880	14078	6.36	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	63	7
3966MH0001680021402881C00	2881	14096	6.25	-0.1	0.1	28.9	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 04_October_2023

SOL 3966 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Burnt_Mountain – after DRT – ~5 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3966MH0007430011402883C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3967MH0001530001402904R00	2904	MOTOR COUNT:		15233	RANGE (cm):		2.6	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3967MH0001530001402905S00	2905	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00743	STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	3-Oct-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00153	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		36	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3966	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3967	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3966MH0007430021402884C00	2884	15089	2.86	-0.1	0.1	17.0	0.2	255	1
3966MH0007430021402885C00	2885	15125	2.79	-0.1	0.1	16.7	0.2	223	2
3966MH0007430021402886C00	2886	15161	2.72	-0.1	0.1	16.5	0.2	191	3
3966MH0007430021402887C00	2887	15197	2.65	-0.1	0.1	16.2	0.2	159	4
3966MH0007430021402888C00	2888	15233	2.59	-0.1	0.1	16.0	0.2	127	5
3966MH0007430021402889C00	2889	15269	2.53	-0.1	0.1	15.8	0.2	95	6
3966MH0007430021402890C00	2890	15305	2.47	0.0	0.1	15.6	0.2	63	7
3966MH0007430021402891C00	2891	15341	2.41	0.0	0.1	15.4	0.2	31	8

UPDATED: 04_October_2023

SOL 3966 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Bearpaw_Meadow – ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3966MH0001680011402893C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3967MH0001530001402902R00	2902	MOTOR COUNT:		13994	RANGE (cm):		6.9	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3967MH0001530001402903S00	2903	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	3-Oct-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00153	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3966	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3967	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3966MH0001680021402894C00	2894	13922	7.39	-0.2	0.2	32.9	0.6	255	1
3966MH0001680021402895C00	2895	13940	7.26	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	223	2
3966MH0001680021402896C00	2896	13958	7.13	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	191	3
3966MH0001680021402897C00	2897	13976	7.00	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	159	4
3966MH0001680021402898C00	2898	13994	6.88	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	127	5
3966MH0001680021402899C00	2899	14012	6.77	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	95	6
3966MH0001680021402900C00	2900	14030	6.65	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	63	7
3966MH0001680021402901C00	2901	14048	6.54	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 09_October_2023

SOL 3968 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Helen_Lake – before DRT – stereo-1 – ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3968MH0001820011402913C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3969MH0002270001402972R00	2972	MOTOR COUNT:		13986	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3969MH0002270001402973S00	2973	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00182	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	5-Oct-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00227	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3968	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3969	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3968MH0001820021402914C00	2914	13890	7.63	-0.2	0.2	33.7	0.7	255	1
3968MH0001820021402915C00	2915	13914	7.44	-0.2	0.2	33.1	0.7	223	2
3968MH0001820021402916C00	2916	13938	7.27	-0.2	0.2	32.5	0.6	191	3
3968MH0001820021402917C00	2917	13962	7.10	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	159	4
3968MH0001820021402918C00	2918	13986	6.94	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	127	5
3968MH0001820021402919C00	2919	14010	6.78	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	95	6
3968MH0001820021402920C00	2920	14034	6.63	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	63	7
3968MH0001820021402921C00	2921	14058	6.48	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 09_October_2023

SOL 3968 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Helen_Lake – before DRT – stereo-2 – ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3968MH0001820011402923C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3969MH0002270001402970R00	2970	MOTOR COUNT:		13989	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3969MH0002270001402971S00	2971	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00182	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	5-Oct-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00227	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3968	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3969	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3968MH0001820021402924C00	2924	13893	7.60	-0.2	0.2	33.7	0.7	255	1
3968MH0001820021402925C00	2925	13917	7.42	-0.2	0.2	33.0	0.6	223	2
3968MH0001820021402926C00	2926	13941	7.25	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	191	3
3968MH0001820021402927C00	2927	13965	7.08	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	159	4
3968MH0001820021402928C00	2928	13989	6.92	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	127	5
3968MH0001820021402929C00	2929	14013	6.76	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	95	6
3968MH0001820021402930C00	2930	14037	6.61	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.5	63	7
3968MH0001820021402931C00	2931	14061	6.46	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	31	8

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SOL 3968 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Helen_Lake - before DRT - ~2 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3968MH0003370011402933C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3969MH0002270001402968R00	2968	MOTOR COUNT:		14642	RANGE (cm):	4.0		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3969MH0002270001402969S00	2969	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00337	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	5-Oct-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00227	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		42	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3968	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3969	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3968MH0003370021402934C00	2934	14474	4.52	-0.1	0.1	22.8	0.3	255	1
3968MH0003370021402935C00	2935	14516	4.37	-0.1	0.1	22.3	0.3	223	2
3968MH0003370021402936C00	2936	14558	4.22	-0.1	0.1	21.8	0.3	191	3
3968MH0003370021402937C00	2937	14600	4.09	-0.1	0.1	21.3	0.3	159	4
3968MH0003370021402938C00	2938	14642	3.96	-0.1	0.1	20.8	0.3	127	5
3968MH0003370021402939C00	2939	14684	3.83	-0.1	0.1	20.4	0.3	95	6
3968MH0003370021402940C00	2940	14726	3.71	-0.1	0.1	20.0	0.3	63	7
3968MH0003370021402941C00	2941	14768	3.60	-0.1	0.1	19.6	0.3	31	8

UPDATED: 09_October_2023

SOL 3968 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Marion_Peak - stereo-1 - ~45 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3968MH0001820011402945C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3969MH0002270001402966R00	2966	MOTOR COUNT:		14095	RANGE (cm):	6.3		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3969MH0002270001402967S00	2967	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00182	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	5-Oct-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00227	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3968	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3969	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3968MH0001820021402946C00	2946	13999	6.85	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	255	1
3968MH0001820021402947C00	2947	14023	6.70	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	223	2
3968MH0001820021402948C00	2948	14047	6.55	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	191	3
3968MH0001820021402949C00	2949	14071	6.40	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	159	4
3968MH0001820021402950C00	2950	14095	6.26	-0.1	0.1	28.9	0.5	127	5
3968MH0001820021402951C00	2951	14119	6.12	-0.1	0.1	28.5	0.5	95	6
3968MH0001820021402952C00	2952	14143	5.99	-0.1	0.1	28.0	0.5	63	7
3968MH0001820021402953C00	2953	14167	5.86	-0.1	0.1	27.5	0.4	31	8

UPDATED: 09_October_2023

SOL 3968 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Marion_Peak – stereo-2 – ~45 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3968MH0001820011402955C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3969MH0002270001402964R00	2964	MOTOR COUNT:		14099	RANGE (cm):		6.2	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3969MH0002270001402965S00	2965	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00182		STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	5-Oct-23		MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227		MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3968		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3969
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3968MH0001820021402956C00	2956	14003	6.82	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	255	1
3968MH0001820021402957C00	2957	14027	6.67	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	223	2
3968MH0001820021402958C00	2958	14051	6.52	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	191	3
3968MH0001820021402959C00	2959	14075	6.38	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	159	4
3968MH0001820021402960C00	2960	14099	6.24	-0.1	0.1	28.9	0.5	127	5
3968MH0001820021402961C00	2961	14123	6.10	-0.1	0.1	28.4	0.5	95	6
3968MH0001820021402962C00	2962	14147	5.97	-0.1	0.1	27.9	0.5	63	7
3968MH0001820021402963C00	2963	14171	5.84	-0.1	0.1	27.5	0.4	31	8

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SOL 3971 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Helen_Lake - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3971MH0001680011402977C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3972MH0001700001403074R00	3074	MOTOR COUNT:		13985	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3972MH0001700001403075S00	3075	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	8-Oct-23	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00170	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3971	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3972	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3971MH0001680021402978C00	2978	13913	7.45	-0.2	0.2	33.1	0.7	255	1
3971MH0001680021402979C00	2979	13931	7.32	-0.2	0.2	32.7	0.6	223	2
3971MH0001680021402980C00	2980	13949	7.19	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	191	3
3971MH0001680021402981C00	2981	13967	7.07	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	159	4
3971MH0001680021402982C00	2982	13985	6.94	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	127	5
3971MH0001680021402983C00	2983	14003	6.82	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	95	6
3971MH0001680021402984C00	2984	14021	6.71	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	63	7
3971MH0001680021402985C00	2985	14039	6.59	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	31	8

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SOL 3971 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Helen_Lake - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3971MH0001680011402987C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3972MH0001700001403072R00	3072	MOTOR COUNT:		13989	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3972MH0001700001403073S00	3073	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	8-Oct-23	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00170	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3971	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3972	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3971MH0001680021402988C00	2988	13917	7.42	-0.2	0.2	33.0	0.6	255	1
3971MH0001680021402989C00	2989	13935	7.29	-0.2	0.2	32.6	0.6	223	2
3971MH0001680021402990C00	2990	13953	7.16	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	191	3
3971MH0001680021402991C00	2991	13971	7.04	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	159	4
3971MH0001680021402992C00	2992	13989	6.92	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	127	5
3971MH0001680021402993C00	2993	14007	6.80	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	95	6
3971MH0001680021402994C00	2994	14025	6.68	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	63	7
3971MH0001680021402995C00	2995	14043	6.57	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	31	8

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SOL 3971 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Helen_Lake - after DRT - ~2 cm standoff								
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3971MH0003020011402997C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		3972MH0001700001403070R00		3070		MOTOR COUNT:		14644	RANGE (cm):	3.9
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		3972MH0001700001403071S00		3071		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00302	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		8-Oct-23				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00170	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3971		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3972
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8	
				NEAR	FAR					
3971MH0003020021402998C00	2998	14524	4.34	-0.1	0.1	22.2	0.3	255	1	
3971MH0003020021402999C00	2999	14554	4.24	-0.1	0.1	21.8	0.3	223	2	
3971MH0003020021403000C00	3000	14584	4.14	-0.1	0.1	21.5	0.3	191	3	
3971MH0003020021403001C00	3001	14614	4.04	-0.1	0.1	21.1	0.3	159	4	
3971MH0003020021403002C00	3002	14644	3.95	-0.1	0.1	20.8	0.3	127	5	
3971MH0003020021403003C00	3003	14674	3.86	-0.1	0.1	20.5	0.3	95	6	
3971MH0003020021403004C00	3004	14704	3.77	-0.1	0.1	20.2	0.3	63	7	
3971MH0003020021403005C00	3005	14734	3.69	-0.1	0.1	19.9	0.3	31	8	

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SOL 3971 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Feather_Peak - stereo-1 - ~4 cm standoff								
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3971MH0001680011403009C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		3972MH0001700001403068R00		3068		MOTOR COUNT:		14128	RANGE (cm):	6.1
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		3972MH0001700001403069S00		3069		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		8-Oct-23				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00170	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3971		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3972
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8	
				NEAR	FAR					
3971MH0001680021403010C00	3010	14056	6.49	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	255	1	
3971MH0001680021403011C00	3011	14074	6.38	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	223	2	
3971MH0001680021403012C00	3012	14092	6.28	-0.1	0.1	29.0	0.5	191	3	
3971MH0001680021403013C00	3013	14110	6.17	-0.1	0.1	28.6	0.5	159	4	
3971MH0001680021403014C00	3014	14128	6.07	-0.1	0.1	28.3	0.5	127	5	
3971MH0001680021403015C00	3015	14146	5.97	-0.1	0.1	27.9	0.5	95	6	
3971MH0001680021403016C00	3016	14164	5.88	-0.1	0.1	27.6	0.4	63	7	
3971MH0001680021403017C00	3017	14182	5.78	-0.1	0.1	27.3	0.4	31	8	

UPDATED: 11_October_2023

SOL 3971 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Feather_Peak - stereo-2 - ~4 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3971MH0001680011403019C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3972MH0001700001403066R00	3066	MOTOR COUNT:		14127	RANGE (cm):	6.1		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3972MH0001700001403067S00	3067	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	8-Oct-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00170	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3971	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3972	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3971MH0001680021403020C00	3020	14055	6.50	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	255	1
3971MH0001680021403021C00	3021	14073	6.39	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	223	2
3971MH0001680021403022C00	3022	14091	6.28	-0.1	0.1	29.0	0.5	191	3
3971MH0001680021403023C00	3023	14109	6.18	-0.1	0.1	28.7	0.5	159	4
3971MH0001680021403024C00	3024	14127	6.08	-0.1	0.1	28.3	0.5	127	5
3971MH0001680021403025C00	3025	14145	5.98	-0.1	0.1	28.0	0.5	95	6
3971MH0001680021403026C00	3026	14163	5.88	-0.1	0.1	27.6	0.4	63	7
3971MH0001680021403027C00	3027	14181	5.79	-0.1	0.1	27.3	0.4	31	8

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SOL 3971 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Heart_Lake - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3971MH0001680011403031C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3972MH0001700001403064R00	3064	MOTOR COUNT:		14009	RANGE (cm):	6.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3972MH0001700001403065S00	3065	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	8-Oct-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00170	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3971	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3972	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3971MH0001680021403032C00	3032	13937	7.28	-0.2	0.2	32.5	0.6	255	1
3971MH0001680021403033C00	3033	13955	7.15	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	223	2
3971MH0001680021403034C00	3034	13973	7.02	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	191	3
3971MH0001680021403035C00	3035	13991	6.90	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	159	4
3971MH0001680021403036C00	3036	14009	6.79	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	127	5
3971MH0001680021403037C00	3037	14027	6.67	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	95	6
3971MH0001680021403038C00	3038	14045	6.56	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	63	7
3971MH0001680021403039C00	3039	14063	6.45	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	31	8

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SOL 3971 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Heart_Lake – stereo-2 – ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3971MH0001680011403041C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3972MH0001700001403062R00	3062	MOTOR COUNT:		14008	RANGE (cm):	6.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3972MH0001700001403063S00	3063	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	8-Oct-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00170	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3971	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3972	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3971MH0001680021403042C00	3042	13936	7.28	-0.2	0.2	32.5	0.6	255	1
3971MH0001680021403043C00	3043	13954	7.16	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	223	2
3971MH0001680021403044C00	3044	13972	7.03	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	191	3
3971MH0001680021403045C00	3045	13990	6.91	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	159	4
3971MH0001680021403046C00	3046	14008	6.79	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	127	5
3971MH0001680021403047C00	3047	14026	6.68	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	95	6
3971MH0001680021403048C00	3048	14044	6.56	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	63	7
3971MH0001680021403049C00	3049	14062	6.45	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	31	8

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SOL 3971 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Heart_Lake – ~1 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3971MH0007430011403051C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3972MH0001700001403060R00	3060	MOTOR COUNT:		15148	RANGE (cm):	2.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3972MH0001700001403061S00	3061	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00743	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	8-Oct-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00170	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		36	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3971	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3972	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3971MH0007430021403052C00	3052	15004	3.03	-0.1	0.1	17.6	0.2	255	1
3971MH0007430021403053C00	3053	15040	2.95	-0.1	0.1	17.3	0.2	223	2
3971MH0007430021403054C00	3054	15076	2.88	-0.1	0.1	17.0	0.2	191	3
3971MH0007430021403055C00	3055	15112	2.81	-0.1	0.1	16.8	0.2	159	4
3971MH0007430021403056C00	3056	15148	2.74	-0.1	0.1	16.6	0.2	127	5
3971MH0007430021403057C00	3057	15184	2.68	-0.1	0.1	16.3	0.2	95	6
3971MH0007430021403058C00	3058	15220	2.61	-0.1	0.1	16.1	0.2	63	7
3971MH0007430021403059C00	3059	15256	2.55	-0.1	0.1	15.9	0.2	31	8

UPDATED: 13_October_2023

SOL 3975 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Sequoia - after DRT - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3975MH0001680011403083C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3975MH0001530001403130R00	3130	MOTOR COUNT:		13987	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3975MH0001530001403131S00	3131	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	12-Oct-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00153	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3975	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3975	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3975MH0001680021403084C00	3084	13915	7.44	-0.2	0.2	33.1	0.6	255	1
3975MH0001680021403085C00	3085	13933	7.31	-0.2	0.2	32.6	0.6	223	2
3975MH0001680021403086C00	3086	13951	7.18	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	191	3
3975MH0001680021403087C00	3087	13969	7.05	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	159	4
3975MH0001680021403088C00	3088	13987	6.93	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	127	5
3975MH0001680021403089C00	3089	14005	6.81	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	95	6
3975MH0001680021403090C00	3090	14023	6.70	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	63	7
3975MH0001680021403091C00	3091	14041	6.58	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 13_October_2023

SOL 3975 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Sequoia - after DRT - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3975MH0001680011403093C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3975MH0001530001403128R00	3128	MOTOR COUNT:		13988	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3975MH0001530001403129S00	3129	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	12-Oct-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00153	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3975	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3975	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3975MH0001680021403094C00	3094	13916	7.43	-0.2	0.2	33.1	0.6	255	1
3975MH0001680021403095C00	3095	13934	7.30	-0.2	0.2	32.6	0.6	223	2
3975MH0001680021403096C00	3096	13952	7.17	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	191	3
3975MH0001680021403097C00	3097	13970	7.05	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	159	4
3975MH0001680021403098C00	3098	13988	6.92	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	127	5
3975MH0001680021403099C00	3099	14006	6.80	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	95	6
3975MH0001680021403100C00	3100	14024	6.69	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	63	7
3975MH0001680021403101C00	3101	14042	6.58	-0.2	0.2	30.0	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 13_October_2023

SOL 3975 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Sequoia - after DRT - APXS spot 2 - ~2 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3975MH0003020011403103C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3975MH0001530001403126R00	3126	MOTOR COUNT:		14648	RANGE (cm):	3.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3975MH0001530001403127S00	3127	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00302	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	12-Oct-23	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00153	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3975	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3975	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3975MH0003020021403104C00	3104	14528	4.32	-0.1	0.1	22.1	0.3	255	1
3975MH0003020021403105C00	3105	14558	4.22	-0.1	0.1	21.8	0.3	223	2
3975MH0003020021403106C00	3106	14588	4.12	-0.1	0.1	21.4	0.3	191	3
3975MH0003020021403107C00	3107	14618	4.03	-0.1	0.1	21.1	0.3	159	4
3975MH0003020021403108C00	3108	14648	3.94	-0.1	0.1	20.8	0.3	127	5
3975MH0003020021403109C00	3109	14678	3.85	-0.1	0.1	20.4	0.3	95	6
3975MH0003020021403110C00	3110	14708	3.76	-0.1	0.1	20.1	0.3	63	7
3975MH0003020021403111C00	3111	14738	3.68	-0.1	0.1	19.8	0.3	31	8

UPDATED: 13_October_2023

SOL 3975 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Sequoia - after DRT - APXS spot 1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3975MH0001680011403113C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3975MH0001530001403124R00	3124	MOTOR COUNT:		13978	RANGE (cm):	7.0		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3975MH0001530001403125S00	3125	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	12-Oct-23	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00153	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3975	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3975	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3975MH0001680021403114C00	3114	13906	7.50	-0.2	0.2	33.3	0.7	255	1
3975MH0001680021403115C00	3115	13924	7.37	-0.2	0.2	32.8	0.6	223	2
3975MH0001680021403116C00	3116	13942	7.24	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	191	3
3975MH0001680021403117C00	3117	13960	7.11	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	159	4
3975MH0001680021403118C00	3118	13978	6.99	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	127	5
3975MH0001680021403119C00	3119	13996	6.87	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	95	6
3975MH0001680021403120C00	3120	14014	6.75	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	63	7
3975MH0001680021403121C00	3121	14032	6.64	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	31	8

UPDATED: 16_October_2023

SOL 3978 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

	target Sequoia2 - after sol 3975 DRT - after sol 3975 drill bit preload test - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff								
			CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3978MH0001680011403135C00			
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3978MH0001530001403182R00	3182	MOTOR COUNT:		13992	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3978MH0001530001403183S00	3183	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	15-Oct-23	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00153	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3978	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3978	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3978MH0001680021403136C00	3136	13920	7.40	-0.2	0.2	32.9	0.6	255	1
3978MH0001680021403137C00	3137	13938	7.27	-0.2	0.2	32.5	0.6	223	2
3978MH0001680021403138C00	3138	13956	7.14	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	191	3
3978MH0001680021403139C00	3139	13974	7.02	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	159	4
3978MH0001680021403140C00	3140	13992	6.90	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	127	5
3978MH0001680021403141C00	3141	14010	6.78	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	95	6
3978MH0001680021403142C00	3142	14028	6.66	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	63	7
3978MH0001680021403143C00	3143	14046	6.55	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 16_October_2023

SOL 3978 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

	target Sequoia2 - after sol 3975 DRT - after sol 3975 drill bit preload test - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff								
			CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3978MH0001680011403145C00			
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3978MH0001530001403180R00	3180	MOTOR COUNT:		13993	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3978MH0001530001403181S00	3181	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	15-Oct-23	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00153	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3978	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3978	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3978MH0001680021403146C00	3146	13921	7.39	-0.2	0.2	32.9	0.6	255	1
3978MH0001680021403147C00	3147	13939	7.26	-0.2	0.2	32.5	0.6	223	2
3978MH0001680021403148C00	3148	13957	7.14	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	191	3
3978MH0001680021403149C00	3149	13975	7.01	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	159	4
3978MH0001680021403150C00	3150	13993	6.89	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	127	5
3978MH0001680021403151C00	3151	14011	6.77	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	95	6
3978MH0001680021403152C00	3152	14029	6.66	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	63	7
3978MH0001680021403153C00	3153	14047	6.55	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 16_October_2023

SOL 3978 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Sequoia2 - after sol 3975 DRT - after sol 3975 drill bit preload test - APXS spot 2 - ~2 cm standoff							
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3978MH0003020011403155C00			
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3978MH0001530001403178R00	3178		MOTOR COUNT:		14666	RANGE (cm):	3.9	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3978MH0001530001403179S00	3179		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00302	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	15-Oct-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00153	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3978	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3978	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3978MH0003020021403156C00	3156	14546	4.26	-0.1	0.1	21.9	0.3	255	1
3978MH0003020021403157C00	3157	14576	4.16	-0.1	0.1	21.6	0.3	223	2
3978MH0003020021403158C00	3158	14606	4.07	-0.1	0.1	21.2	0.3	191	3
3978MH0003020021403159C00	3159	14636	3.97	-0.1	0.1	20.9	0.3	159	4
3978MH0003020021403160C00	3160	14666	3.88	-0.1	0.1	20.6	0.3	127	5
3978MH0003020021403161C00	3161	14696	3.80	-0.1	0.1	20.3	0.3	95	6
3978MH0003020021403162C00	3162	14726	3.71	-0.1	0.1	20.0	0.3	63	7
3978MH0003020021403163C00	3163	14756	3.63	-0.1	0.1	19.7	0.3	31	8

UPDATED: 16_October_2023

SOL 3978 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Sequoia2 - after sol 3975 DRT - after sol 3975 drill bit preload test - APXS spot 1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		3978MH0001680011403165C00			
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	3978MH0001530001403176R00	3176		MOTOR COUNT:		13998	RANGE (cm):	6.9	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	3978MH0001530001403177S00	3177		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	15-Oct-23			MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00153	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		3978	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		3978	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
3978MH0001680021403166C00	3166	13926	7.36	-0.2	0.2	32.8	0.6	255	1
3978MH0001680021403167C00	3167	13944	7.23	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	223	2
3978MH0001680021403168C00	3168	13962	7.10	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	191	3
3978MH0001680021403169C00	3169	13980	6.98	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	159	4
3978MH0001680021403170C00	3170	13998	6.86	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	127	5
3978MH0001680021403171C00	3171	14016	6.74	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	95	6
3978MH0001680021403172C00	3172	14034	6.63	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	63	7
3978MH0001680021403173C00	3173	14052	6.51	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	31	8

6 Image comment, purpose, RATIONALE_DESC

A RATIONALE_DESC accompanies each MAHLI image and each focus merge product archived with the NASA PDS. It is found in in each archived image label file (.LBL).

The RATIONALE_DESC is a text description of the purpose (rationale) behind the acquisition of each MAHLI parent image.

For onboard focus merge products, the RATIONALE_DESC includes information regarding when the merge was performed and which parent images were merged. This information is not automatically tracked by the instrument or ground data system and thus requires human intervention; this is the only pathway by which this information is conveyed to the data user through the NASA PDS archival products.

The MAHLI Team drafts each RATIONALE_DESC as the data are acquired and returned to Earth. Final editing of each RATIONALE_DESC is performed a few months before the data are archived with the NASA PDS. In some cases, an error might be detected in a RATIONALE_DESC some time after the data are first archived; in such a case, the corrections are made in a later release of MAHLI data to the PDS (as long as the mission continues and funding is available to do so).

The pages that follow capture the RATIONALE_DESC for each MAHLI image acquired and lists the ID for the best available image or focus merge product returned to Earth. Note that the RATIONALE_DESC also applies to any other child images spawned by a given parent image and thus there might be additional images, not listed here, that correspond to a given RATIONALE_DESC. In some cases, it was only necessary to return a thumbnail image; the IDs for these are given in orange text. As noted earlier, purple text indicates Image IDs for which the last two characters might differ from those in the NASA PDS archives.

Note that the text on the pages that follow is tiny. We highly recommend that the reader view this document electronically (*i.e.*, PDF file on a computer screen) and magnify the view $\geq 400\%$.

The *MAHLI Image Comment Sheets* that follow include data acquired Sol 3903–3999. During this period, the instrument obtained images and/or performed focus merges on **Sols 3904, 3905, 3906, 3907, 3908, 3909, 3910, 3912, 3914, 3916, 3917, 3921, 3926, 3928, 3930, 3931, 3934, 3937, 3938, 3943, 3946, 3948, 3953, 3955, 3960, 3962, 3964, 3966, 3967, 3968, 3969, 3971, 3972, 3975, 3978.**

updated: 31_July_2023

Sol 3904 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s):	23 Jul 23
camera position:	0
total parent images:	0
focus merges performed:	3
total focus merge products:	6
total parent images + focus merge products:	6

Image ID:
 black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CDPID:
 Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities: Focus stack images from Sol 3902 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00289	Focus Merges	3904MH001930001401669900	1659	target Jamari - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3902 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1651-1658 - best focus image product
		3904MH001930001401660500	1660	target Jamari - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3902 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1651-1658 - range map product
		3904MH001930001401661800	1661	target Jamari - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-0 - standoff near 3 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3902 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1641-1648 - best focus image product
		3904MH001930001401662500	1662	target Jamari - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3902 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1641-1648 - range map product
		3904MH001930001401663800	1663	target Jamari - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3902 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1631-1638 - best focus image product
		3904MH001930001401664500	1664	target Jamari - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3902 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1631-1638 - range map product

updated: 03_August_2023

Sol 3905 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s):	0 Aug 23
camera position:	2
total parent images:	23
focus merges performed:	2
total focus merge products:	4
total parent images + focus merge products:	29

MAHLI imaged the target Novo_Paraiso and the focus stack images were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00190	Novo_Paraiso ~25 cm standoff	3905MH00190001401666C00	1665	autoFocus sub-frame for target Novo_Paraiso - standoff near 25 cm
		3905MH00190001401666C00	1666	target Novo_Paraiso - standoff near 25 cm
mN00168	Novo_Paraiso stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3905MH00168001401667C00	1667	autoFocus sub-frame for target Novo_Paraiso - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3905MH00168001401668C00	1668	target Novo_Paraiso - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3905MH00168001401669C00	1669	target Novo_Paraiso - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3905MH00168001401670C00	1670	target Novo_Paraiso - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3905MH00168001401671C00	1671	target Novo_Paraiso - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3905MH00168001401672C00	1672	target Novo_Paraiso - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3905MH00168001401673C00	1673	target Novo_Paraiso - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3905MH00168001401674C00	1674	target Novo_Paraiso - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3905MH00168001401675C00	1675	target Novo_Paraiso - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3905MH00168001401676C00	1676	target Novo_Paraiso - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00168	Novo_Paraiso stereo-2 ~45 mm standoff	3905MH00168001401677C00	1677	autoFocus sub-frame for target Novo_Paraiso - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
		3905MH00168001401678C00	1678	target Novo_Paraiso - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
		3905MH00168001401679C00	1679	target Novo_Paraiso - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3905MH00168001401680C00	1680	target Novo_Paraiso - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3905MH00168001401681C00	1681	target Novo_Paraiso - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3905MH00168001401682C00	1682	target Novo_Paraiso - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3905MH00168001401683C00	1683	target Novo_Paraiso - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3905MH00168001401684C00	1684	target Novo_Paraiso - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3905MH00168001401685C00	1685	target Novo_Paraiso - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3905MH00168001401686C00	1686	target Novo_Paraiso - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00205	Focus Merges	3905MH00205001401687R00	1687	target Novo_Paraiso - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3905 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1679-1686 - best focus image product
		3905MH00205001401688S00	1688	target Novo_Paraiso - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3905 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1679-1686 - range map product
		3905MH00205001401689R00	1689	target Novo_Paraiso - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3905 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1669-1676 - best focus image product
		3905MH00205001401690S00	1690	target Novo_Paraiso - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3905 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1669-1676 - range map product

updated: 03_August_2023

Sol 3906 - MAHLI Images

		acquired/performed date(s)	0-Aug-23	
		camera position	4	Image ID:
		total parent images	33	black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
		focus merges performed	3	CDPID:
		total focus merge products	6	Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in POS archive product labels
		total parent images + focus merge products	39	
summary of MAHLI activities: MAHLI imaged the DRT brushed target Kefalonia and the focus stack images were merged.				
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN002190	Kefalonia after DRT ~25 cm standoff	3906MH00190001401691C00	1691	autoFocus sub-frame for target Kefalonia - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
		3906MH00190001401692C00	1692	target Kefalonia - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
mN002168	Kefalonia after DRT stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3906MH00168001401693C00	1693	autoFocus sub-frame for target Kefalonia - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3906MH00168001401694C00	1694	target Kefalonia - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3906MH00168001401695C00	1695	target Kefalonia - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3906MH00168001401696C00	1696	target Kefalonia - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3906MH00168001401697C00	1697	target Kefalonia - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3906MH00168001401698C00	1698	target Kefalonia - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3906MH00168001401699C00	1699	target Kefalonia - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3906MH00168001401700C00	1700	target Kefalonia - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3906MH00168001401701C00	1701	target Kefalonia - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3906MH00168001401702C00	1702	target Kefalonia - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN002168	Kefalonia after DRT stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3906MH00168001401703C00	1703	autoFocus sub-frame for target Kefalonia - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3906MH00168001401704C00	1704	target Kefalonia - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3906MH00168001401705C00	1705	target Kefalonia - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3906MH00168001401706C00	1706	target Kefalonia - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3906MH00168001401707C00	1707	target Kefalonia - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3906MH00168001401708C00	1708	target Kefalonia - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3906MH00168001401709C00	1709	target Kefalonia - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3906MH00168001401710C00	1710	target Kefalonia - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3906MH00168001401711C00	1711	target Kefalonia - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3906MH00168001401712C00	1712	target Kefalonia - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN002743	Kefalonia after DRT ~1 cm standoff	3906MH00743001401713C00	1713	autoFocus sub-frame for target Kefalonia - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm
		3906MH00743001401714C00	1714	target Kefalonia - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm
		3906MH00743001401715C00	1715	target Kefalonia - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3906MH00743001401716C00	1716	target Kefalonia - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3906MH00743001401717C00	1717	target Kefalonia - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3906MH00743001401718C00	1718	target Kefalonia - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3906MH00743001401719C00	1719	target Kefalonia - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3906MH00743001401720C00	1720	target Kefalonia - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3906MH00743001401721C00	1721	target Kefalonia - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3906MH00743001401722C00	1722	target Kefalonia - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN002193	Focus Merges	3906MH00193001401723R00	1723	target Kefalonia - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3906 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1713-1722 - best focus image product
		3906MH00193001401724R00	1724	target Kefalonia - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3906 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1715-1722 - range map product
		3906MH00193001401725R00	1725	target Kefalonia - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3906 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1705-1712 - best focus image product
		3906MH00193001401726R00	1726	target Kefalonia - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3906 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1705-1712 - range map product
		3906MH00193001401727R00	1727	target Kefalonia - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3906 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1695-1702 - best focus image product
		3906MH00193001401728R00	1728	target Kefalonia - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3906 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1695-1702 - range map product

updated: 07_August_2023

Sol 3907 - MAHLI Images

acquired(performed date(s))	8-Aug-23
camera position	6
total parent images	64
focus merges performed	0
total focus merge products	0
total parent images + focus merge products	64

MAHLI image the DRT + brushed target Samaria and the target Kythira.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALISE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00190	Samaria after DRT ~24 cm standoff	3907MH00190001401729ZC0D	1729	autofocus sub-frame for target Samaria - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 24 cm
		3907MH00190001401730ZC0D	1730	target Samaria - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 24 cm
mN00168	Samaria after DRT stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3907MH00168001401731ZC0D	1731	autofocus sub-frame for target Samaria - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3907MH00168001401732ZC0D	1732	target Samaria - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3907MH00168001401733ZC0D	1733	target Samaria - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - Image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3907MH00168001401734ZC0D	1734	target Samaria - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - Image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3907MH00168001401735ZC0D	1735	target Samaria - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - Image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3907MH00168001401736ZC0D	1736	target Samaria - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - Image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3907MH00168001401737ZC0D	1737	target Samaria - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - Image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3907MH00168001401738ZC0D	1738	target Samaria - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - Image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3907MH00168001401739ZC0D	1739	target Samaria - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - Image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3907MH00168001401740ZC0D	1740	target Samaria - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - Image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00168	Samaria after DRT stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3907MH00168001401741ZC0D	1741	autofocus sub-frame for target Samaria - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3907MH00168001401742ZC0D	1742	target Samaria - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3907MH00168001401743ZC0D	1743	target Samaria - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - Image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3907MH00168001401744ZC0D	1744	target Samaria - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - Image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3907MH00168001401745ZC0D	1745	target Samaria - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - Image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3907MH00168001401746ZC0D	1746	target Samaria - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - Image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3907MH00168001401747ZC0D	1747	target Samaria - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - Image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3907MH00168001401748ZC0D	1748	target Samaria - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - Image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3907MH00168001401749ZC0D	1749	target Samaria - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - Image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3907MH00168001401750ZC0D	1750	target Samaria - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - Image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00743	Samaria after DRT ~15 mm standoff	3907MH00743001401751ZC0D	1751	autofocus sub-frame for target Samaria - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm
		3907MH00743001401752ZC0D	1752	target Samaria - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm
		3907MH00743001401753ZC0D	1753	target Samaria - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - Image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3907MH00743001401754ZC0D	1754	target Samaria - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - Image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3907MH00743001401755ZC0D	1755	target Samaria - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - Image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3907MH00743001401756ZC0D	1756	target Samaria - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - Image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3907MH00743001401757ZC0D	1757	target Samaria - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - Image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3907MH00743001401758ZC0D	1758	target Samaria - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - Image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3907MH00743001401759ZC0D	1759	target Samaria - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - Image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3907MH00743001401760ZC0D	1760	target Samaria - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - Image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00190	Kythira ~25 cm standoff	3907MH00190001401761ZC0D	1761	autofocus sub-frame for target Kythira - standoff near 25 cm
		3907MH00190001401762ZC0D	1762	target Kythira - standoff near 25 cm
mN00182	Kythira stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3907MH00182001401763ZC0D	1763	autofocus sub-frame for target Kythira - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3907MH00182001401764ZC0D	1764	target Kythira - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3907MH00182001401765ZC0D	1765	target Kythira - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - Image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3907MH00182001401766ZC0D	1766	target Kythira - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - Image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3907MH00182001401767ZC0D	1767	target Kythira - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - Image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3907MH00182001401768ZC0D	1768	target Kythira - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - Image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3907MH00182001401769ZC0D	1769	target Kythira - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - Image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3907MH00182001401770ZC0D	1770	target Kythira - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - Image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3907MH00182001401771ZC0D	1771	target Kythira - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - Image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3907MH00182001401772ZC0D	1772	target Kythira - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - Image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00182	Kythira stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3907MH00182001401773ZC0D	1773	autofocus sub-frame for target Kythira - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3907MH00182001401774ZC0D	1774	target Kythira - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3907MH00182001401775ZC0D	1775	target Kythira - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - Image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3907MH00182001401776ZC0D	1776	target Kythira - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - Image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3907MH00182001401777ZC0D	1777	target Kythira - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - Image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3907MH00182001401778ZC0D	1778	target Kythira - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - Image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3907MH00182001401779ZC0D	1779	target Kythira - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - Image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3907MH00182001401780ZC0D	1780	target Kythira - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - Image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3907MH00182001401781ZC0D	1781	target Kythira - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - Image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3907MH00182001401782ZC0D	1782	target Kythira - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - Image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00426	Kythira ~1 cm standoff	3907MH00426001401783ZC0D	1783	autofocus sub-frame for target Kythira - standoff near 1 cm
		3907MH00426001401784ZC0D	1784	target Kythira - standoff near 1 cm
		3907MH00426001401785ZC0D	1785	target Kythira - standoff near 1 cm - Image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3907MH00426001401786ZC0D	1786	target Kythira - standoff near 1 cm - Image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3907MH00426001401787ZC0D	1787	target Kythira - standoff near 1 cm - Image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3907MH00426001401788ZC0D	1788	target Kythira - standoff near 1 cm - Image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3907MH00426001401789ZC0D	1789	target Kythira - standoff near 1 cm - Image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3907MH00426001401790ZC0D	1790	target Kythira - standoff near 1 cm - Image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3907MH00426001401791ZC0D	1791	target Kythira - standoff near 1 cm - Image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3907MH00426001401792ZC0D	1792	target Kythira - standoff near 1 cm - Image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack

updated: 07_August_2023

Sol 3908 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s):	0 Aug 23
camera position:	0
total parent images:	0
focus merges performed:	6
total focus merge products:	12
total parent images + focus merge products:	12

Image ID: black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CDPID: Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities		Focus stack images from Sol 3907 were merged.		Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	
m1000163	Focus Merges	3908MH00163000140179300	1793	target Kythira - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3907 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1785-1792 - best focus image product
		3908MH001630001401794500	1794	target Kythira - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3907 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1785-1792 - range map product
		3908MH001630001401795900	1795	target Kythira - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3907 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1775-1782 - best focus image product
		3908MH001630001401796500	1796	target Kythira - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3907 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1775-1782 - range map product
		3908MH001630001401797900	1797	target Kythira - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3907 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1765-1772 - best focus image product
		3908MH001630001401798500	1798	target Kythira - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3907 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1765-1772 - range map product
		3908MH001630001401799900	1799	target Samaria - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3907 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1753-1760 - best focus image product
		3908MH001630001401800500	1800	target Samaria - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3907 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1753-1760 - range map product
		3908MH001630001401801900	1801	target Samaria - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3907 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1743-1750 - best focus image product
		3908MH001630001401802500	1802	target Samaria - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3907 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1743-1750 - range map product
		3908MH001630001401803900	1803	target Samaria - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3907 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1733-1740 - best focus image product
		3908MH001630001401804500	1804	target Samaria - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3907 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1733-1740 - range map product

updated: 07_August_2023

Sol 3909 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	5 Aug 23
camera position	7
total parent images	54
focus merges performed	0
total focus merge products	0
total parent images + focus merge products	54

MAHLI imaged the target Kolpos_Megaron and the DRT brushed target Sopot.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00190	Kolpos_Megaron ~24 cm standoff	3909MH001900014018050CD	1805	autofocus sub-frame for target Kolpos_Megaron - standoff near 24 cm
		3909MH001900014018060CD	1806	target Kolpos_Megaron - standoff near 24 cm
mN00224	Kolpos_Megaron stereo-1 ~45 mm standoff	3909MH002240014018070CD	1807	autofocus sub-frame for target Kolpos_Megaron - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm
		3909MH002240014018080CD	1808	target Kolpos_Megaron - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm
		3909MH002240014018090CD	1809	target Kolpos_Megaron - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3909MH002240014018100CD	1810	target Kolpos_Megaron - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3909MH002240014018110CD	1811	target Kolpos_Megaron - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3909MH002240014018120CD	1812	target Kolpos_Megaron - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3909MH002240014018130CD	1813	target Kolpos_Megaron - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3909MH002240014018140CD	1814	target Kolpos_Megaron - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3909MH002240014018150CD	1815	target Kolpos_Megaron - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3909MH002240014018160CD	1816	target Kolpos_Megaron - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00224	Kolpos_Megaron stereo-2 ~4 cm standoff	3909MH002240014018170CD	1817	autofocus sub-frame for target Kolpos_Megaron - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm
		3909MH002240014018180CD	1818	target Kolpos_Megaron - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm
		3909MH002240014018190CD	1819	target Kolpos_Megaron - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3909MH002240014018200CD	1820	target Kolpos_Megaron - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3909MH002240014018210CD	1821	target Kolpos_Megaron - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3909MH002240014018220CD	1822	target Kolpos_Megaron - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3909MH002240014018230CD	1823	target Kolpos_Megaron - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3909MH002240014018240CD	1824	target Kolpos_Megaron - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3909MH002240014018250CD	1825	target Kolpos_Megaron - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3909MH002240014018260CD	1826	target Kolpos_Megaron - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00190	Sopoto after DRT ~25 cm standoff	3909MH001900014018270CD	1827	autofocus sub-frame for target Sopoto - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
		3909MH001900014018280CD	1828	target Sopoto - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
mN00182	Sopoto after DRT stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3909MH001820014018290CD	1829	autofocus sub-frame for target Sopoto - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3909MH001820014018300CD	1830	target Sopoto - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3909MH001820014018310CD	1831	target Sopoto - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3909MH001820014018320CD	1832	target Sopoto - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3909MH001820014018330CD	1833	target Sopoto - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3909MH001820014018340CD	1834	target Sopoto - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3909MH001820014018350CD	1835	target Sopoto - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3909MH001820014018360CD	1836	target Sopoto - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3909MH001820014018370CD	1837	target Sopoto - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3909MH001820014018380CD	1838	target Sopoto - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00182	Sopoto after DRT stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3909MH001820014018390CD	1839	autofocus sub-frame for target Sopoto - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3909MH001820014018400CD	1840	target Sopoto - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3909MH001820014018410CD	1841	target Sopoto - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3909MH001820014018420CD	1842	target Sopoto - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3909MH001820014018430CD	1843	target Sopoto - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3909MH001820014018440CD	1844	target Sopoto - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3909MH001820014018450CD	1845	target Sopoto - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3909MH001820014018460CD	1846	target Sopoto - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3909MH001820014018470CD	1847	target Sopoto - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3909MH001820014018480CD	1848	target Sopoto - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00426	Sopoto after DRT ~15 mm standoff	3909MH004260014018490CD	1849	autofocus sub-frame for target Sopoto - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm
		3909MH004260014018500CD	1850	target Sopoto - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm
		3909MH004260014018510CD	1851	target Sopoto - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3909MH004260014018520CD	1852	target Sopoto - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3909MH004260014018530CD	1853	target Sopoto - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3909MH004260014018540CD	1854	target Sopoto - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3909MH004260014018550CD	1855	target Sopoto - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3909MH004260014018560CD	1856	target Sopoto - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3909MH004260014018570CD	1857	target Sopoto - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3909MH004260014018580CD	1858	target Sopoto - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack

updated: 07_August_2023

Sol 3910 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s):	0-Aug-23
camera position:	0
total parent images:	0
focus merges performed:	5
total focus merge products:	10
total parent images + focus merge products:	10

Image ID:
 black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CDPID:
 Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities: Focus stack images from Sol 3909 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00227	Focus Merges	3910MH000227000140189300	1859	target Sopoto - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3909 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1851-1858 - best focus image product
		3910MH000227000140186050	1860	target Sopoto - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3909 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1851-1858 - range map product
		3910MH000227000140186190	1861	target Sopoto - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-0 - standoff near 3 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3909 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1841-1848 - best focus image product
		3910MH000227000140186250	1862	target Sopoto - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3909 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1841-1848 - range map product
		3910MH000227000140186390	1863	target Sopoto - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3909 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1831-1838 - best focus image product
		3910MH000227000140186450	1864	target Sopoto - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3909 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1831-1838 - range map product
		3910MH000227000140186590	1865	target Kolpos_Megaron - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3909 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1819-1826 - best focus image product
		3910MH000227000140186650	1866	target Kolpos_Megaron - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3909 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1819-1826 - range map product
		3910MH000227000140186790	1867	target Kolpos_Megaron - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3909 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1809-1816 - best focus image product
		3910MH000227000140186850	1868	target Kolpos_Megaron - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3909 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1809-1816 - range map product

updated: 10_August_2023

Sol 3912 - MAHLI Images

		acquired/performed date(s)	8_Aug_23	
		camera positions	4	Image ID:
		total parent images	33	black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
		focus merges performed	3	CPDID:
		total focus merge products	6	Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels
		total parent images + focus merge products	39	
summary of MAHLI activities: MAHLI imaged the DRT + brushed target Ouranopoli and the focus stack images were merged.				
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00190	Ouranopoli after DRT ~25 cm standoff	3912MH00190001401869C00	1869	autoFocus sub-frame for target Ouranopoli - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
		3912MH00190001401870C00	1870	target Ouranopoli - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
mN00182	Ouranopoli after DRT stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3912MH00182001401871C00	1871	autoFocus sub-frame for target Ouranopoli - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3912MH00182001401872C00	1872	target Ouranopoli - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3912MH00182001401873C00	1873	target Ouranopoli - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3912MH00182001401874C00	1874	target Ouranopoli - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3912MH00182001401875C00	1875	target Ouranopoli - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3912MH00182001401876C00	1876	target Ouranopoli - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3912MH00182001401877C00	1877	target Ouranopoli - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3912MH00182001401878C00	1878	target Ouranopoli - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3912MH00182001401879C00	1879	target Ouranopoli - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3912MH00182001401880C00	1880	target Ouranopoli - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00182	Ouranopoli after DRT stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3912MH00182001401881C00	1881	autoFocus sub-frame for target Ouranopoli - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3912MH00182001401882C00	1882	target Ouranopoli - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3912MH00182001401883C00	1883	target Ouranopoli - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3912MH00182001401884C00	1884	target Ouranopoli - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3912MH00182001401885C00	1885	target Ouranopoli - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3912MH00182001401886C00	1886	target Ouranopoli - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3912MH00182001401887C00	1887	target Ouranopoli - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3912MH00182001401888C00	1888	target Ouranopoli - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3912MH00182001401889C00	1889	target Ouranopoli - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3912MH00182001401890C00	1890	target Ouranopoli - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00796	Ouranopoli after DRT ~1 cm standoff	3912MH00796001401891C00	1891	autoFocus sub-frame for target Ouranopoli - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm
		3912MH00796001401892C00	1892	target Ouranopoli - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm
		3912MH00796001401893C00	1893	target Ouranopoli - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3912MH00796001401894C00	1894	target Ouranopoli - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3912MH00796001401895C00	1895	target Ouranopoli - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3912MH00796001401896C00	1896	target Ouranopoli - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3912MH00796001401897C00	1897	target Ouranopoli - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3912MH00796001401898C00	1898	target Ouranopoli - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3912MH00796001401899C00	1899	target Ouranopoli - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3912MH00796001401900C00	1900	target Ouranopoli - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00189	Focus Merges	3912MH00193001401901R00	1901	target Ouranopoli - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3912 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1893-1900 - best focus image product
		3912MH00193001401902S00	1902	target Ouranopoli - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3912 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1893-1900 - range map product
		3912MH00193001401903R00	1903	target Ouranopoli - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3912 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1883-1890 - best focus image product
		3912MH00193001401904S00	1904	target Ouranopoli - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3912 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1883-1890 - range map product
		3912MH00193001401905R00	1905	target Ouranopoli - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3912 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1873-1880 - best focus image product
		3912MH00193001401906S00	1906	target Ouranopoli - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3912 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1873-1880 - range map product

updated: 11_August_2023

Sol 3914 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	10-Aug-23
camera positions	4
total parent images	33
focus merges performed	3
total focus merge products	6
total parent images + focus merge products	39

MAHLI imaged the DRT + brushed target Skepato and the focus stack images were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN002190	Skepato after DRT ~25 cm standoff	3914MH0001900014019070CD	1907	autoFocus sub-frame for target Skepato - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
		3914MH0001900014019080CD	1908	target Skepato - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
mN002198	Skepato after DRT stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3914MH000168002140191000CD	1909	autoFocus sub-frame for target Skepato - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3914MH000168002140191010CD	1910	target Skepato - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3914MH000168002140191100CD	1911	target Skepato - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3914MH000168002140191200CD	1912	target Skepato - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3914MH000168002140191300CD	1913	target Skepato - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3914MH000168002140191400CD	1914	target Skepato - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3914MH000168002140191500CD	1915	target Skepato - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3914MH000168002140191600CD	1916	target Skepato - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3914MH000168002140191700CD	1917	target Skepato - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3914MH000168002140191800CD	1918	target Skepato - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN002198	Skepato after DRT stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3914MH000168002140191900CD	1919	autoFocus sub-frame for target Skepato - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3914MH000168002140192000CD	1920	target Skepato - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3914MH000168002140192100CD	1921	target Skepato - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3914MH000168002140192200CD	1922	target Skepato - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3914MH000168002140192300CD	1923	target Skepato - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3914MH000168002140192400CD	1924	target Skepato - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3914MH000168002140192500CD	1925	target Skepato - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3914MH000168002140192600CD	1926	target Skepato - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3914MH000168002140192700CD	1927	target Skepato - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3914MH000168002140192800CD	1928	target Skepato - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN002743	Skepato after DRT ~1 cm standoff	3914MH000743002140193000CD	1929	autoFocus sub-frame for target Skepato - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm
		3914MH000743002140193010CD	1930	target Skepato - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm
		3914MH000743002140193100CD	1931	target Skepato - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3914MH000743002140193200CD	1932	target Skepato - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3914MH000743002140193300CD	1933	target Skepato - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3914MH000743002140193400CD	1934	target Skepato - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3914MH000743002140193500CD	1935	target Skepato - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3914MH000743002140193600CD	1936	target Skepato - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3914MH000743002140193700CD	1937	target Skepato - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3914MH000743002140193800CD	1938	target Skepato - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN002193	Focus Merges	3914MH000193001401943900CD	1939	target Skepato - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3914 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1931-1938 - best focus image product
		3914MH000193001401944000CD	1940	target Skepato - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3914 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1931-1938 - range map product
		3914MH000193001401943800CD	1941	target Skepato - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3914 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1921-1928 - best focus image product
		3914MH000193001401942900CD	1942	target Skepato - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3914 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1921-1928 - range map product
		3914MH000193001401943000CD	1943	target Skepato - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3914 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1911-1918 - best focus image product
3914MH000193001401944500CD	1944	target Skepato - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3914 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1911-1918 - range map product		

updated: 16_August_2023

Sol 3916 - MAHLI Images

		acquired/performed date(s)	12-Aug-23	
		camera position	14	Image ID:
		total parent images	54	black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
		focus merges performed	0	CDPID:
		total focus merge products	0	Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels
		total parent images + focus merge products	54	
summary of MAHLI activities		MAHLI imaged the DRT & brushed target Ntourourvana.		
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00190	Ntourourvana before DRT ~25 cm standoff	3916MH001900001401945C00	1945	autofocus sub-frame for target Ntourourvana - before dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 25 cm
		3916MH00190001401946C00	1946	target Ntourourvana - before dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 25 cm
mN00122	Ntourourvana before DRT APXS spot 2 ~5 cm standoff	3916MH00122001401947C00	1947	autofocus sub-frame for target Ntourourvana - before dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3916MH00122001401948C00	1948	target Ntourourvana - before dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm
mN00190	Ntourourvana after DRT ~25 cm standoff	3916MH001900001401949C00	1949	autofocus sub-frame for target Ntourourvana - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 25 cm
		3916MH00190001401950C00	1950	target Ntourourvana - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 25 cm
mN00168	Ntourourvana after DRT APXS spot 2 stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3916MH001680001401951C00	1951	autofocus sub-frame for target Ntourourvana - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3916MH00168001401952C00	1952	target Ntourourvana - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3916MH001680021401953C00	1953	target Ntourourvana - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3916MH001680031401954C00	1954	target Ntourourvana - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3916MH001680041401955C00	1955	target Ntourourvana - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3916MH001680051401956C00	1956	target Ntourourvana - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3916MH001680061401957C00	1957	target Ntourourvana - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3916MH001680071401958C00	1958	target Ntourourvana - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3916MH001680081401959C00	1959	target Ntourourvana - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3916MH001680091401960C00	1960	target Ntourourvana - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00168	Ntourourvana after DRT APXS spot 2 stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3916MH001680001401961C00	1961	autofocus sub-frame for target Ntourourvana - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3916MH00168001401962C00	1962	target Ntourourvana - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3916MH001680021401963C00	1963	target Ntourourvana - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3916MH001680031401964C00	1964	target Ntourourvana - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3916MH001680041401965C00	1965	target Ntourourvana - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3916MH001680051401966C00	1966	target Ntourourvana - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3916MH001680061401967C00	1967	target Ntourourvana - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3916MH001680071401968C00	1968	target Ntourourvana - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3916MH001680081401969C00	1969	target Ntourourvana - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3916MH001680091401970C00	1970	target Ntourourvana - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00864	Ntourourvana after DRT APXS spot 1 ~1 cm standoff	3916MH000864001401971C00	1971	autofocus sub-frame for target Ntourourvana - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm
		3916MH000864001401972C00	1972	target Ntourourvana - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm
		3916MH0008640021401973C00	1973	target Ntourourvana - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3916MH0008640031401974C00	1974	target Ntourourvana - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3916MH0008640041401975C00	1975	target Ntourourvana - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3916MH0008640051401976C00	1976	target Ntourourvana - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3916MH0008640061401977C00	1977	target Ntourourvana - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3916MH0008640071401978C00	1978	target Ntourourvana - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3916MH0008640081401979C00	1979	target Ntourourvana - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3916MH0008640091401980C00	1980	target Ntourourvana - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00168	Ntourourvana after DRT APXS spot 1 ~5 cm standoff	3916MH001680001401981C00	1981	autofocus sub-frame for target Ntourourvana - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3916MH00168001401982C00	1982	target Ntourourvana - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3916MH001680021401983C00	1983	target Ntourourvana - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3916MH001680031401984C00	1984	target Ntourourvana - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3916MH001680041401985C00	1985	target Ntourourvana - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3916MH001680051401986C00	1986	target Ntourourvana - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3916MH001680061401987C00	1987	target Ntourourvana - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3916MH001680071401988C00	1988	target Ntourourvana - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3916MH001680081401989C00	1989	target Ntourourvana - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3916MH001680091401990C00	1990	target Ntourourvana - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00148	Ntourourvana after DRT mosaic position 1 of 4 ~9 cm standoff	3916MH001480001401991C00	1991	autofocus sub-frame for target Ntourourvana - after dust removal tool (DRT) - mosaic position 1 of 4 - standoff near 9 cm
		3916MH00148001401992C00	1992	target Ntourourvana - after dust removal tool (DRT) - mosaic position 1 of 4 - standoff near 9 cm
mN00148	Ntourourvana after DRT mosaic position 2 of 4 ~85 mm standoff	3916MH001480001401993C00	1993	autofocus sub-frame for target Ntourourvana - after dust removal tool (DRT) - mosaic position 2 of 4 - standoff near 85 mm
		3916MH00148001401994C00	1994	target Ntourourvana - after dust removal tool (DRT) - mosaic position 2 of 4 - standoff near 85 mm
mN00148	Ntourourvana after DRT mosaic position 3 of 4 ~85 mm standoff	3916MH001480001401995C00	1995	autofocus sub-frame for target Ntourourvana - after dust removal tool (DRT) - mosaic position 3 of 4 - standoff near 85 mm
		3916MH00148001401996C00	1996	target Ntourourvana - after dust removal tool (DRT) - mosaic position 3 of 4 - standoff near 85 mm
mN00148	Ntourourvana after DRT mosaic position 4 of 4 ~85 mm standoff	3916MH001480001401997C00	1997	autofocus sub-frame for target Ntourourvana - after dust removal tool (DRT) - mosaic position 4 of 4 - standoff near 85 mm
		3916MH00148001401998C00	1998	target Ntourourvana - after dust removal tool (DRT) - mosaic position 4 of 4 - standoff near 85 mm

updated: 14_August_2023

Sol 3917 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s):	13-Aug-23
camera position:	0
total parent images:	0
focus merges performed:	4
total focus merge products:	8
total parent images + focus merge products:	8

Image ID:
 black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CDPID:
 Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities: Focus stack images from Sol 3916 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
m1N0013	Focus Merges	3917MH00153000140199900	1999	target Ntourntourvana - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3916 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1963-1970 - best focus image product
		3917MH00153000140200050	2000	target Ntourntourvana - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3916 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1983-1990 - range map product
		3917MH00153000140200190	2001	target Ntourntourvana - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3916 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1973-1990 - best focus image product
		3917MH00153000140200250	2002	target Ntourntourvana - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3916 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1973-1980 - range map product
		3917MH00153000140200390	2003	target Ntourntourvana - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3916 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1963-1970 - best focus image product
		3917MH00153000140200450	2004	target Ntourntourvana - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3916 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1963-1970 - range map product
		3917MH00153000140200590	2005	target Ntourntourvana - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3916 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1953-1960 - best focus image product
		3917MH00153000140200650	2006	target Ntourntourvana - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3916 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1953-1960 - range map product

updated: 14_November_2023

Sol 3921 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	17-Aug-23
camera position	2
total parent images	63
focus merges performed	6
total focus merge products	12
total parent images + focus merge products	74

MAHLI image of the targets Kameniano and Eleftheroupoli. The focus stack images were also merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDP	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)		
mN00865	Kameniano ~25 cm standoff	3921MH000865001402007C00	2007	autofocus sub-frame for target Kameniano1 - standoff near 25 cm		
		3921MH000865001402008C00	2008	target Kameniano1 - standoff near 25 cm		
		3921MH000865001402009C00	2009	target Kameniano1 - standoff near 25 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3921MH000865001402010C00	2010	target Kameniano1 - standoff near 25 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3921MH000865001402011C00	2011	target Kameniano1 - standoff near 25 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3921MH000865001402012C00	2012	target Kameniano1 - standoff near 25 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3921MH000865001402013C00	2013	target Kameniano1 - standoff near 25 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3921MH000865001402014C00	2014	target Kameniano1 - standoff near 25 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3921MH000865001402015C00	2015	target Kameniano1 - standoff near 25 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3921MH000865001402016C00	2016	target Kameniano1 - standoff near 25 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3921MH000380001402017C00	2017	autofocus sub-frame for target Kameniano1 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm		
		3921MH000380001402018C00	2018	target Kameniano1 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm		
		3921MH000380001402019C00	2019	target Kameniano1 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3921MH000380001402020C00	2020	target Kameniano1 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3921MH000380001402021C00	2021	target Kameniano1 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3921MH000380001402022C00	2022	target Kameniano1 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mN00358	Kameniano stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3921MH000380001402023C00	2023	target Kameniano1 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3921MH000380001402024C00	2024	target Kameniano1 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3921MH000380001402025C00	2025	target Kameniano1 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3921MH000380001402026C00	2026	target Kameniano1 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3921MH000380001402027C00	2027	autofocus sub-frame for target Kameniano1 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm		
		3921MH000380001402028C00	2028	target Kameniano1 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm		
		3921MH000380001402029C00	2029	target Kameniano1 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3921MH000380001402030C00	2030	target Kameniano1 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3921MH000380001402031C00	2031	target Kameniano1 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3921MH000380001402032C00	2032	target Kameniano1 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3921MH000380001402033C00	2033	target Kameniano1 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3921MH000380001402034C00	2034	target Kameniano1 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3921MH000380001402035C00	2035	target Kameniano1 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3921MH000380001402036C00	2036	target Kameniano1 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		mN00405	Kameniano ~3 cm standoff	3921MH000405001402037C00	2037	autofocus sub-frame for target Kameniano1 - standoff near 3 cm
				3921MH000405001402038C00	2038	target Kameniano1 - standoff near 3 cm
3921MH000405001402039C00	2039			target Kameniano1 - standoff near 3 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3921MH000405001402040C00	2040			target Kameniano1 - standoff near 3 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3921MH000405001402041C00	2041			target Kameniano1 - standoff near 3 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3921MH000405001402042C00	2042			target Kameniano1 - standoff near 3 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3921MH000405001402043C00	2043			target Kameniano1 - standoff near 3 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3921MH000405001402044C00	2044			target Kameniano1 - standoff near 3 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3921MH000405001402045C00	2045			target Kameniano1 - standoff near 3 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3921MH000405001402046C00	2046			target Kameniano1 - standoff near 3 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mN00190	Eleftheroupoli ~24 cm standoff			3921MH000190001402047C00	2047	autofocus sub-frame for target Eleftheroupoli - standoff near 24 cm
				3921MH000190001402048C00	2048	target Eleftheroupoli - standoff near 24 cm
mN00168	Eleftheroupoli stereo-1 ~45 mm standoff			3921MH000168001402049C00	2049	autofocus sub-frame for target Eleftheroupoli - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm
				3921MH000168001402050C00	2050	target Eleftheroupoli - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm
				3921MH000168001402051C00	2051	target Eleftheroupoli - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
				3921MH000168001402052C00	2052	target Eleftheroupoli - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3921MH000168001402053C00	2053	target Eleftheroupoli - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3921MH000168001402054C00	2054	target Eleftheroupoli - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3921MH000168001402055C00	2055	target Eleftheroupoli - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3921MH000168001402056C00	2056	target Eleftheroupoli - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3921MH000168001402057C00	2057	target Eleftheroupoli - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3921MH000168001402058C00	2058	target Eleftheroupoli - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		mN00168	Eleftheroupoli stereo-2 ~45 mm standoff	3921MH000168001402059C00	2059	autofocus sub-frame for target Eleftheroupoli - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
				3921MH000168001402060C00	2060	target Eleftheroupoli - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
				3921MH000168001402061C00	2061	target Eleftheroupoli - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
				3921MH000168001402062C00	2062	target Eleftheroupoli - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
				3921MH000168001402063C00	2063	target Eleftheroupoli - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
				3921MH000168001402064C00	2064	target Eleftheroupoli - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
3921MH000168001402065C00	2065			target Eleftheroupoli - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3921MH000168001402066C00	2066			target Eleftheroupoli - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3921MH000168001402067C00	2067			target Eleftheroupoli - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3921MH000168001402068C00	2068			target Eleftheroupoli - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		

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mnh00163	Focus Merge	3921MH0016300140206900	2069	target Eleftheroupoli - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3921 with MEL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2061-2068 - best focus image product
		3921MH00163001402070500	2070	target Eleftheroupoli - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3921 with MEL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2061-2068 - range map product
		3921MH00163001402071800	2071	target Eleftheroupoli - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3921 with MEL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2051-2058 - best focus image product
		3921MH00163001402072500	2072	target Eleftheroupoli - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3921 with MEL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2051-2058 - range map product
		3921MH00163001402073800	2073	target Kamenianoi - standoff near 3 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3921 with MEL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2039-2046 - best focus image product
		3921MH00163001402074500	2074	target Kamenianoi - standoff near 3 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3921 with MEL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2039-2046 - range map product
		3921MH00163001402075800	2075	target Kamenianoi - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3921 with MEL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2029-2036 - best focus image product
		3921MH00163001402076500	2076	target Kamenianoi - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3921 with MEL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2029-2036 - range map product
		3921MH00163001402077800	2077	target Kamenianoi - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3921 with MEL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2019-2026 - best focus image product
		3921MH00163001402078500	2078	target Kamenianoi - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3921 with MEL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2019-2026 - range map product
		3921MH00163001402079800	2079	target Kamenianoi - standoff near 25 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3921 with MEL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2009-2016 - best focus image product
		3921MH00163001402080500	2080	target Kamenianoi - standoff near 25 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3921 with MEL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2009-2016 - range map product

Sol 3926 - MAHLI Images

		acquired/performed date(s)		23-Aug-23	
		camera position		13	Image ID:
		total parent images		104	black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
		focus merges performed		10	CDPID:
		total focus merge products		20	Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels
		total parent images + focus merge products		124	
summary of MAHLI activities: MAHLI imaged the target DRT-dusted target Myrkas, acquired a 1x4 vertical mosaic on Myrkas, and imaged the target Helmos. The focus stack images were also merged.					
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALISE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)	
mN00190	Myrkas after DRT ~25 cm standoff	3926MH00190001402081C00	2081	autofocus sub-frame for target Myrkas - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm	
		3926MH00190001402082C00	2082	target Myrkas - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm	
mN00182	Myrkas after DRT stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3926MH00182001402083C00	2083	autofocus sub-frame for target Myrkas - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm	
		3926MH00182001402084C00	2084	target Myrkas - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm	
		3926MH00182001402085C00	2085	target Myrkas - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - Image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3926MH00182001402086C00	2086	target Myrkas - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - Image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3926MH00182001402087C00	2087	target Myrkas - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - Image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3926MH00182001402088C00	2088	target Myrkas - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - Image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3926MH00182001402089C00	2089	target Myrkas - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - Image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3926MH00182001402090C00	2090	target Myrkas - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - Image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3926MH00182001402091C00	2091	target Myrkas - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - Image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3926MH00182001402092C00	2092	target Myrkas - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - Image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack	
mN00182	Myrkas after DRT stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3926MH00182001402093C00	2093	autofocus sub-frame for target Myrkas - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm	
		3926MH00182001402094C00	2094	target Myrkas - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm	
		3926MH00182001402095C00	2095	target Myrkas - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - Image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3926MH00182001402096C00	2096	target Myrkas - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - Image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3926MH00182001402097C00	2097	target Myrkas - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - Image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3926MH00182001402098C00	2098	target Myrkas - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - Image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3926MH00182001402099C00	2099	target Myrkas - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - Image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3926MH00182001402100C00	2100	target Myrkas - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - Image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3926MH00182001402101C00	2101	target Myrkas - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - Image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3926MH00182001402102C00	2102	target Myrkas - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - Image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack	
mN00386	Myrkas after DRT ~1 cm standoff	3926MH00386001402103C00	2103	autofocus sub-frame for target Myrkas - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm	
		3926MH00386001402104C00	2104	target Myrkas - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm	
		3926MH00386001402105C00	2105	target Myrkas - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - Image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3926MH00386001402106C00	2106	target Myrkas - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - Image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3926MH00386001402107C00	2107	target Myrkas - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - Image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3926MH00386001402108C00	2108	target Myrkas - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - Image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3926MH00386001402109C00	2109	target Myrkas - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - Image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3926MH00386001402110C00	2110	target Myrkas - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - Image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3926MH00386001402111C00	2111	target Myrkas - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - Image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3926MH00386001402112C00	2112	target Myrkas - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - Image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack	
mN00152	Myrkas mosaic position 1 of 4 ~4 cm standoff	3926MH00152001402113C00	2113	autofocus sub-frame for target Myrkas - mosaic position 1 of 4 - standoff near 4 cm	
		3926MH00152001402114C00	2114	target Myrkas - mosaic position 1 of 4 - standoff near 4 cm	
		3926MH00152001402115C00	2115	target Myrkas - mosaic position 1 of 4 - standoff near 4 cm - Image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3926MH00152001402116C00	2116	target Myrkas - mosaic position 1 of 4 - standoff near 4 cm - Image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3926MH00152001402117C00	2117	target Myrkas - mosaic position 1 of 4 - standoff near 4 cm - Image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3926MH00152001402118C00	2118	target Myrkas - mosaic position 1 of 4 - standoff near 4 cm - Image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3926MH00152001402119C00	2119	target Myrkas - mosaic position 1 of 4 - standoff near 4 cm - Image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3926MH00152001402120C00	2120	target Myrkas - mosaic position 1 of 4 - standoff near 4 cm - Image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3926MH00152001402121C00	2121	target Myrkas - mosaic position 1 of 4 - standoff near 4 cm - Image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3926MH00152001402122C00	2122	target Myrkas - mosaic position 1 of 4 - standoff near 4 cm - Image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack	
mN00152	Myrkas mosaic position 2 of 4 ~4 cm standoff	3926MH00152001402123C00	2123	autofocus sub-frame for target Myrkas - mosaic position 2 of 4 - standoff near 4 cm	
		3926MH00152001402124C00	2124	target Myrkas - mosaic position 2 of 4 - standoff near 4 cm	
		3926MH00152001402125C00	2125	target Myrkas - mosaic position 2 of 4 - standoff near 4 cm - Image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3926MH00152001402126C00	2126	target Myrkas - mosaic position 2 of 4 - standoff near 4 cm - Image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3926MH00152001402127C00	2127	target Myrkas - mosaic position 2 of 4 - standoff near 4 cm - Image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3926MH00152001402128C00	2128	target Myrkas - mosaic position 2 of 4 - standoff near 4 cm - Image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3926MH00152001402129C00	2129	target Myrkas - mosaic position 2 of 4 - standoff near 4 cm - Image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3926MH00152001402130C00	2130	target Myrkas - mosaic position 2 of 4 - standoff near 4 cm - Image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3926MH00152001402131C00	2131	target Myrkas - mosaic position 2 of 4 - standoff near 4 cm - Image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3926MH00152001402132C00	2132	target Myrkas - mosaic position 2 of 4 - standoff near 4 cm - Image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack	
mN00152	Myrkas mosaic position 3 of 4 ~4 cm standoff	3926MH00152001402133C00	2133	autofocus sub-frame for target Myrkas - mosaic position 3 of 4 - standoff near 4 cm	
		3926MH00152001402134C00	2134	target Myrkas - mosaic position 3 of 4 - standoff near 4 cm	
		3926MH00152001402135C00	2135	target Myrkas - mosaic position 3 of 4 - standoff near 4 cm - Image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3926MH00152001402136C00	2136	target Myrkas - mosaic position 3 of 4 - standoff near 4 cm - Image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3926MH00152001402137C00	2137	target Myrkas - mosaic position 3 of 4 - standoff near 4 cm - Image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3926MH00152001402138C00	2138	target Myrkas - mosaic position 3 of 4 - standoff near 4 cm - Image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3926MH00152001402139C00	2139	target Myrkas - mosaic position 3 of 4 - standoff near 4 cm - Image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3926MH00152001402140C00	2140	target Myrkas - mosaic position 3 of 4 - standoff near 4 cm - Image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3926MH00152001402141C00	2141	target Myrkas - mosaic position 3 of 4 - standoff near 4 cm - Image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3926MH00152001402142C00	2142	target Myrkas - mosaic position 3 of 4 - standoff near 4 cm - Image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack	

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updated: 06_September_2023

Sol 3928 - MAHLI Images

		acquired/performed date(s)	25-Aug-23	
		camera position	7	Image ID:
		total parent images	54	black - best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange - only a thumbnail has been received
		focus merges performed	5	CDPID:
		total focus merge products	10	Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in POS archive product labels
		total parent images + focus merge products	64	
summary of MAHLI activities		MAHLI imaged the targets Epidaurus and Linnæ Styrfälla. The focus stack images were also merged.		
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00190	Epidaurus ~25 cm standoff	3928MH0001900014022050CD	2205	autofocus sub-frame for target Epidaurus - standoff near 25 cm
		3928MH0001900014022060CD	2206	target Epidaurus - standoff near 25 cm
mN00173	Epidaurus stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3928MH0001730014022070CD	2207	autofocus sub-frame for target Epidaurus - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3928MH0001730014022080CD	2208	target Epidaurus - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3928MH0001730014022090CD	2209	target Epidaurus - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3928MH0001730014022100CD	2210	target Epidaurus - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3928MH0001730014022110CD	2211	target Epidaurus - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3928MH0001730014022120CD	2212	target Epidaurus - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3928MH0001730014022130CD	2213	target Epidaurus - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3928MH0001730014022140CD	2214	target Epidaurus - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3928MH0001730014022150CD	2215	target Epidaurus - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3928MH0001730014022160CD	2216	target Epidaurus - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00173	Epidaurus stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3928MH0001730014022170CD	2217	autofocus sub-frame for target Epidaurus - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3928MH0001730014022180CD	2218	target Epidaurus - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3928MH0001730014022190CD	2219	target Epidaurus - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3928MH0001730014022200CD	2220	target Epidaurus - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3928MH0001730014022210CD	2221	target Epidaurus - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3928MH0001730014022220CD	2222	target Epidaurus - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3928MH0001730014022230CD	2223	target Epidaurus - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3928MH0001730014022240CD	2224	target Epidaurus - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3928MH0001730014022250CD	2225	target Epidaurus - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3928MH0001730014022260CD	2226	target Epidaurus - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00176	Epidaurus ~2 cm standoff	3928MH0001760014022270CD	2227	autofocus sub-frame for target Epidaurus - standoff near 2 cm
		3928MH0001760014022280CD	2228	target Epidaurus - standoff near 2 cm
		3928MH0001760014022290CD	2229	target Epidaurus - standoff near 2 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3928MH0001760014022300CD	2230	target Epidaurus - standoff near 2 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3928MH0001760014022310CD	2231	target Epidaurus - standoff near 2 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3928MH0001760014022320CD	2232	target Epidaurus - standoff near 2 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3928MH0001760014022330CD	2233	target Epidaurus - standoff near 2 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3928MH0001760014022340CD	2234	target Epidaurus - standoff near 2 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3928MH0001760014022350CD	2235	target Epidaurus - standoff near 2 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3928MH0001760014022360CD	2236	target Epidaurus - standoff near 2 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00190	Linnæ Styrfälla ~24 cm standoff	3928MH0001900014022370CD	2237	autofocus sub-frame for target Linnæ Styrfälla - standoff near 24 cm
		3928MH0001900014022380CD	2238	target Linnæ Styrfälla - standoff near 24 cm
mN00173	Linnæ Styrfälla stereo-1 ~35 mm standoff	3928MH0001730014022390CD	2239	autofocus sub-frame for target Linnæ Styrfälla - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm
		3928MH0001730014022400CD	2240	target Linnæ Styrfälla - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm
		3928MH0001730014022410CD	2241	target Linnæ Styrfälla - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3928MH0001730014022420CD	2242	target Linnæ Styrfälla - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3928MH0001730014022430CD	2243	target Linnæ Styrfälla - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3928MH0001730014022440CD	2244	target Linnæ Styrfälla - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3928MH0001730014022450CD	2245	target Linnæ Styrfälla - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3928MH0001730014022460CD	2246	target Linnæ Styrfälla - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3928MH0001730014022470CD	2247	target Linnæ Styrfälla - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3928MH0001730014022480CD	2248	target Linnæ Styrfälla - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00173	Linnæ Styrfälla stereo-2 ~35 mm standoff	3928MH0001730014022490CD	2249	autofocus sub-frame for target Linnæ Styrfälla - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm
		3928MH0001730014022500CD	2250	target Linnæ Styrfälla - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm
		3928MH0001730014022510CD	2251	target Linnæ Styrfälla - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3928MH0001730014022520CD	2252	target Linnæ Styrfälla - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3928MH0001730014022530CD	2253	target Linnæ Styrfälla - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3928MH0001730014022540CD	2254	target Linnæ Styrfälla - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3928MH0001730014022550CD	2255	target Linnæ Styrfälla - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3928MH0001730014022560CD	2256	target Linnæ Styrfälla - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3928MH0001730014022570CD	2257	target Linnæ Styrfälla - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3928MH0001730014022580CD	2258	target Linnæ Styrfälla - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00227	Focus Merges	3928MH0002270014022590CD	2259	target Linnæ Styrfälla - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3928 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2251-2258 - best focus image product
		3928MH0002270014022600CD	2260	target Linnæ Styrfälla - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3928 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2251-2259 - range map product
		3928MH0002270014022610CD	2261	target Linnæ Styrfälla - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3928 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2241-2248 - best focus image product
		3928MH0002270014022620CD	2262	target Linnæ Styrfälla - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3928 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2241-2248 - range map product
		3928MH0002270014022630CD	2263	target Epidaurus - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3928 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2229-2236 - best focus image product
		3928MH0002270014022640CD	2264	target Epidaurus - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3928 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2229-2236 - range map product
		3928MH0002270014022650CD	2265	target Epidaurus - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3928 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2219-2226 - best focus image product
		3928MH0002270014022660CD	2266	target Epidaurus - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3928 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2219-2226 - range map product
3928MH0002270014022670CD	2267	target Epidaurus - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3928 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2209-2216 - best focus image product		
3928MH0002270014022680CD	2268	target Epidaurus - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3928 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2209-2216 - range map product		

Sol 3930 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	27_Aug-23
camera position	13
total parent images	85
focus merges performed	0
total focus merge products	0
total parent images + focus merge products	85

Image ID:
 black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CPDPID:
 Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities

MAHLI Image the targets Meteora, Styx and Knossos.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL, DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00148	Meteora ~10 cm standoff	3930MH0014800140226900	2269	autofocus sub-frame for target Meteora - standoff near 10 cm
		3930MH0014800140227000	2270	target Meteora - standoff near 10 cm
mN00173	Meteora stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3930MH0017300140227100	2271	autofocus sub-frame for target Meteora - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3930MH0017300140227200	2272	target Meteora - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3930MH0017300140227300	2273	target Meteora - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3930MH0017300140227400	2274	target Meteora - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3930MH0017300140227500	2275	target Meteora - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3930MH0017300140227600	2276	target Meteora - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3930MH0017300140227700	2277	target Meteora - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3930MH0017300140227800	2278	target Meteora - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3930MH0017300140227900	2279	target Meteora - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3930MH0017300140228000	2280	target Meteora - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00173	Meteora stereo-2 ~45 mm standoff	3930MH0017300140228100	2281	autofocus sub-frame for target Meteora - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
		3930MH0017300140228200	2282	target Meteora - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
		3930MH0017300140228300	2283	target Meteora - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3930MH0017300140228400	2284	target Meteora - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3930MH0017300140228500	2285	target Meteora - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3930MH0017300140228600	2286	target Meteora - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3930MH0017300140228700	2287	target Meteora - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3930MH0017300140228800	2288	target Meteora - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3930MH0017300140228900	2289	target Meteora - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3930MH0017300140229000	2290	target Meteora - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00176	Meteora ~1 cm standoff	3930MH0017600140229100	2291	autofocus sub-frame for target Meteora - standoff near 1 cm
		3930MH0017600140229200	2292	target Meteora - standoff near 1 cm
		3930MH0017600140229300	2293	target Meteora - standoff near 1 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3930MH0017600140229400	2294	target Meteora - standoff near 1 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3930MH0017600140229500	2295	target Meteora - standoff near 1 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3930MH0017600140229600	2296	target Meteora - standoff near 1 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3930MH0017600140229700	2297	target Meteora - standoff near 1 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3930MH0017600140229800	2298	target Meteora - standoff near 1 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3930MH0017600140229900	2299	target Meteora - standoff near 1 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3930MH0017600140230000	2300	target Meteora - standoff near 1 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00190	Styx ~24 cm standoff	3930MH0019000140230100	2301	autofocus sub-frame for target Styx - standoff near 24 cm
		3930MH0019000140230200	2302	target Styx - standoff near 24 cm
mN00849	Styx stereo-1 ~13 cm standoff	3930MH0084900140230300	2303	autofocus sub-frame for target Styx - stereo-1 - standoff near 13 cm
		3930MH0084900140230400	2304	target Styx - stereo-1 - standoff near 13 cm
		3930MH0084900140230500	2305	target Styx - stereo-1 - standoff near 13 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3930MH0084900140230600	2306	target Styx - stereo-1 - standoff near 13 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3930MH0084900140230700	2307	target Styx - stereo-1 - standoff near 13 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3930MH0084900140230800	2308	target Styx - stereo-1 - standoff near 13 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3930MH0084900140230900	2309	target Styx - stereo-1 - standoff near 13 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3930MH0084900140231000	2310	target Styx - stereo-1 - standoff near 13 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3930MH0084900140231100	2311	target Styx - stereo-1 - standoff near 13 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3930MH0084900140231200	2312	target Styx - stereo-1 - standoff near 13 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00849	Styx stereo-2 ~14 cm standoff	3930MH0084900140231300	2313	autofocus sub-frame for target Styx - stereo-2 - standoff near 14 cm
		3930MH0084900140231400	2314	target Styx - stereo-2 - standoff near 14 cm
		3930MH0084900140231500	2315	target Styx - stereo-2 - standoff near 14 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3930MH0084900140231600	2316	target Styx - stereo-2 - standoff near 14 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3930MH0084900140231700	2317	target Styx - stereo-2 - standoff near 14 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3930MH0084900140231800	2318	target Styx - stereo-2 - standoff near 14 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3930MH0084900140231900	2319	target Styx - stereo-2 - standoff near 14 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3930MH0084900140232000	2320	target Styx - stereo-2 - standoff near 14 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3930MH0084900140232100	2321	target Styx - stereo-2 - standoff near 14 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3930MH0084900140232200	2322	target Styx - stereo-2 - standoff near 14 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00190	Knossos ~25 cm standoff	3930MH0019000140232300	2323	autofocus sub-frame for target Knossos - standoff near 25 cm
		3930MH0019000140232400	2324	target Knossos - standoff near 25 cm
mN00182	Knossos stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3930MH0018200140232500	2325	autofocus sub-frame for target Knossos - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3930MH0018200140232600	2326	target Knossos - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3930MH0018200140232700	2327	target Knossos - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3930MH0018200140232800	2328	target Knossos - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3930MH0018200140232900	2329	target Knossos - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3930MH0018200140233000	2330	target Knossos - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3930MH0018200140233100	2331	target Knossos - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3930MH0018200140233200	2332	target Knossos - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3930MH0018200140233300	2333	target Knossos - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3930MH0018200140233400	2334	target Knossos - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack

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mH00182	Knossos stereo-2 -5 cm standoff	9930MH001820001402335C00	2335	autofocus sub-frame for target Knossos - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		9930MH001820011402336C00	2336	target Knossos - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		9930MH001820021402337C00	2337	target Knossos - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		9930MH001820021402338C00	2338	target Knossos - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		9930MH001820021402339C00	2339	target Knossos - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		9930MH001820021402340C00	2340	target Knossos - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		9930MH001820021402341C00	2341	target Knossos - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		9930MH001820021402342C00	2342	target Knossos - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		9930MH001820021402343C00	2343	target Knossos - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
9930MH001820021402344C00	2344	target Knossos - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mH00864	Knossos -1 cm standoff	9930MH000864001402345C00	2345	autofocus sub-frame for target Knossos - standoff near 1 cm
		9930MH0008640011402346C00	2346	target Knossos - standoff near 1 cm
		9930MH000864001402347C00	2347	target Knossos - standoff near 1 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		9930MH000864001402348C00	2348	target Knossos - standoff near 1 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		9930MH000864001402349C00	2349	target Knossos - standoff near 1 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		9930MH000864001402350C00	2350	target Knossos - standoff near 1 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		9930MH000864001402351C00	2351	target Knossos - standoff near 1 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		9930MH000864001402352C00	2352	target Knossos - standoff near 1 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		9930MH000864001402353C00	2353	target Knossos - standoff near 1 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
9930MH000864001402354C00	2354	target Knossos - standoff near 1 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		

updated: 29_August_2023

Sol 3931 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	28-Aug-23
camera position	0
total parent images	0
focus merges performed	8
total focus merge products	16
total parent images + focus merge products	16

Image ID: black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CDPID: Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities

Focus stack images from Sol 3930 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
m1N00070	Focus Merges	3931MH000170000140235900	2335	target Knossos - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3930 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2347-2354 - best focus image product
		3931MH000170000140235600	2356	target Knossos - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3930 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2347-2354 - range map product
		3931MH000170000140235700	2357	target Knossos - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3930 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2337-2344 - best focus image product
		3931MH000170000140235800	2358	target Knossos - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3930 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2337-2344 - range map product
		3931MH000170000140235900	2359	target Knossos - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3930 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2327-2334 - best focus image product
		3931MH000170000140236000	2360	target Knossos - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3930 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2327-2334 - range map product
		3931MH000170000140236100	2361	target Styx - stereo-2 - standoff near 14 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3930 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2315-2322 - best focus image product
		3931MH000170000140236200	2362	target Styx - stereo-2 - standoff near 14 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3930 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2315-2322 - range map product
		3931MH000170000140236300	2363	target Styx - stereo-1 - standoff near 13 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3930 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2305-2312 - best focus image product
		3931MH000170000140236400	2364	target Styx - stereo-1 - standoff near 13 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3930 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2305-2312 - range map product
		3931MH000170000140236500	2365	target Meteora - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3930 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2293-2300 - range map product
		3931MH000170000140236600	2366	target Meteora - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3930 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2293-2300 - range map product
		3931MH000170000140236700	2367	target Meteora - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3930 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2283-2290 - best focus image product
		3931MH000170000140236800	2368	target Meteora - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3930 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2283-2290 - range map product
		3931MH000170000140236900	2369	target Meteora - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3930 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2273-2280 - best focus image product
		3931MH000170000140237000	2370	target Meteora - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3930 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2273-2280 - range map product

updated: 06_September_2023

Sol 3934 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	21-Aug-23
camera position	2
total parent images	23
focus merges performed	2
total focus merge products	4
total parent images + focus merge products	29

MAHLI imaged the target Paion and the focus stack images were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00190	Paion ~24 cm standoff	3934MH00190001402374C00	2371	autoFocus sub-frame for target Paion - standoff near 24 cm
		3934MH00190001402372C00	2372	target Paion - standoff near 24 cm
mN00182	Paion stereo-1 ~45 mm standoff	3934MH00182001402373C00	2373	autoFocus sub-frame for target Paion - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm
		3934MH00182001402374C00	2374	target Paion - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm
		3934MH00182001402375C00	2375	target Paion - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3934MH00182001402376C00	2376	target Paion - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3934MH00182001402377C00	2377	target Paion - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3934MH00182001402378C00	2378	target Paion - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3934MH00182001402379C00	2379	target Paion - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3934MH00182001402380C00	2380	target Paion - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3934MH00182001402381C00	2381	target Paion - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3934MH00182001402382C00	2382	target Paion - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00182	Paion stereo-2 ~45 mm standoff	3934MH00182001402383C00	2383	autoFocus sub-frame for target Paion - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
		3934MH00182001402384C00	2384	target Paion - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
		3934MH00182001402385C00	2385	target Paion - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3934MH00182001402386C00	2386	target Paion - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3934MH00182001402387C00	2387	target Paion - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3934MH00182001402388C00	2388	target Paion - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3934MH00182001402389C00	2389	target Paion - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3934MH00182001402390C00	2390	target Paion - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3934MH00182001402391C00	2391	target Paion - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3934MH00182001402392C00	2392	target Paion - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00205	Focus Merges	3934MH002050001402393R00	2393	target Paion - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3934 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2385-2392 - best focus image product
		3934MH002050001402394S00	2394	target Paion - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3934 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2385-2392 - range map product
		3934MH002050001402395R00	2395	target Paion - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3934 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2375-2382 - best focus image product
		3934MH002050001402396S00	2396	target Paion - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3934 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2375-2382 - range map product

mH00426	Artemisio after DRT ~1 cm standoff	9337MH0004260014024614C00	2461	autofocus sub-frame for target Artemisio - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm
		9337MH0004260014024620C00	2462	target Artemisio - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm
		9337MH0004260014024630C00	2463	target Artemisio - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		9337MH0004260014024640C00	2464	target Artemisio - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		9337MH0004260014024650C00	2465	target Artemisio - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		9337MH0004260014024660C00	2466	target Artemisio - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		9337MH0004260014024670C00	2467	target Artemisio - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		9337MH0004260014024680C00	2468	target Artemisio - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		9337MH0004260014024690C00	2469	target Artemisio - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		9337MH0004260014024700C00	2470	target Artemisio - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack

updated: 14_November_2023

Sol 3938 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s):	6 Sep 23
camera positions:	0
total parent images:	0
focus merges performed:	6
total focus merge products:	12
total parent images + focus merge products:	12

Image ID:
 black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CDPID:
 Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities: Focus stack images from Sol 3937 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
m1000163	Focus Merges	3938MH001630001402471900	2471	target Artemisio - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3937 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2463-2470 - best focus image product
		3938MH001630001402472500	2472	target Artemisio - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3937 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2463-2470 - range map product
		3938MH001630001402473800	2473	target Artemisio - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3937 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2453-2460 - best focus image product
		3938MH001630001402474500	2474	target Artemisio - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3937 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2453-2460 - range map product
		3938MH001630001402475900	2475	target Artemisio - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3937 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2443-2450 - best focus image product
		3938MH001630001402476500	2476	target Artemisio - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3937 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2443-2450 - range map product
		3938MH001630001402477900	2477	target Areopoli - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3937 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2431-2438 - best focus image product
		3938MH001630001402478500	2478	target Areopoli - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3937 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2431-2438 - range map product
		3938MH001630001402479900	2479	target Areopoli - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3937 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2415-2422 - best focus image product
		3938MH001630001402480500	2480	target Areopoli - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3937 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2415-2422 - range map product
		3938MH001630001402481900	2481	target Areopoli - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 55 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3937 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2405-2412 - best focus image product
		3938MH001630001402482500	2482	target Areopoli - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 55 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3937 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2405-2412 - range map product

Sol 3943 - MAHLI Images

		acquired/performed date(s)	8-Sep-23	
		camera position	7	Image ID:
		total parent images	54	black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
		focus merges performed	5	CDPID:
		total focus merge products	10	Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels
		total parent images + focus merge products	64	
summary of MAHLI activities: MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed target Hydra and the target Dodoni. The focus stack images were also merged.				
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00190	Hydra after DRT ~25 cm standoff	3943MH00190001402483C0D	2483	autofocus sub-frame for target Hydra - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
		3943MH00190001402484C0D	2484	target Hydra - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
mN00168	Hydra after DRT stereo-1 ~45 mm standoff	3943MH00168001402485C0D	2485	autofocus sub-frame for target Hydra - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm
		3943MH00168001402486C0D	2486	target Hydra - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm
		3943MH00168001402487C0D	2487	target Hydra - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3943MH00168001402488C0D	2488	target Hydra - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3943MH00168001402489C0D	2489	target Hydra - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3943MH00168001402490C0D	2490	target Hydra - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3943MH00168001402491C0D	2491	target Hydra - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3943MH00168001402492C0D	2492	target Hydra - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3943MH00168001402493C0D	2493	target Hydra - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3943MH00168001402494C0D	2494	target Hydra - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00168	Hydra after DRT stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3943MH00168001402495C0D	2495	autofocus sub-frame for target Hydra - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3943MH00168001402496C0D	2496	target Hydra - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3943MH00168001402497C0D	2497	target Hydra - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3943MH00168001402498C0D	2498	target Hydra - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3943MH00168001402499C0D	2499	target Hydra - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3943MH00168001402500C0D	2500	target Hydra - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3943MH00168001402501C0D	2501	target Hydra - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3943MH00168001402502C0D	2502	target Hydra - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3943MH00168001402503C0D	2503	target Hydra - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3943MH00168001402504C0D	2504	target Hydra - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00302	Hydra after DRT stereo-2 ~2 cm standoff	3943MH00302001402505C0D	2505	autofocus sub-frame for target Hydra - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm
		3943MH00302001402506C0D	2506	target Hydra - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm
		3943MH00302001402507C0D	2507	target Hydra - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3943MH00302001402508C0D	2508	target Hydra - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3943MH00302001402509C0D	2509	target Hydra - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3943MH00302001402510C0D	2510	target Hydra - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3943MH00302001402511C0D	2511	target Hydra - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3943MH00302001402512C0D	2512	target Hydra - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3943MH00302001402513C0D	2513	target Hydra - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3943MH00302001402514C0D	2514	target Hydra - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00190	Dodoni ~25 cm standoff	3943MH00190001402515C0D	2515	autofocus sub-frame for target Dodoni - standoff near 25 cm
		3943MH00190001402516C0D	2516	target Dodoni - standoff near 25 cm
mN00306	Dodoni stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3943MH00306001402517C0D	2517	autofocus sub-frame for target Dodoni - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3943MH00306001402518C0D	2518	target Dodoni - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3943MH00306001402519C0D	2519	target Dodoni - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3943MH00306001402520C0D	2520	target Dodoni - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3943MH00306001402521C0D	2521	target Dodoni - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3943MH00306001402522C0D	2522	target Dodoni - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3943MH00306001402523C0D	2523	target Dodoni - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3943MH00306001402524C0D	2524	target Dodoni - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3943MH00306001402525C0D	2525	target Dodoni - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3943MH00306001402526C0D	2526	target Dodoni - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00306	Dodoni stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3943MH00306001402527C0D	2527	autofocus sub-frame for target Dodoni - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3943MH00306001402528C0D	2528	target Dodoni - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3943MH00306001402529C0D	2529	target Dodoni - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3943MH00306001402530C0D	2530	target Dodoni - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3943MH00306001402531C0D	2531	target Dodoni - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3943MH00306001402532C0D	2532	target Dodoni - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3943MH00306001402533C0D	2533	target Dodoni - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3943MH00306001402534C0D	2534	target Dodoni - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3943MH00306001402535C0D	2535	target Dodoni - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3943MH00306001402536C0D	2536	target Dodoni - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00227	Focus Merges	3943MH000227001402537R0D	2537	target Dodoni - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3943 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2529-2536 - best focus image product
		3943MH000227001402538S0D	2538	target Dodoni - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3943 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2529-2536 - range map product
		3943MH000227001402539R0D	2539	target Dodoni - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3943 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2519-2526 - best focus image product
		3943MH000227001402540S0D	2540	target Dodoni - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3943 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2519-2526 - range map product
		3943MH000227001402541R0D	2541	target Hydra - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3943 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2507-2514 - best focus image product
		3943MH000227001402542S0D	2542	target Hydra - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3943 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2507-2514 - range map product
		3943MH000227001402543R0D	2543	target Hydra - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3943 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2497-2504 - best focus image product
		3943MH000227001402544S0D	2544	target Hydra - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3943 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2497-2504 - range map product
		3943MH000227001402545R0D	2545	target Hydra - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3943 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2487-2494 - best focus image product
		3943MH000227001402546S0D	2546	target Hydra - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3943 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2487-2494 - range map product

updated: 21_September_2023

Sol 3946 - MAHLI Images

summary of MAHLI activities		MAHLI imaged the DRT + brushed target Antikythera and the focus stack images were merged.		Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)	
acquired/performed date(s)		12-Sep-23		Image ID:	
camera position		4		black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received	
total parent images		33		CDPID:	
focus merges performed		3		Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in POS archive product labels	
total focus merge products		6			
total parent images + focus merge products		39			
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID		
mN002190	Antikythera after DRT ~25 cm standoff	3946MH00190001402547000	2547	autofocus sub-frame for target Antikythera - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm	
		3946MH00190001402548000	2548	target Antikythera - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm	
mN002168	Antikythera after DRT stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3946MH00168001402549000	2549	autofocus sub-frame for target Antikythera - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm	
		3946MH00168001402550000	2550	target Antikythera - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm	
		3946MH00168001402551000	2551	target Antikythera - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3946MH00168001402552000	2552	target Antikythera - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3946MH00168001402553000	2553	target Antikythera - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3946MH00168001402554000	2554	target Antikythera - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3946MH00168001402555000	2555	target Antikythera - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3946MH00168001402556000	2556	target Antikythera - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3946MH00168001402557000	2557	target Antikythera - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3946MH00168001402558000	2558	target Antikythera - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack	
mN002168	Antikythera after DRT stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3946MH00168001402559000	2559	autofocus sub-frame for target Antikythera - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm	
		3946MH00168001402560000	2560	target Antikythera - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm	
		3946MH00168001402561000	2561	target Antikythera - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3946MH00168001402562000	2562	target Antikythera - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3946MH00168001402563000	2563	target Antikythera - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3946MH00168001402564000	2564	target Antikythera - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3946MH00168001402565000	2565	target Antikythera - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3946MH00168001402566000	2566	target Antikythera - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3946MH00168001402567000	2567	target Antikythera - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3946MH00168001402568000	2568	target Antikythera - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack	
mN002302	Antikythera after DRT ~2 cm standoff	3946MH00302001402569000	2569	autofocus sub-frame for target Antikythera - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm	
		3946MH00302001402570000	2570	target Antikythera - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm	
		3946MH00302001402571000	2571	target Antikythera - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3946MH00302001402572000	2572	target Antikythera - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3946MH00302001402573000	2573	target Antikythera - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3946MH00302001402574000	2574	target Antikythera - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3946MH00302001402575000	2575	target Antikythera - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3946MH00302001402576000	2576	target Antikythera - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3946MH00302001402577000	2577	target Antikythera - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3946MH00302001402578000	2578	target Antikythera - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack	
mN002193	Focus Merges	3946MH00193001402579000	2579	target Antikythera - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3946 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2571-2578 - best focus image product	
		3946MH00193001402580000	2580	target Antikythera - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3946 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2571-2578 - range map product	
		3946MH00193001402581000	2581	target Antikythera - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3946 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2561-2568 - best focus image product	
		3946MH00193001402582000	2582	target Antikythera - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3946 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2561-2568 - range map product	
		3946MH00193001402583000	2583	target Antikythera - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3946 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2551-2558 - best focus image product	
3946MH00193001402584000	2584	target Antikythera - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3946 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2551-2558 - range map product			

updated: 20_September_2023

Sol 3953 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	18-Sep-23
camera position	0
total parent images	0
focus merges performed	3
total focus merge products	6
total parent images + focus merge products	6

Image ID: black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CDPID: Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities: The focus stack images from Sol 3948 were merged again; this happened because a fault occurred onboard the rover that prevented acquisition and merge of new MAHLI data planned for the DRT-brushed target Sugarloaf.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00189	Focus Merges	3953MH001930001402623900	2623	target Mosquito_Flat - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3948 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2609-2616 - best focus image product
		3953MH001930001402624500	2624	target Mosquito_Flat - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3948 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2609-2616 - range map product
		3953MH001930001402625900	2625	target Mosquito_Flat - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3948 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2599-2606 - best focus image product
		3953MH001930001402626500	2626	target Mosquito_Flat - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3948 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2599-2606 - range map product
		3953MH001930001402627900	2627	target Mosquito_Flat - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3948 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2589-2596 - best focus image product
		3953MH001930001402628500	2628	target Mosquito_Flat - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3948 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2589-2596 - range map product

updated: 22_September_2023

Sol 3955 - MAHLI Images

		acquired/performed date(s)		21-Sep-23	
		camera position	53	Image ID:	
		total parent images	5	black - best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange - only a thumbnail has been received	
		focus merges performed	5	CDPID:	
		total focus merge products	10	Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels	
		total parent images + focus merge products	53		
summary of MAHLI activities: MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed target Sugarloaf (brushed on Sol 3953) and acquired a 2x1 mosaic of the target Toms_Place.					
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)	
mN00190	Sugarloaf after sol 3953 DRT ~25 cm standoff	3955MH001900001402629ZC00	2629	autofocus sub-frame for target Sugarloaf - after sol 3953 dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm	
		3955MH00190001402630ZC00	2630	target Sugarloaf - after sol 3953 dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm	
mN00168	Sugarloaf after sol 3953 DRT stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3955MH001680001402631ZC00	2631	autofocus sub-frame for target Sugarloaf - after sol 3953 dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm	
		3955MH00168001402632ZC00	2632	target Sugarloaf - after sol 3953 dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm	
		3955MH00168001402633ZC00	2633	target Sugarloaf - after sol 3953 dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3955MH00168001402634ZC00	2634	target Sugarloaf - after sol 3953 dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3955MH00168001402635ZC00	2635	target Sugarloaf - after sol 3953 dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3955MH00168001402636ZC00	2636	target Sugarloaf - after sol 3953 dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3955MH00168001402637ZC00	2637	target Sugarloaf - after sol 3953 dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3955MH00168001402638ZC00	2638	target Sugarloaf - after sol 3953 dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3955MH00168001402639ZC00	2639	target Sugarloaf - after sol 3953 dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3955MH00168001402640ZC00	2640	target Sugarloaf - after sol 3953 dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack	
mN00168	Sugarloaf after sol 3953 DRT stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3955MH001680001402641ZC00	2641	autofocus sub-frame for target Sugarloaf - after sol 3953 dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm	
		3955MH00168001402642ZC00	2642	target Sugarloaf - after sol 3953 dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm	
		3955MH00168001402643ZC00	2643	target Sugarloaf - after sol 3953 dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3955MH00168001402644ZC00	2644	target Sugarloaf - after sol 3953 dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3955MH00168001402645ZC00	2645	target Sugarloaf - after sol 3953 dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3955MH00168001402646ZC00	2646	target Sugarloaf - after sol 3953 dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3955MH00168001402647ZC00	2647	target Sugarloaf - after sol 3953 dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3955MH00168001402648ZC00	2648	target Sugarloaf - after sol 3953 dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3955MH00168001402649ZC00	2649	target Sugarloaf - after sol 3953 dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3955MH00168001402650ZC00	2650	target Sugarloaf - after sol 3953 dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack	
mN00743	Sugarloaf after sol 3953 DRT stereo-2 ~1 cm standoff	3955MH007430001402651ZC00	2651	autofocus sub-frame for target Sugarloaf - after sol 3953 dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm	
		3955MH00743001402652ZC00	2652	target Sugarloaf - after sol 3953 dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm	
		3955MH00743001402653ZC00	2653	target Sugarloaf - after sol 3953 dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3955MH00743001402654ZC00	2654	target Sugarloaf - after sol 3953 dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3955MH00743001402655ZC00	2655	target Sugarloaf - after sol 3953 dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3955MH00743001402656ZC00	2656	target Sugarloaf - after sol 3953 dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3955MH00743001402657ZC00	2657	target Sugarloaf - after sol 3953 dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3955MH00743001402658ZC00	2658	target Sugarloaf - after sol 3953 dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3955MH00743001402659ZC00	2659	target Sugarloaf - after sol 3953 dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3955MH00743001402660ZC00	2660	target Sugarloaf - after sol 3953 dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack	
mN00865	Toms_Place mosaic position 1 of 2 ~25 cm standoff	3955MH008650001402661ZC00	2661	autofocus sub-frame for target Toms_Place - mosaic position 1 of 2 - standoff near 25 cm	
		3955MH00865001402662ZC00	2662	target Toms_Place - mosaic position 1 of 2 - standoff near 25 cm	
		3955MH00865001402663ZC00	2663	target Toms_Place - mosaic position 1 of 2 - standoff near 25 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3955MH00865001402664ZC00	2664	target Toms_Place - mosaic position 1 of 2 - standoff near 25 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3955MH00865001402665ZC00	2665	target Toms_Place - mosaic position 1 of 2 - standoff near 25 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3955MH00865001402666ZC00	2666	target Toms_Place - mosaic position 1 of 2 - standoff near 25 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3955MH00865001402667ZC00	2667	target Toms_Place - mosaic position 1 of 2 - standoff near 25 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3955MH00865001402668ZC00	2668	target Toms_Place - mosaic position 1 of 2 - standoff near 25 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3955MH00865001402669ZC00	2669	target Toms_Place - mosaic position 1 of 2 - standoff near 25 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3955MH00865001402670ZC00	2670	target Toms_Place - mosaic position 1 of 2 - standoff near 25 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack	
mN00865	Toms_Place mosaic position 2 of 2 ~27 cm standoff	3955MH008650001402671ZC00	2671	autofocus sub-frame for target Toms_Place - mosaic position 2 of 2 - standoff near 27 cm	
		3955MH00865001402672ZC00	2672	target Toms_Place - mosaic position 2 of 2 - standoff near 27 cm	
		3955MH00865001402673ZC00	2673	target Toms_Place - mosaic position 2 of 2 - standoff near 27 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3955MH00865001402674ZC00	2674	target Toms_Place - mosaic position 2 of 2 - standoff near 27 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3955MH00865001402675ZC00	2675	target Toms_Place - mosaic position 2 of 2 - standoff near 27 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3955MH00865001402676ZC00	2676	target Toms_Place - mosaic position 2 of 2 - standoff near 27 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3955MH00865001402677ZC00	2677	target Toms_Place - mosaic position 2 of 2 - standoff near 27 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3955MH00865001402678ZC00	2678	target Toms_Place - mosaic position 2 of 2 - standoff near 27 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3955MH00865001402679ZC00	2679	target Toms_Place - mosaic position 2 of 2 - standoff near 27 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3955MH00865001402680ZC00	2680	target Toms_Place - mosaic position 2 of 2 - standoff near 27 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack	
mN00227	Focus Merges	3955MH002270001402681R00	2681	target Toms_Place - mosaic position 2 of 2 - standoff near 27 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3955 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2673-2680 - best focus image product	
		3955MH002270001402682R00	2682	target Toms_Place - mosaic position 2 of 2 - standoff near 27 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3955 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2673-2680 - range map product	
		3955MH002270001402683R00	2683	target Toms_Place - mosaic position 1 of 2 - standoff near 25 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3955 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2663-2670 - best focus image product	
		3955MH002270001402684R00	2684	target Toms_Place - mosaic position 1 of 2 - standoff near 25 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3955 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2663-2670 - range map product	
		3955MH002270001402685R00	2685	target Sugarloaf - after sol 3953 dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3955 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2653-2660 - best focus image product	
		3955MH002270001402686R00	2686	target Sugarloaf - after sol 3953 dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3955 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2653-2660 - range map product	
		3955MH002270001402687R00	2687	target Sugarloaf - after sol 3953 dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3955 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2643-2650 - best focus image product	
		3955MH002270001402688R00	2688	target Sugarloaf - after sol 3953 dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3955 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2643-2650 - range map product	
		3955MH002270001402689R00	2689	target Sugarloaf - after sol 3953 dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3955 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2633-2640 - best focus image product	
		3955MH002270001402690R00	2690	target Sugarloaf - after sol 3953 dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3955 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2633-2640 - range map product	

updated: 02_October_2023

Sol 3960 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	04-Sep-2012/04-Sep-2012
camera position	4
total parent images	25
focus merges performed	2
total focus merge products	4
total parent images + focus merge products	29

MAHLI imaged the target Silver_Spur and the REMS UV Sensor. The focus stack images were also merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00190	Silver_Spur ~25 cm standoff	3960MH00190001402691C00	2691	autoFocus sub-frame for target Silver_Spur - standoff near 25 cm
		3960MH00190001402692C00	2692	target Silver_Spur - standoff near 25 cm
mN00182	Silver_Spur stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3960MH00182001402693C00	2693	autoFocus sub-frame for target Silver_Spur - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3960MH00182001402694C00	2694	target Silver_Spur - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3960MH00182001402695C00	2695	target Silver_Spur - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3960MH00182001402696C00	2696	target Silver_Spur - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3960MH00182001402697C00	2697	target Silver_Spur - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3960MH00182001402698C00	2698	target Silver_Spur - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3960MH00182001402699C00	2699	target Silver_Spur - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3960MH00182001402700C00	2700	target Silver_Spur - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3960MH00182001402701C00	2701	target Silver_Spur - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3960MH00182001402702C00	2702	target Silver_Spur - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00182	Silver_Spur stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3960MH00182001402703C00	2703	autoFocus sub-frame for target Silver_Spur - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3960MH00182001402704C00	2704	target Silver_Spur - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3960MH00182001402705C00	2705	target Silver_Spur - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3960MH00182001402706C00	2706	target Silver_Spur - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3960MH00182001402707C00	2707	target Silver_Spur - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3960MH00182001402708C00	2708	target Silver_Spur - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3960MH00182001402709C00	2709	target Silver_Spur - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3960MH00182001402710C00	2710	target Silver_Spur - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3960MH00182001402711C00	2711	target Silver_Spur - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3960MH00182001402712C00	2712	target Silver_Spur - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00095	REMS UV sensor ~15 cm standoff	3960MH00095001402713C00	2713	autoFocus sub-frame for REMS UV sensor - characterize dust accumulation
		3960MH00095001402714C00	2714	REMS UV sensor - characterize dust accumulation
mN00265	Focus Merges	3960MH00265001402715R00	2715	target Silver_Spur - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3960 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2705-2712 - best focus image product
		3960MH00265001402716S00	2716	target Silver_Spur - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3960 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2705-2712 - range map product
		3960MH00265001402717R00	2717	target Silver_Spur - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3960 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2693-2702 - best focus image product
		3960MH00265001402718S00	2718	target Silver_Spur - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3960 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2693-2702 - range map product

updated: 31_October_2023

Sol 3962 - MAHLI Images

		acquired/performed date(s)	28-Sep-23	
		camera position	55	Image ID:
		total parent images:	4	black - best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange - only a thumbnail has been received
		focus merges performed:	4	CDPID:
		total focus merge products:	8	Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels
		total parent images + focus merge products:	64	
summary of MAHLI activities: MAHLI imaged the targets Burnt_Mountain and Blackcap_Mountain as well as the MAHLI and APXS calibration targets. The focus stack images were also merged.				
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00190	Burnt_Mountain before DRT ~25 cm standoff	3962MH0019000140271900	2719	autofocus sub-frame for target Burnt_Mountain - before dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
		3962MH0019000140272000	2720	target Burnt_Mountain - before dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
mN00173	Burnt_Mountain before DRT stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3962MH0017300140271100	2721	autofocus sub-frame for target Burnt_Mountain - before dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3962MH0017300140272200	2722	target Burnt_Mountain - before dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3962MH0017300140273300	2723	target Burnt_Mountain - before dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3962MH0017300140274400	2724	target Burnt_Mountain - before dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3962MH0017300140275500	2725	target Burnt_Mountain - before dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3962MH0017300140276600	2726	target Burnt_Mountain - before dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3962MH0017300140277700	2727	target Burnt_Mountain - before dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3962MH0017300140278800	2728	target Burnt_Mountain - before dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3962MH0017300140279900	2729	target Burnt_Mountain - before dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3962MH0017300140273000	2730	target Burnt_Mountain - before dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00173	Burnt_Mountain before DRT stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3962MH0017300140273100	2731	autofocus sub-frame for target Burnt_Mountain - before dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3962MH0017300140273200	2732	target Burnt_Mountain - before dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3962MH0017300140273300	2733	target Burnt_Mountain - before dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3962MH0017300140273400	2734	target Burnt_Mountain - before dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3962MH0017300140273500	2735	target Burnt_Mountain - before dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3962MH0017300140273600	2736	target Burnt_Mountain - before dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3962MH0017300140273700	2737	target Burnt_Mountain - before dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3962MH0017300140273800	2738	target Burnt_Mountain - before dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3962MH0017300140273900	2739	target Burnt_Mountain - before dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3962MH0017300140274000	2740	target Burnt_Mountain - before dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00190	Blackcap_Mountain ~25 cm standoff	3962MH0019000140274100	2741	autofocus sub-frame for target Blackcap_Mountain - standoff near 25 cm
		3962MH0019000140274200	2742	target Blackcap_Mountain - standoff near 25 cm
mN00224	Blackcap_Mountain stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3962MH0022400140274300	2743	autofocus sub-frame for target Blackcap_Mountain - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3962MH0022400140274400	2744	target Blackcap_Mountain - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3962MH0022400140274500	2745	target Blackcap_Mountain - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3962MH0022400140274600	2746	target Blackcap_Mountain - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3962MH0022400140274700	2747	target Blackcap_Mountain - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3962MH0022400140274800	2748	target Blackcap_Mountain - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3962MH0022400140274900	2749	target Blackcap_Mountain - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3962MH0022400140275000	2750	target Blackcap_Mountain - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3962MH0022400140275100	2751	target Blackcap_Mountain - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3962MH0022400140275200	2752	target Blackcap_Mountain - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00224	Blackcap_Mountain stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3962MH0022400140275300	2753	autofocus sub-frame for target Blackcap_Mountain - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3962MH0022400140275400	2754	target Blackcap_Mountain - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3962MH0022400140275500	2755	target Blackcap_Mountain - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3962MH0022400140275600	2756	target Blackcap_Mountain - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3962MH0022400140275700	2757	target Blackcap_Mountain - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3962MH0022400140275800	2758	target Blackcap_Mountain - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3962MH0022400140275900	2759	target Blackcap_Mountain - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3962MH0022400140276000	2760	target Blackcap_Mountain - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3962MH0022400140276100	2761	target Blackcap_Mountain - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3962MH0022400140276200	2762	target Blackcap_Mountain - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00371	MAHLI cal target - centered on bar target ~5 cm working distance	3962MH0037100140276300	2763	autofocus sub-frame for MAHLI calibration target - bar target - near 5 cm working distance
		3962MH0037100140276400	2764	MAHLI calibration target - bar target - near 5 cm working distance
mN00372	MAHLI cal target - centered on cent target ~5 cm working distance	3962MH0037200140276500	2765	autofocus sub-frame for MAHLI calibration target - cent target - near 5 cm working distance
		3962MH0037200140276600	2766	MAHLI calibration target - cent target - near 5 cm working distance
mN00374	MAHLI cal target - wheel + surface 30 cm working distance from target	3962MH0037400140276700	2767	autofocus sub-frame for MAHLI calibration target and wheel and Mars surface - calibration target near 30 cm working distance - focus on calibration target
		3962MH0037400140276800	2768	MAHLI calibration target and wheel and Mars surface - calibration target near 30 cm working distance - focus on calibration target
		3962MH0037400140276900	2769	MAHLI calibration target and wheel and Mars surface - calibration target near 30 cm working distance - manual focus at infinity
mN00373	APXS cal target ~5 cm standoff	3962MH0037300140277000	2770	autofocus sub-frame for APXS calibration target - standoff near 5 cm
		3962MH0037300140277100	2771	APXS calibration target - standoff near 5 cm
mN00153	Focus Merges	3962MH0015300140277200	2772	target Blackcap_Mountain - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3960 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2755-2762 - best focus image product
		3962MH0015300140277300	2773	target Blackcap_Mountain - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3960 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2755-2762 - range map product
		3962MH0015300140277400	2774	target Blackcap_Mountain - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3960 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2745-2752 - best focus image product
		3962MH0015300140277500	2775	target Blackcap_Mountain - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3960 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2745-2752 - range map product
		3962MH0015300140277600	2776	target Burnt_Mountain - before dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3960 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2733-2740 - best focus image product
		3962MH0015300140277700	2777	target Burnt_Mountain - before dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3960 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2733-2740 - range map product
		3962MH0015300140277800	2778	target Burnt_Mountain - before dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3960 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2723-2730 - best focus image product
		3962MH0015300140277900	2779	target Burnt_Mountain - before dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3960 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2723-2730 - range map product

mNH00163	Focus Merge	3964MH00163000140284900	2844	target White_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3964 with MEL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2838-2843 - best focus image product
		3964MH00163000140284500	2845	target White_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3964 with MEL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2838-2843 - range map product
		3964MH00163000140284600	2846	target White_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3964 with MEL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2826-2833 - best focus image product
		3964MH00163000140284700	2847	target White_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3964 with MEL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2826-2833 - range map product
		3964MH00163000140284800	2848	target White_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3964 with MEL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2816-2823 - best focus image product
		3964MH00163000140284900	2849	target White_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3964 with MEL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2816-2823 - range map product
		3964MH00163000140285000	2850	target Cloudripper - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3964 with MEL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2804-2811 - best focus image product
		3964MH00163000140285100	2851	target Cloudripper - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3964 with MEL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2804-2811 - range map product
		3964MH00163000140285200	2852	target Cloudripper - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3964 with MEL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2794-2801 - best focus image product
		3964MH00163000140285300	2853	target Cloudripper - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3964 with MEL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2794-2801 - range map product
		3964MH00163000140285400	2854	target Cloudripper - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3964 with MEL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2784-2791 - best focus image product
		3964MH00163000140285500	2855	target Cloudripper - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3964 with MEL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2784-2791 - range map product

updated: 04_October_2023

Sol 3966 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s):	3-Oct-23
camera position:	0
total parent images:	45
focus merges performed:	0
total focus merge products:	0
total parent images + focus merge products:	45

MAHLI imaged the DRT brushed target *Burnt_Mountain* and the target *Bearpaw_Meadow*.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_E_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00190	Burnt_Mountain before DRT ~24 cm standoff	3966MH00190001402856C0D	2856	autofocus sub-frame for target <i>Burnt_Mountain</i> - before dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 24 cm
		3966MH00190001402857C0D	2857	target <i>Burnt_Mountain</i> - before dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 24 cm
mN00122	Burnt_Mountain before DRT ~45 mm standoff	3966MH00122001402858C0D	2858	autofocus sub-frame for target <i>Burnt_Mountain</i> - before dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 45 mm
		3966MH00122001402859C0D	2859	target <i>Burnt_Mountain</i> - before dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 45 mm
mN00190	Burnt_Mountain after DRT ~24 cm standoff	3966MH00190001402860C0D	2860	autofocus sub-frame for target <i>Burnt_Mountain</i> - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 24 cm
		3966MH00190001402861C0D	2861	target <i>Burnt_Mountain</i> - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 24 cm
mN00168	Burnt_Mountain after DRT stereo-1 ~45 mm standoff	3966MH00168001402862C0D	2862	autofocus sub-frame for target <i>Burnt_Mountain</i> - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm
		3966MH00168001402863C0D	2863	target <i>Burnt_Mountain</i> - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm
		3966MH00168001402864C0D	2864	target <i>Burnt_Mountain</i> - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3966MH00168001402865C0D	2865	target <i>Burnt_Mountain</i> - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3966MH00168001402866C0D	2866	target <i>Burnt_Mountain</i> - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3966MH00168001402867C0D	2867	target <i>Burnt_Mountain</i> - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3966MH00168001402868C0D	2868	target <i>Burnt_Mountain</i> - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3966MH00168001402869C0D	2869	target <i>Burnt_Mountain</i> - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3966MH00168001402870C0D	2870	target <i>Burnt_Mountain</i> - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3966MH00168001402871C0D	2871	target <i>Burnt_Mountain</i> - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00168	Burnt_Mountain after DRT stereo-2 ~45 mm standoff	3966MH00168001402872C0D	2872	autofocus sub-frame for target <i>Burnt_Mountain</i> - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
		3966MH00168001402873C0D	2873	target <i>Burnt_Mountain</i> - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
		3966MH00168001402874C0D	2874	target <i>Burnt_Mountain</i> - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3966MH00168001402875C0D	2875	target <i>Burnt_Mountain</i> - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3966MH00168001402876C0D	2876	target <i>Burnt_Mountain</i> - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3966MH00168001402877C0D	2877	target <i>Burnt_Mountain</i> - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3966MH00168001402878C0D	2878	target <i>Burnt_Mountain</i> - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3966MH00168001402879C0D	2879	target <i>Burnt_Mountain</i> - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3966MH00168001402880C0D	2880	target <i>Burnt_Mountain</i> - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3966MH00168001402881C0D	2881	target <i>Burnt_Mountain</i> - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00743	Burnt_Mountain after DRT ~5 mm standoff	3966MH00743001402882C0D	2882	autofocus sub-frame for target <i>Burnt_Mountain</i> - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm
		3966MH00743001402883C0D	2883	target <i>Burnt_Mountain</i> - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm
		3966MH00743001402884C0D	2884	target <i>Burnt_Mountain</i> - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3966MH00743001402885C0D	2885	target <i>Burnt_Mountain</i> - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3966MH00743001402886C0D	2886	target <i>Burnt_Mountain</i> - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3966MH00743001402887C0D	2887	target <i>Burnt_Mountain</i> - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3966MH00743001402888C0D	2888	target <i>Burnt_Mountain</i> - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3966MH00743001402889C0D	2889	target <i>Burnt_Mountain</i> - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3966MH00743001402890C0D	2890	target <i>Burnt_Mountain</i> - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3966MH00743001402891C0D	2891	target <i>Burnt_Mountain</i> - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00168	Bearpaw_Meadow ~5 cm standoff	3966MH00168001402892C0D	2892	autofocus sub-frame for target <i>Bearpaw_Meadow</i> - standoff near 5 cm
		3966MH00168001402893C0D	2893	target <i>Bearpaw_Meadow</i> - standoff near 5 cm
		3966MH00168001402894C0D	2894	target <i>Bearpaw_Meadow</i> - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3966MH00168001402895C0D	2895	target <i>Bearpaw_Meadow</i> - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3966MH00168001402896C0D	2896	target <i>Bearpaw_Meadow</i> - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3966MH00168001402897C0D	2897	target <i>Bearpaw_Meadow</i> - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3966MH00168001402898C0D	2898	target <i>Bearpaw_Meadow</i> - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3966MH00168001402899C0D	2899	target <i>Bearpaw_Meadow</i> - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3966MH00168001402900C0D	2900	target <i>Bearpaw_Meadow</i> - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3966MH00168001402901C0D	2901	target <i>Bearpaw_Meadow</i> - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack

updated: 04_October_2023

Sol 3967 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s):	4-Oct-23
camera position:	0
total parent images:	0
focus merges performed:	4
total focus merge products:	8
total parent images + focus merge products:	8

Image ID:
 black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CDPID:
 Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities: Focus stack images from Sol 3966 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
m1N00133	Focus Merges	3967MH001530001402902900	2902	target Bearpaw_Meadow - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3966 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2894-2901 - best focus image product
		3967MH001530001402903500	2903	target Bearpaw_Meadow - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3966 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2894-2901 - range map product
		3967MH001530001402904900	2904	target Burnt_Mountain - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3966 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2884-2891 - best focus image product
		3967MH001530001402905500	2905	target Burnt_Mountain - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3966 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2884-2891 - range map product
		3967MH001530001402906900	2906	target Burnt_Mountain - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3966 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2874-2881 - best focus image product
		3967MH001530001402907500	2907	target Burnt_Mountain - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3966 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2874-2881 - range map product
		3967MH001530001402908900	2908	target Burnt_Mountain - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3966 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2864-2871 - best focus image product
		3967MH001530001402909500	2909	target Burnt_Mountain - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3966 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2864-2871 - range map product

updated: 09_October_2023

Sol 3968 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	5-Oct-23
camera position	0
total parent images	54
focus merges performed	0
total focus merge products	0
total parent images + focus merge products	54

MAHLI imaged the targets Helen_Lake and Marion_Peak.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00190	Helen_Lake before DRT ~25 cm standoff	3968MH00190001402910C00	2910	autofocus sub-frame for target Helen_Lake - before dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
		3968MH00190001402911C00	2911	target Helen_Lake - before dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
mN00182	Helen_Lake before DRT stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3968MH00182001402912C00	2912	autofocus sub-frame for target Helen_Lake - before dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3968MH00182001402913C00	2913	target Helen_Lake - before dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3968MH00182001402914C00	2914	target Helen_Lake - before dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3968MH00182001402915C00	2915	target Helen_Lake - before dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3968MH00182001402916C00	2916	target Helen_Lake - before dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3968MH00182001402917C00	2917	target Helen_Lake - before dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3968MH00182001402918C00	2918	target Helen_Lake - before dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3968MH00182001402919C00	2919	target Helen_Lake - before dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3968MH00182001402920C00	2920	target Helen_Lake - before dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3968MH00182001402921C00	2921	target Helen_Lake - before dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00182	Helen_Lake before DRT stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3968MH00182001402922C00	2922	autofocus sub-frame for target Helen_Lake - before dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3968MH00182001402923C00	2923	target Helen_Lake - before dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3968MH00182001402924C00	2924	target Helen_Lake - before dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3968MH00182001402925C00	2925	target Helen_Lake - before dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3968MH00182001402926C00	2926	target Helen_Lake - before dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3968MH00182001402927C00	2927	target Helen_Lake - before dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3968MH00182001402928C00	2928	target Helen_Lake - before dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3968MH00182001402929C00	2929	target Helen_Lake - before dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3968MH00182001402930C00	2930	target Helen_Lake - before dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3968MH00182001402931C00	2931	target Helen_Lake - before dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00337	Helen_Lake before DRT ~2 cm standoff	3968MH000337001402932C00	2932	autofocus sub-frame for target Helen_Lake - before dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm
		3968MH000337001402933C00	2933	target Helen_Lake - before dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm
		3968MH000337001402934C00	2934	target Helen_Lake - before dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3968MH000337001402935C00	2935	target Helen_Lake - before dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3968MH000337001402936C00	2936	target Helen_Lake - before dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3968MH000337001402937C00	2937	target Helen_Lake - before dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3968MH000337001402938C00	2938	target Helen_Lake - before dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3968MH000337001402939C00	2939	target Helen_Lake - before dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3968MH000337001402940C00	2940	target Helen_Lake - before dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3968MH000337001402941C00	2941	target Helen_Lake - before dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00190	Marion_Peak ~24 cm standoff	3968MH00190001402942C00	2942	autofocus sub-frame for target Marion_Peak - standoff near 24 cm
		3968MH00190001402943C00	2943	target Marion_Peak - standoff near 24 cm
mN00182	Marion_Peak stereo-1 ~45 mm standoff	3968MH00182001402944C00	2944	autofocus sub-frame for target Marion_Peak - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm
		3968MH00182001402945C00	2945	target Marion_Peak - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm
		3968MH00182001402946C00	2946	target Marion_Peak - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3968MH00182001402947C00	2947	target Marion_Peak - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3968MH00182001402948C00	2948	target Marion_Peak - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3968MH00182001402949C00	2949	target Marion_Peak - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3968MH00182001402950C00	2950	target Marion_Peak - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3968MH00182001402951C00	2951	target Marion_Peak - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3968MH00182001402952C00	2952	target Marion_Peak - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3968MH00182001402953C00	2953	target Marion_Peak - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00182	Marion_Peak stereo-2 ~45 mm standoff	3968MH00182001402954C00	2954	autofocus sub-frame for target Marion_Peak - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
		3968MH00182001402955C00	2955	target Marion_Peak - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
		3968MH00182001402956C00	2956	target Marion_Peak - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3968MH00182001402957C00	2957	target Marion_Peak - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3968MH00182001402958C00	2958	target Marion_Peak - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3968MH00182001402959C00	2959	target Marion_Peak - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3968MH00182001402960C00	2960	target Marion_Peak - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3968MH00182001402961C00	2961	target Marion_Peak - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3968MH00182001402962C00	2962	target Marion_Peak - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3968MH00182001402963C00	2963	target Marion_Peak - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack

updated: 09_October_2023

Sol 3969 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s):	6-Oct-23
camera position:	0
total parent images:	0
focus merges performed:	5
total focus merge products:	10
total parent images + focus merge products:	10

Image ID:
 black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CDPID:
 Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities

Focus stack images from Sol 3968 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00227	Focus Merges	3969MH0002270001402964R00	2964	target Marion_Peak - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3968 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2936-2963 - best focus image product
		3969MH0002270001402965S00	2965	target Marion_Peak - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3968 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2936-2963 - range map product
		3969MH0002270001402966R00	2966	target Marion_Peak - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3968 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2946-2953 - best focus image product
		3969MH0002270001402967S00	2967	target Marion_Peak - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3968 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2946-2953 - range map product
		3969MH0002270001402968R00	2968	target Helen_Lake - before dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3968 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2934-2941 - best focus image product
		3969MH0002270001402969S00	2969	target Helen_Lake - before dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3968 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2934-2941 - range map product
		3969MH0002270001402970R00	2970	target Helen_Lake - before dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3968 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2924-2931 - best focus image product
		3969MH0002270001402971S00	2971	target Helen_Lake - before dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3968 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2924-2931 - range map product
		3969MH0002270001402972R00	2972	target Helen_Lake - before dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3968 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2914-2921 - best focus image product
		3969MH0002270001402973S00	2973	target Helen_Lake - before dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3968 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2914-2921 - range map product

updated: 11_October_2023

Sol 3971 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	8-Oct-23
camera position	13
total parent images	85
focus merges performed	0
total focus merge products	0
total parent images + focus merge products	85

MAHLI imaged the DRT + brushed target Helen_Lake and the targets Feather_Peak and Heart_Lake.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00190	Helen_Lake after DRT ~25 cm standoff	3971MH0019000114029740CD	2974	autofocus sub-frame for target Helen_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
		3971MH0019000114029750CD	2975	target Helen_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
mN00168	Helen_Lake after DRT stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3971MH0016800114029760CD	2976	autofocus sub-frame for target Helen_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3971MH0016800114029770CD	2977	target Helen_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3971MH0016800114029780CD	2978	target Helen_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3971MH0016800114029790CD	2979	target Helen_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3971MH0016800114029800CD	2980	target Helen_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3971MH0016800114029810CD	2981	target Helen_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3971MH0016800114029820CD	2982	target Helen_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3971MH0016800114029830CD	2983	target Helen_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3971MH0016800114029840CD	2984	target Helen_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3971MH0016800114029850CD	2985	target Helen_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00168	Helen_Lake after DRT stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3971MH0016800114029860CD	2986	autofocus sub-frame for target Helen_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3971MH0016800114029870CD	2987	target Helen_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3971MH0016800114029880CD	2988	target Helen_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3971MH0016800114029890CD	2989	target Helen_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3971MH0016800114029900CD	2990	target Helen_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3971MH0016800114029910CD	2991	target Helen_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3971MH0016800114029920CD	2992	target Helen_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3971MH0016800114029930CD	2993	target Helen_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3971MH0016800114029940CD	2994	target Helen_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3971MH0016800114029950CD	2995	target Helen_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00302	Helen_Lake after DRT ~2 cm standoff	3971MH0030200114029960CD	2996	autofocus sub-frame for target Helen_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm
		3971MH0030200114029970CD	2997	target Helen_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm
		3971MH0030200114029980CD	2998	target Helen_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3971MH0030200114029990CD	2999	target Helen_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3971MH0030200114030000CD	3000	target Helen_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3971MH0030200114030010CD	3001	target Helen_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3971MH0030200114030020CD	3002	target Helen_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3971MH0030200114030030CD	3003	target Helen_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3971MH0030200114030040CD	3004	target Helen_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3971MH0030200114030050CD	3005	target Helen_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00190	Feather_Peak ~24 cm standoff	3971MH0019000114030060CD	3006	autofocus sub-frame for target Feather_Peak - standoff near 24 cm
		3971MH0019000114030070CD	3007	target Feather_Peak - standoff near 24 cm
mN00168	Feather_Peak stereo-1 ~4 cm standoff	3971MH0016800114030080CD	3008	autofocus sub-frame for target Feather_Peak - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm
		3971MH0016800114030090CD	3009	target Feather_Peak - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm
		3971MH0016800114030100CD	3010	target Feather_Peak - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3971MH0016800114030110CD	3011	target Feather_Peak - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3971MH0016800114030120CD	3012	target Feather_Peak - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3971MH0016800114030130CD	3013	target Feather_Peak - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3971MH0016800114030140CD	3014	target Feather_Peak - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3971MH0016800114030150CD	3015	target Feather_Peak - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3971MH0016800114030160CD	3016	target Feather_Peak - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3971MH0016800114030170CD	3017	target Feather_Peak - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00168	Feather_Peak stereo-2 ~4 cm standoff	3971MH0016800114030180CD	3018	autofocus sub-frame for target Feather_Peak - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm
		3971MH0016800114030190CD	3019	target Feather_Peak - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm
		3971MH0016800114030200CD	3020	target Feather_Peak - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3971MH0016800114030210CD	3021	target Feather_Peak - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3971MH0016800114030220CD	3022	target Feather_Peak - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3971MH0016800114030230CD	3023	target Feather_Peak - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3971MH0016800114030240CD	3024	target Feather_Peak - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3971MH0016800114030250CD	3025	target Feather_Peak - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3971MH0016800114030260CD	3026	target Feather_Peak - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3971MH0016800114030270CD	3027	target Feather_Peak - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00190	Heart_Lake ~24 cm standoff	3971MH0019000114030280CD	3028	autofocus sub-frame for target Heart_Lake - standoff near 24 cm
		3971MH0019000114030290CD	3029	target Heart_Lake - standoff near 24 cm
mN00168	Heart_Lake stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3971MH0016800114030300CD	3030	autofocus sub-frame for target Heart_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3971MH0016800114030310CD	3031	target Heart_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3971MH0016800114030320CD	3032	target Heart_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3971MH0016800114030330CD	3033	target Heart_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3971MH0016800114030340CD	3034	target Heart_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3971MH0016800114030350CD	3035	target Heart_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3971MH0016800114030360CD	3036	target Heart_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3971MH0016800114030370CD	3037	target Heart_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3971MH0016800114030380CD	3038	target Heart_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3971MH0016800114030390CD	3039	target Heart_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack

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mH00168	Heart_Lake stereo-2 -5 cm standoff	3971MH00168001403040C00	3040	autofocus sub-frame for target Heart_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3971MH00168001403041C00	3041	target Heart_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3971MH00168001403042C00	3042	target Heart_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3971MH00168001403043C00	3043	target Heart_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3971MH00168001403044C00	3044	target Heart_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3971MH00168001403045C00	3045	target Heart_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3971MH00168001403046C00	3046	target Heart_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3971MH00168001403047C00	3047	target Heart_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3971MH00168001403048C00	3048	target Heart_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
3971MH00168001403049C00	3049	target Heart_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mH00743	Heart_Lake -1 cm standoff	3971MH00743001403050C00	3050	autofocus sub-frame for target Heart_Lake - standoff near 1 cm
		3971MH00743001403051C00	3051	target Heart_Lake - standoff near 1 cm
		3971MH00743001403052C00	3052	target Heart_Lake - standoff near 1 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3971MH00743001403053C00	3053	target Heart_Lake - standoff near 1 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3971MH00743001403054C00	3054	target Heart_Lake - standoff near 1 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3971MH00743001403055C00	3055	target Heart_Lake - standoff near 1 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3971MH00743001403056C00	3056	target Heart_Lake - standoff near 1 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3971MH00743001403057C00	3057	target Heart_Lake - standoff near 1 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3971MH00743001403058C00	3058	target Heart_Lake - standoff near 1 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
3971MH00743001403059C00	3059	target Heart_Lake - standoff near 1 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		

updated: 09_October_2023

Sol 3972 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s):	0-04-23
camera position:	0
total parent images:	0
focus merges performed:	8
total focus merge products:	16
total parent images + focus merge products:	16

Image ID:
 black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CDPID:
 Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities: Focus stack images from Sol 3971 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
m1N00170	Focus Merges	3972MH00170001403060R00	3060	target Heart_Lake - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3971 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3052-3059 - best focus image product
		3972MH00170001403061S00	3061	target Heart_Lake - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3971 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3052-3059 - range map product
		3972MH00170001403062R00	3062	target Heart_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3971 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3042-3049 - best focus image product
		3972MH00170001403063S00	3063	target Heart_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3971 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3042-3049 - range map product
		3972MH00170001403064R00	3064	target Heart_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3971 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3032-3039 - best focus image product
		3972MH00170001403065S00	3065	target Heart_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3971 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3032-3039 - range map product
		3972MH00170001403066R00	3066	target Feather_Peak - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3971 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3020-3027 - best focus image product
		3972MH00170001403067S00	3067	target Feather_Peak - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3971 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3020-3027 - range map product
		3972MH00170001403068R00	3068	target Feather_Peak - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3971 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3010-3017 - best focus image product
		3972MH00170001403069S00	3069	target Feather_Peak - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3971 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3010-3017 - range map product
		3972MH00170001403070R00	3070	target Helen_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3971 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2998-3005 - range map product
		3972MH00170001403071S00	3071	target Helen_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3971 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2998-3005 - range map product
		3972MH00170001403072R00	3072	target Helen_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3971 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2988-2995 - best focus image product
		3972MH00170001403073S00	3073	target Helen_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3971 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2988-2995 - range map product
		3972MH00170001403074R00	3074	target Helen_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3971 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2978-2985 - best focus image product
		3972MH00170001403075S00	3075	target Helen_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3971 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2978-2985 - range map product

updated: 13_October_2023

Sol 3975 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	12-Oct-23
camera positions	4
total parent images	48
focus merges performed	4
total focus merge products	8
total parent images + focus merge products	56

MAHLI imaged the intended drill target Sequoia before and after DRT and after a drill bit preload test. The focus stack images were merged as well.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDP	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00190	Sequoia before DRT ~25 cm standoff	3975MH00190001403076CD	3076	autoFocus sub-frame for intended Sequoia drill site - before dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 25 cm
		3975MH00190001403077CD	3077	intended Sequoia drill site - before dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 25 cm
mN00212	Sequoia before DRT APXS spot 2 ~5 cm standoff	3975MH00122001403078CD	3078	autoFocus sub-frame for intended Sequoia drill site - before dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3975MH00122001403079CD	3079	intended Sequoia drill site - before dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm
mN00190	Sequoia after DRT ~25 cm standoff	3975MH00190001403080CD	3080	autoFocus sub-frame for intended Sequoia drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 25 cm
		3975MH00190001403081CD	3081	intended Sequoia drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 25 cm
mN00168	Sequoia after DRT APXS spot 2 stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3975MH00168001403082CD	3082	autoFocus sub-frame for intended Sequoia drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3975MH00168001403083CD	3083	intended Sequoia drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3975MH00168001403084CD	3084	intended Sequoia drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3975MH00168001403085CD	3085	intended Sequoia drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3975MH00168001403086CD	3086	intended Sequoia drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3975MH00168001403087CD	3087	intended Sequoia drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3975MH00168001403088CD	3088	intended Sequoia drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3975MH00168001403089CD	3089	intended Sequoia drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3975MH00168001403090CD	3090	intended Sequoia drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3975MH00168001403091CD	3091	intended Sequoia drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00168	Sequoia after DRT APXS spot 2 stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3975MH00168001403092CD	3092	autoFocus sub-frame for intended Sequoia drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3975MH00168001403093CD	3093	intended Sequoia drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3975MH00168001403094CD	3094	intended Sequoia drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3975MH00168001403095CD	3095	intended Sequoia drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3975MH00168001403096CD	3096	intended Sequoia drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3975MH00168001403097CD	3097	intended Sequoia drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3975MH00168001403098CD	3098	intended Sequoia drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3975MH00168001403099CD	3099	intended Sequoia drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3975MH00168001403100CD	3100	intended Sequoia drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3975MH00168001403101CD	3101	intended Sequoia drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00302	Sequoia after DRT APXS spot 2 ~2 cm standoff	3975MH00302001403102CD	3102	autoFocus sub-frame for intended Sequoia drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 2 cm
		3975MH00302001403103CD	3103	intended Sequoia drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 2 cm
		3975MH00302001403104CD	3104	intended Sequoia drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 2 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3975MH00302001403105CD	3105	intended Sequoia drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 2 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3975MH00302001403106CD	3106	intended Sequoia drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 2 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3975MH00302001403107CD	3107	intended Sequoia drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 2 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3975MH00302001403108CD	3108	intended Sequoia drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 2 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3975MH00302001403109CD	3109	intended Sequoia drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 2 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3975MH00302001403110CD	3110	intended Sequoia drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 2 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3975MH00302001403111CD	3111	intended Sequoia drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 2 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00168	Sequoia after DRT APXS spot 1 ~5 cm standoff	3975MH00168001403112CD	3112	autoFocus sub-frame for intended Sequoia drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3975MH00168001403113CD	3113	intended Sequoia drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3975MH00168001403114CD	3114	intended Sequoia drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3975MH00168001403115CD	3115	intended Sequoia drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3975MH00168001403116CD	3116	intended Sequoia drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3975MH00168001403117CD	3117	intended Sequoia drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3975MH00168001403118CD	3118	intended Sequoia drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3975MH00168001403119CD	3119	intended Sequoia drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3975MH00168001403120CD	3120	intended Sequoia drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3975MH00168001403121CD	3121	intended Sequoia drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00465	Sequoia after DRT after drill bit preload test ~5 cm standoff	3975MH00465001403122CD	3122	autoFocus sub-frame for intended Sequoia drill site - drill bit preload test - image acquired after preload - after sol 3975 dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 35 cm
		3975MH00465001403123CD	3123	intended Sequoia drill site - drill bit preload test - image acquired after preload - after sol 3975 dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 35 cm
mN00153	Focus Merges	3975MH001530014031240D	3124	intended Sequoia drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3975 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3114-3121 - best focus image product
		3975MH001530014031250D	3125	intended Sequoia drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3975 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3114-3121 - range map product
		3975MH001530014031260D	3126	intended Sequoia drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3975 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3104-3111 - best focus image product
		3975MH0015300140312750D	3127	intended Sequoia drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3975 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3104-3111 - range map product
		3975MH001530014031280D	3128	intended Sequoia drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3975 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3094-3101 - best focus image product
		3975MH0015300140312950D	3129	intended Sequoia drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3975 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3094-3101 - range map product
		3975MH001530014031300D	3130	intended Sequoia drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3975 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3084-3091 - best focus image product
		3975MH0015300140313150D	3131	intended Sequoia drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3975 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3084-3091 - range map product

7 Definitions, conventions, and acronyms

7.1 Definitions and conventions

absolute focus stack

A MAHLI focus stack acquired using a commanded (manual) focus setting. The starting focus position (a stepper motor count), and the incremental change in focus position (a stepper motor count interval) between frames in the focus stack, are specified by instrument commanding.

best focus image product

A *focus merge product* created onboard the MAHLI instrument from up to 8 *parent images* acquired as a focus stack. The *best focus image product* is a color JPEG that combines the in-focus (or closest to in-focus) elements of the up to 8 *parent images* into a single image. The onboard focus merge software also creates a *range map product*.

focus merge product

Using the methods described by Edgett *et al.* (2012), *focus merge products* are created onboard the MAHLI instrument from up to 8 *parent images* acquired as a focus stack. Two products are created, a *best focus image product* and a *range map product*.

MAHLI toolframe +X distance

Same as *standoff distance*. See *standoff distance*.

parent and child images

Every MAHLI image has a *parent image*, the picture originally commanded to be acquired. Upon command, the parent image can spawn children (each a *child image*) onboard the instrument. Examples of children include *thumbnail images*, focus merge products, and any version of the image that is compressed differently than the parent (Edgett *et al.* 2012). While a parent can be an image that was compressed during image acquisition, our best practice since landing on Mars has been to acquire and store (onboard the instrument) most MAHLI images in uncompressed 8-bit form. An uncompressed 8-bit parent image can be commanded for compression some time after acquisition and storage, whereas a parent that was compressed at the time of acquisition cannot be further compressed onboard the instrument. When a parent is stored onboard in uncompressed form, it can be used to create multiple versions of the image, each time with a different compression scheme, for downlink to Earth. Thus, if the image received is over-compressed, we have the option to retrieve it again (as many times as necessary) in a less compressed form. Indeed, the majority of MAHLI images received from Mars have been losslessly compressed children of an uncompressed, 8-bit parent.

range

Used here in the context of describing a focus merge range map product, this term refers to the distance between the front lens element and in-focus elements of the imaged subject in a given MAHLI focus merge product. As each MAHLI focus stack is acquired at a fixed *working distance*, the range denotes the distance between the camera and the relief elements of the target (*i.e.*, subject), as indicated by grayscale pixel values (data number, DN) in the range map product.

range map product

A grayscale JPEG image *focus merge product* created onboard the MAHLI instrument from up to 8 *parent images* acquired as a focus stack. The *range map product* accompanies a *best focus image product*. The grayscale pixel values (data number, DN) can be correlated with knowledge of instrument focus, *working distance*, *range*, and pixel scale.

RATIONALE_DESC

The term, RATIONALE_DESC, comes from the NASA PDS archivists. The RATIONALE_DESC for a given MAHLI image is a text description of the rationale or purpose behind the acquisition of a given MAHLI parent image or onboard focus merge product. Each parent image RATIONALE_DESC provides information that the MAHLI team desired to communicate to data users, such as the intended image target, intended working or standoff distance, intended purpose of the image (e.g., stereo, mosaic, autofocus sub-frame, range-finding), image position in a focus stack, as well as information regarding how the image supports observations made by other MSL science instruments, especially APXS and ChemCam. The RATIONALE_DESC for a focus merge product tells the user which images were merged (on what sol they were acquired and images of which CDPIDs were merged), as well as the focus merge product type (best focus or range map product).

relative focus stack

A MAHLI focus stack acquired using a starting focus position determined by a preceding instrument command. Usually, this is a focus setting based upon a focus position determined by a preceding autofocus command. The incremental change in focus position (a stepper motor count interval) between frames in the focus stack is specified by instrument commanding.

RP distance

RP refers to Rover Planners, the personnel who drive the Curiosity rover and operate its robotic arm. RP distance is equivalent to *standoff distance*. See definition of *standoff distance*.

sol

A Martian day; duration of ~1.027 Earth days.

Sol

A specific Martian sol during the MSL Curiosity mission. Because it landed during local afternoon, the sol that Curiosity arrived on Mars was designated Sol 0 and the first full sol after landing was Sol 1.

standoff distance

Also known as the MAHLI *toolframe distance* and *RP distance*, this is range between the subject photographed and the Y, Z plane defined by the two MAHLI contact sensor probe tips when they are not in contact with a surface. In the MAHLI toolframe, the X axis is equivalent to the instrument's optic (z) axis; the distance between the Y, Z plane and the subject is +X; the – X-axis goes from the Y, Z plane into the camera. *Standoff distance* and *RP distance* are equivalent to the +X MAHLI toolframe distance. MAHLI *standoff distance* is 1.9 cm less than *working distance*.

thumbnail images

Reduced-size versions of MAHLI *parent images* and *focus merge products*, approximately 1/8th size in terms of pixel dimensions. Under most circumstances, a *thumbnail image* is returned to Earth for every *parent image* acquired or *focus merge product* created, whether a full-size version of the *parent image* (or a *child image*) or *focus merge product* is returned or not.

working distance

A photography term that refers to the range between the front lens element of a camera and the subject imaged. MAHLI working distance is 1.9 cm greater than the toolframe (also known as standoff or RP) distance.

7.2 Acronyms

APXS

Alpha Particle X-ray Spectrometer (science instrument aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

CDPID or MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID

Each MAHLI parent image acquired or onboard focus merge product created and stored in the instrument's DEA flash memory is assigned a Camera Data Product ID (CDPID). This identifier, plus the time at which (or sol on which) the data were acquired, uniquely identify each image. The CDPID and sol are incorporated into the image ID. Data acquired by the camera but not stored in the DEA have less unique CDPIDs; these acquisitions have generally been rare and easy for the operations team to track (*i.e.*, 12 such images were obtained during Interplanetary Cruise, only one such image was obtained during the first 1000 sols of operations on Mars).

ChemCam

Chemistry Camera; Laser Induced Breakdown Spectrometer (LIBS) and Remote Microscopic Imager (RMI) (science instrument suite aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

CheMin

Chemistry and Mineralogy x-ray diffraction (XRD) and x-ray fluorescence (XRF) sample analysis investigation (science instrument aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

CHIMRA

Collection and Handling for Interior Martian Rock Analysis (sample handling and processing subsystem on Curiosity's robotic arm)

DEA

Digital Electronics Assembly, the MAHLI electronics housed inside Curiosity's rover body.

DN

data number (image pixel value)

DOF

image depth of field

DRT

Dust Removal Tool (wire brush tool on Curiosity's robotic arm)

EDR

Experiment Data Record

Hazcam(s)

Hazard cameras (engineering cameras aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

ID or image ID

Image identifier (NASA PDS image identifier for MAHLI images and focus merge products).

JPL-Caltech

Jet Propulsion Laboratory, California Institute of Technology, Pasadena, California, USA

MAHLI

Mars Hand Lens Imager (science instrument aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

MARDI

Mars Descent Imager (science instrument aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

Mastcam-34 (also M-34 and M34)

34 mm focal length Mast Camera (science instrument aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

Mastcam-100 (also M-100 and M100)

100 mm focal length Mast Camera (science instrument aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

MSL

Mars Science Laboratory

MSSS

Malin Space Science Systems, San Diego, California, USA

NASA

National Aeronautics and Space Administration (USA space agency)

Navcam(s)

Navigation cameras (engineering cameras aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

PDS

Planetary Data System (NASA planetary science data archives)

QMS

Quadrupole Mass Spectrometer (part of the SAM instrument suite aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

RDR

Reduced Data Record

REMS

Rover Environment and Monitoring Station (science instrument suite aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

SAM

Sample Analysis at Mars (science instrument suite aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

TLS

Tunable Laser Spectrometer (part of the SAM instrument suite aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

USA

United States of America

UTC

Coordinated Universal Time

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